

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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这些会议文结合了会议的材料 – 研究论文和科学工作者的论文报告。它考察了职业化人格的技术和社会学问题。一些文章涉及人格职业化研究问题的理论和方法论方法和原则。

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海水中船舶钢和碳钢腐蚀破坏的特征和差异
**FEATURES AND DIFFERENCES OF CORROSION DESTRUCTION
OF SHIPBUILDING AND CARBON STEELS IN SEAWATER**

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摘要: 研究表明, 船用钢材和碳钢的腐蚀破坏最能用腐蚀损失 d (μm) 随时间变化的抛物线关系来精确描述。研究还表明, 腐蚀速率 τ ($\mu\text{m}/\text{年}$) 在初始阶段达到最大值——船用钢材为前1.5年, 碳钢St3kp为前0.2年。

关键词: 海洋腐蚀, 船用钢材, 碳钢, 模型表示, 非线性估计。

Abstract. *It has been shown that the corrosion-induced destruction of both shipbuilding steels and carbon steel is most accurately described by a parabolic dependence of corrosion loss d (μm) on time. It is demonstrated that the corrosion rate τ ($\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$) reaches its maximum during the initial period — the first 1.5 years for shipbuilding steels and 0.2 years for carbon steel St3kp.*

Keywords: *marine corrosion, shipbuilding steels, carbon steel. model representations, nonlinear estimation.*

Corrosion of shipbuilding steels

Samples of shipbuilding steel grades A, AH, B, and DH were subjected to corrosion testing for an extended period (up to 5 years). Square samples (100×100 mm) with a thickness of 6 mm (sample surface area $S = 223 \text{ cm}^2$) were treated in a rust removal solution according to GOST 9.907-83 (100 ml concentrated $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + 5 \text{ g CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2$ per 1 L of water), rinsed, dried, weighed, and secured on frames in seawater at a depth of 3 m. Data of corrosion tests (values of corrosion losses d , average d_{avg} , (μm) and degree of conversion $\alpha = \frac{d}{d_{\text{max}}}$) are presented in Table 1.

Under natural marine conditions [1÷3], corrosion losses $d(t)$ obey a parabolic dependence (Figure 1 *a*), with the corrosion rate $\tau = d/t$ being maximal during the initial period and subsequently gradually decreasing (Figure 1 *b*).

For the statistical processing of experimental data, the mathematical expression of the model for the degree of conversion α is utilized in the form of the Avrami–Erofeev equation:

$$\alpha = 1 - \exp(-k \cdot t^n), \quad (1)$$

where k — the reaction rate constant; n — the exponent, which can be defined as the sum of the number of stages in the formation of nuclei of the reaction β and the directions of nuclei growth λ [4]:

$$n = \beta + \lambda. \quad (2)$$

Table 1. Corrosion test data of shipbuilding steels *A*, *B*, *AH*, and *DH* [3]

Exposure; <i>t</i> , years	Corrosion losses of shipbuilding steels; <i>d</i> , microns				Average values of corrosion losses; <i>d</i> _{avg} , microns	Extent of transformation; $\alpha = \frac{d}{d_{\max}}$
	A	B	AH	DH		
0.44	43	86	48	058	59	0.217
0.94	130	52	95	120	99	0.364
1.40	128	149	156	221	164	0.603
2.03	162	148	147	171	163	0.599
2.41	171	162	162	188	171	0.629
3.03	207	216	192	248	216	0.794
3.36	184	220	213	230	212	0.779
4.03	234	264	249	269	254	0.934
4.35	260	285	256	286	270	0.993
4.97	252	299	238	293	272	1

The analysis of the dependence of the transformation degree on the exposure duration of samples in seawater, performed by nonlinear estimation using the Statistica software, reveals a parabolic relationship $\alpha = 1 - \exp(-0.503 \cdot t^{1.059}) \approx 1 - \exp(-0.5 \cdot t)$ with a correlation coefficient $R = 0.9691$ (Figure 2).

In the case of applying the model $\alpha = 1 - \exp(-k \cdot t^2)$ The correlation is weaker: $R = 0.8582$.

The dependence for shipbuilding steels of the correlation coefficient R and the constant k on n within the interval $n(1;2)$ is presented in Figure 3. The best fit occurs at a value of n close to 1; consequently, the parabolic relationship of corrosion loss values d over time most accurately describes the corrosion destruction process of shipbuilding steels in seawater.

Figure 1. Averaged values for shipbuilding steels of grades *A*, *AH*, *B*, and *DH* obtained during corrosion tests: corrosion losses (a) and corrosion rates (b).

Figure 2. Relationship of the degree of conversion $\alpha = \frac{d}{d_\infty}$ to time ($R = 0.9691$).

Figure 3. Dependence of the correlation coefficient R (a) and the constant k (b) on n for shipbuilding steels

Corrosion of carbon steel St3kp

Rectangular cathode samples (80×50 mm) of St3kp steel with a thickness of 1.5 mm (surface area $S = 80 \text{ cm}^2$) were subjected to testing for six months. The anode was a 25×160×2.0 mm plate made of platinized titanium Ti (Pt). The surface preparation of samples was performed similarly to the procedure and sequence applied to shipbuilding steel specimens: rust removal, washing, drying, and weighing. Cathodic polarization of steel samples was conducted during the summer period at temperatures ranging from +10 to +25 °C in seawater with salinity $SAL = 30 \text{ ‰}$ and the following ionic composition: $[Ca^{2+}] = 8.85$; $[HCO_3^-] = 2.0$; $[Mg^{2+}] = 46.2$; $[SO_4^{2-}] = 24.2 \text{ mmol/L}$. During each sampling interval, the specimens were cleaned of attached marine organisms and their metabolic products, then rust was removed. The samples were subsequently washed, dried, weighed, and corrosion loss values were calculated. The data obtained are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Corrosion test data of St3kp steel [3]

Exposure		Corrosion loss; $d, \mu\text{m}$	Corrosion rate; $\tau = \frac{d}{t}, \frac{\mu\text{m}}{\text{year}}$	Extent of transformation $\alpha = \frac{d}{d_x}$
t, days	t, years			
30	0.0821	16.3	198	0.351
37	0.101	20.3	201	0.437

Exposure		Corrosion loss; $d, \mu\text{m}$	Corrosion rate; $\tau = \frac{d}{t}, \frac{\mu\text{m}}{\text{year}}$	Extent of transformation $\alpha = \frac{d}{d_{\infty}}$
t, days	t, years			
67	0.186	29.0	156	0.624
103	0.282	36.0	128	0.774
113	0.310	39.4	127	0.847
134	0.367	43.0	117	0.925
179	0.490	46.5	95	1

Figure 4. Average values for carbon steel St3kp during corrosion tests: corrosion losses (a) and corrosion rate (b).

As in the case of shipbuilding steels, the corrosion losses $d(t)$ obey a parabolic dependence (Figure 4 a), and the corrosion rate $\tau = d/t$ is maximal during the initial period and then gradually decreases (Figure 4 б). Nonetheless, there is a significant difference: the corrosion destruction of carbon steel proceeds much more rapidly.

Analysis of the dependence (1) of the degree of conversion on the electrolysis time using the nonlinear estimation method in the Statistica software yields a parabolic relationship of the form $\alpha = 1 - \exp(-6,908 \cdot t^{1.17}) \approx 1 - \exp(-6,9 \cdot t^{1.1})$, where the correlation coefficient for carbon steel exhibits a higher value than that for shipbuilding steels (Figure 5):

Figure 5. Relationship of the degree of conversion $\alpha = \frac{d}{d_c}$ over time ($R = 0.9919$).

Figure 6. Dependence of the correlation coefficient R (a) and the constant k (b) on n for carbon steel St3kp.

Conclusions

For shipbuilding steels, the transition from the parabolic dependence model to the sigmoidal dependence model $\alpha_1 = 1 - \exp(-k_1 \cdot t) \rightarrow \alpha_2 = 1 - \exp(-k_2 \cdot t^2)$ is accompanied by a decrease in the correlation coefficient from $R_1 = 0.9682$ to $R_2 = 0.8582$, passing through a maximum point $R_{\max} = 0.9691$ at $n = 1.059$, which lies in close proximity corresponding to the parabolic dependence. In the case of carbon steel, a similar transition results in a reduction of the correlation coefficient from $R_1 = 0.9883$ to $R_2 = 0.8695$, passing through a maximum point $R_{\max} = 0.9919$ at $n = 1.117$; that is, this point within the interval $n(1;2)$ is located slightly to the right of the corresponding value for shipbuilding steels.

There is a considerable difference in the values of the rate constants k of corrosion destruction; at the points R_{\max} , the corrosion rate of carbon steel exceeds the corresponding value for shipbuilding steels by more than an order of magnitude:

$$\frac{k_{\text{yez.cm.}}}{k_{\text{cy}\theta\text{.cm.}}} = \frac{-6,908}{-0,503} = 13,7. \quad (8)$$

The greater variability in corrosion loss data for shipbuilding steels compared to St3kp steel, reflected in a lower correlation coefficient, may result from seasonality during prolonged exposure, variations in marine biological activity across different years, as well as other influencing factors.

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对重度合并创伤性脑损伤儿童自主神经张力调节昼夜节律的比较评估
**COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM OF
AUTONOMIC TONE REGULATION IN CHILDREN WITH SEVERE
COMBINED TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY**

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摘要：本研究基于血流动力学监测结果，分析了2016–2021年间在俄罗斯斯紧急与放射医学科学中心住院的36名儿童（第一组）和2023–2024年间接受治疗的35名儿童（第二组）的严重联合性颅脑损伤病例，结果显示：在2022–2024年间接受颅内和颅外联合手术的儿童中，调节自主神经张力的昼夜节律（ CR_{AT} ）平均值显著升高——术后第4天升高60%，术后第11–16天升高60–110%。这种升高可能与继发性并发症（如感染和呼吸机相关性肺炎）有关，主要源于更严重的原发性颅脑损伤，导致受损脑结构（负责适应性过程）的调节功能受到抑制。这与受损脑组织调节功能不足导致的多种代偿机制失效有关。在所有亚组中，第一组儿童均观察到交感神经活动增强对心输出量的显著直接刺激作用，且与总外周血管阻力呈负相关，这与急性创伤后时期高动力循环类型的形成相一致。在整个重症监护室（ICU）治疗期间，TBI 的变化与心肌耗氧量（MOD）的变化之间存在直接相关性。

关键词：昼夜节律，自主神经张力，严重合并性创伤性脑损伤，儿童。

Abstract. *Based on the study of hemodynamic monitoring results, 36 children (group 1) hospitalized at the Russian Scientific Center for Emergency and Radiation Medicine in 2016-2021, and 35 children (group 2) treated in 2023-2024 for severe combined traumatic brain injury were analyzed, revealing the following. In children undergoing combined cranial and extracranial surgeries during 2022-2024, a significant increase in the mesor of the circadian rhythm regulating*

autonomic tone (CR AT) was observed — by 60% on day 4, and by 60-110% on days 11-16. This increase was likely associated with secondary complications such as infection and ventilator-associated pneumonia, primarily stemming from more severe primary traumatic brain injury, which caused a consequent inhibition of the regulatory functions of the damaged brain structures responsible for adaptive processes. This was related to a failure of multiple compensatory mechanisms due to insufficiency of the regulatory functions of the injured brain. A statistically significant direct stimulatory effect of increased sympathetic activity on cardiac output and a negative correlation with total peripheral vascular resistance were observed in children of group 1 across all subgroups, consistent with the formation of a hyperdynamic circulation type in the acute post-traumatic period. A direct correlation between changes in TBI and myocardial oxygen demand (MOD) was noted throughout the entire intensive care unit (ICU) treatment period.

Keywords: *circadian rhythm, autonomic tone, severe combined traumatic brain injury, children.*

Relevance. The autonomic nervous system receives input from various regions of the central nervous system (CNS) involved in processing and integrating information about the state of the body's internal environment and the effects of stimuli from the external environment. These structures include the hypothalamus, nucleus of the solitary tract, reticular formation, amygdala, hippocampus, and olfactory cortex. The autonomic nervous system (ANS) is a key factor modulating cardiac function during the acute phase of cerebral circulation disorders. Disturbance of the dynamic organization of the ANS, understood as the interaction and reciprocal modulation of the sympathetic and parasympathetic neuroeffector mechanisms regulating cardiac activity, contributes to maladaptive responses, thereby increasing myocardial sensitivity to damaging agents. In patients with varying courses of the pathological process, different variants of autonomic regulation changes and unequal degrees of their severity are observed, which enables the use of assessment of alterations in both divisions of the ANS to predict disease severity and outcome. In diseases or dysfunctions of the brain, damage to structures responsible for the central regulation of the cardiovascular system leads to various deviations from the norm, including hypertension and pronounced alterations in heart rate and rhythm. It has been demonstrated that intracranial hypertension disrupts neurohumoral regulatory processes and autonomic functions, as well as undermines compensatory mechanisms. The regulatory role responsible for integrating vascular responses to changes in intracranial pressure is played by the suprasegmental structures of the autonomic nervous system (ANS). Research by multiple authors has clearly demonstrated correlations between the localization of brain injury and cardiac disturbances. The development of transient cardiac disturbances is directly linked to

acute cerebral injury and is referred to as ‘cerebrocardiac syndrome’ (CCS). The pathogenesis of CCS in cerebral ischemia is based on structural myocardial abnormalities that are unrelated to coronary blood flow impairment. In the pathogenesis of central hemodynamics, disorders of autonomic regulation of cardiovascular function and alterations in hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system activity play a leading role, resulting in the development of morphofunctional changes in cardiomyocytes. Acute cerebral injury triggers a systemic inflammatory response and catecholamine surge, leading to the release of neurotransmitters and cytokines that aggravate brain damage and cellular dysfunction. Cardiac injury following TBI is a relatively common complication with complex pathophysiology and potentially contributes to the high mortality of TBI patients [1-4]. However, the literature lacks sufficient data on the characteristics of autonomic hemodynamic responses during the acute phase of severe combined traumatic brain injury (severe combined TBI). Given this insufficiency of information, an attempt was made, based on the analysis of circadian rhythm monitoring data of autonomic tone (circadian rhythm of autonomic tone, CR AT), to evaluate the state of autonomic regulation of hemodynamics in children with severe combined TBI.

Objective of the study. To investigate and conduct a comparative analysis of the characteristics of the circadian rhythm of autonomic tone in patients with severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Materials and methods of the study. Thirty-six children (group 1) hospitalized at the Russian Scientific Center for Emergency and Radiation Medicine from 2016 to 2021 and 35 children (group 2) hospitalized in 2023-2024 for severe combined traumatic brain injury were admitted to the clinic due to road traffic accidents (30) and falls from height (5). Each patient group was studied subdivided into 3 subgroups. Traumatized patients of group 1 were studied in randomized subgroups: subgroup 1 (n=13) received conservative therapy according to indications; subgroup 2 (n=14) underwent extracranial corrective surgical procedures as indicated; and 9 patients in subgroup 3 received both cranial and extracranial surgical interventions according to indications. Patients of group 2 were represented in subgroup 1 without surgery (n=13); extracranial surgeries were performed in 14 patients; within the first hours of admission, according to indications, combined cranial and extracranial surgeries involving a neurosurgeon, general surgeon, and traumatologist were performed in 8 children. No significant age differences were identified between the groups. Monitoring was conducted by comprehensive hourly recording of body temperature parameters, hemodynamics, and respiration. Mechanical respiratory support was initiated with artificial lung ventilation (ALV) for a short duration, followed by transition to SIMV. As the patient’s condition improved, with stabilization of hemodynamics, respiration, recovery of reflexes, and consciousness, patients were transferred to the specialized department.

Results and Discussion. The average mesor of the circadian rhythm of TBI was increased in both groups to a similar degree — by 50% during the first 10 days in the first two subgroups, as well as throughout the entire observation period in the ICU, with a tendency to rise up to 90% in the third subgroup of the second group (Table 1). These findings corresponded to a hypersympathetic response despite an adequate level (based on clinical and functional criteria) of pharmacological stress-protective treatment. The most significant increase in the average level of sympathetic-adrenal system activity by 130% was observed during the first 10 days in the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group, by 110% during the first 10 days in the 2nd subgroup of the 1st group, and by 160% over 28 days in the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group. The minimum values of TBI in the bathyphase were elevated by 20% or more in the 1st and 2nd subgroups of the 2nd group. The intensity of the hypersympatotoxic reaction was confirmed by the highest amplitude values of the circadian rhythm of TBI in the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group (0.8 ± 0.3 units) and maximal daily fluctuations of the daily TBI range reaching 1.3 ± 0.4 units. Thus, children in group 2 were more vulnerable to secondary injuries accompanied by hypersympathetic activity. However, considering the protective nature of hypersympathetic activity in mediating compensatory responses in organs, at the cellular level, the observed difference in group 2 can be interpreted as a more adequate modification of autonomic regulation corresponding to the severity of traumatic injury involving a larger tissue volume (TBI combined with extracranial injuries following corrective surgical interventions).

Table 1. Mean values of the phase structure of circadian rhythm of autonomic tone, units

Groups	Mesor	At acrophase	At bathyphase	Amplitude	Daily fluctuation
Group 1, Subgroup 1, 10 days	1.5 ± 0.1	1.7 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1
Group 2, Subgroup 1, 10 days	1.5 ± 0.1	1.7 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.02	0.4 ± 0.1
Group 1, Subgroup 2, 10 days	1.7 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.4	1.4 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.4
Group 2 Subgroup 2 10 days	1.6 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1
Group 1 Subgroup 3 10 days	1.7 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.03	0.5 ± 0.1
Group 2 Subgroup 3 10 days	1.8 ± 0.1	2.3 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.2	$1.0 \pm 0.3^*$
Group 1 Subgroup 1 26 days	1.6 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.2
Group 2, Subgroup 1, 29 days	1.5 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.2	1.2 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.2
Group 1, Subgroup 2, 30 days	1.6 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.3	1.3 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.2
Group 2, Subgroup 2, 21 days	1.5 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.3
Group 1, Subgroup 3, 30 days	1.7 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.1
Group 2, Subgroup 3, 28 days	1.9 ± 0.3	2.6 ± 0.4	1.3 ± 0.3	$0.8 \pm 0.3^*$	$1.3 \pm 0.4^*$

* statistically significant compared to the indicator in Group 1

Table 2. Comparative assessment of the dynamics of the mesor of the circadian rhythm of TBI, units

Days	Group 1 Subgroup 1	Group 2 Subgroup 1	Group 1 Subgroup 2	Group 2 Subgroup 2	Group 1 Subgroup 3	Group 2 Subgroup 3
1	1.6±0.1	1.7±0.2	1.9±0.3	1.9±0.1	1.6±0.1	1.4±0.3
2	1.6±0.01	1.7±0.1	1.9±0.1	1.8±0.1	1.8±0.1	1.8±0.2
3	1.6±0.1	1.6±0.1	1.8±0.1	1.7±0.1	1.9±0.1*	1.8±0.1
4	1.5±0.1	1.5±0.1	1.6±0.1	1.5±0.1*	1.8±0.1	2.0±0.1*
5	1.4±0.1	1.5±0.02	1.7±0.1	1.4±0.1***	1.7±0.1	1.7±0.1
6	1.4±0.1	1.4±0.1	1.6±0.1	1.4±0.1*	1.6±0.1	1.6±0.2
7	1.4±0.1	1.4±0.1	1.6±0.1	1.6±0.1*	1.6±0.1	1.6±0.1
8	1.4±0.1	1.3±0.1*	1.7±0.1	1.6±0.1*	1.7±0.1	1.8±0.2
9	1.5±0.1	1.2±0.1***	1.4±0.1*	1.6±0.1*	2.0±0.1*	1.9±0.2
10	1.7±0.1	1.4±0.1***	1.6±0.1	1.5±0.1*	1.8±0.1	2.0±0.3
11	1.5±0.1	1.5±0.1	1.8±0.2	1.5±0.1*	1.6±0.1	2.0±0.2***
12	1.5±0.1	1.6±0.2	1.6±0.1	1.6±0.1*	1.8±0.1	2.0±0.2*
13	1.3±0.1*	1.5±0.1	1.6±0.1	1.4±0.2*	1.7±0.1	2.5±0.3***
14	1.6±0.1	1.6±0.2	1.4±0.1*	1.4±0.1*	1.5±0.1	2.6±0.3***
15	1.4±0.1	1.5±0.2	1.6±0.1	1.5±0.1*	1.7±0.1	2.5±0.3***
16	1.5±0.1	1.4±0.1	1.5±0.1	1.4±0.1*	1.8±0.1	2.5±0.2***
17	1.5±0.1	1.6±0.2	1.3±0.1*	1.4±0.1*	1.8±0.2	1.7±0.2
18	1.4±0.2	1.6±0.1	1.3±0.1*	1.4±0.1*	1.5±0.1	1.7±0.2
19	1.6±0.1	1.3±0.2*	1.8±0.1	1.5±0.1***	1.5±0.1	1.8±0.4
20	1.6±0.2	1.3±0.1*	1.6±0.1	1.3±0.2	1.5±0.1	1.3±0.2
21	1.5±0.1	1.4±0.2	1.6±0.1		1.8±0.1	1.6±0.3
22	1.5±0.2	1.5±0.2	1.7±0.1		1.7±0.2	1.9±0.3
23	1.8±0.1	1.4±0.2***	1.7±0.1		1.5±0.1	1.9±0.6
24	1.9±0.2	1.1±0.1***	1.7±0.1		1.7±0.1	1.6±0.4
25	1.9±0.2	1.5±0.2	1.5±0.1		1.6±0.1	1.8±0.5
26	1.9±0.2	2.0±0.3	1.3±0.2		1.5±0.1	1.4±0.3
27		1.5±0.2	1.5±0.1		1.8±0.2	1.4±0.3
28		1.5±0.3	1.6±0.2		1.6±0.1	2.3±0.6
29		1.5±0.1	1.7±0.1		1.6±0.2	
30			2.1±0.3		1.4±0.1	

* — statistically significant compared to the value on day 1

*** — statistically significant difference compared to the value in group 1

On the first day, the mesor of circadian rhythm of TBI was increased by 40% in subgroup 3 of group 2 and by up to 90% in subgroup 2 of groups 1 and 2 (Table

2). We attribute this to a more profound, radical pharmacological stress-protective correction, including general anesthesia and postoperative analgesia on day 1. In the subsequent days, a statistically significant decrease in the mesor of the circadian rhythm of TBI by 30% was observed in Group 1 on day 13, whereas in Group 2, a decrease in the mesor of the circadian rhythm of TBI by 40% was achieved as early as day 8. Conservative sympatholytic therapy proved to be more effective in injured children in Subgroup 1 of Group 2.

Dynamically, in the group of patients who underwent extracranial surgeries, a statistically significant sympatholytic effect of 50-60% was achieved on days 9, 14, 17, and 18 in Group 1. In contrast, in group 2, a significant reduction in sympathetic regulation was achieved as early as day 4 by 40% and was maintained at this level until the end of the observation period. Thus, in group 2 of children following extracranial surgeries, a significant improvement was observed 5 days earlier than in group 1, as indicated by a 40% decrease in the mesor of circadian rhythm of TBI. Unlike groups 1 and 2, in subgroup 3 of children, no decrease in TBI tone was detected; on the contrary, an increase in the mesor of circadian rhythm of TBI was observed by 30% and 40% on days 3 and 9, respectively. In the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group, a statistically significant increase in the mesor of circadian rhythm of TBI was observed by 60% on the 4th day, and by 60-110% on days 11-16, which was most likely associated with secondary complications such as infection and ventilator-associated pneumonia. These complications were primarily determined by more severe primary brain injury, with consequent impairment of regulatory functions responsible for enabling adaptive processes, and disruption of compensatory mechanisms due to failure of regulatory functions in the injured brain.

Fig. 1. Circadian rhythm of TBI in Group 1 at 30 days

Fig. 2. Circadian rhythm in Group 2 at 29 days

Confirmation of the most significant prolonged sympathomimetic reaction is evidenced by a substantially higher level of circadian rhythm by 110% at 09:00 hours. Even during the bathyphase, the parameter remained elevated by 60% in the 3rd subgroup of Group 2 (Fig.2). In Group 1, a stable hyper-sympathetic tone throughout both daytime and nighttime periods persisted, remaining elevated by 50-70% across all three subgroups (Fig.1).

Fig. 3. Amplitude of the 1st subgroup

Fig. 4. Amplitude of the 2nd subgroup

Fig. 5. Amplitude of the 3rd subgroup.

The lowest values of the circadian rhythm amplitude in TBI were observed in Group 1 on the 2nd and subsequent days across all three subgroups (Figs. 3, 4, 5). Higher fluctuations in TBI circadian rhythm amplitude were noted in the 3rd subgroup of Group 2 (Fig. 5). Nearly synchronous changes were detected in the dynamics of the daily range of TBI fluctuations.

Table 3. Correlation analysis of TBI during the first 10 days post-injury.

	10 days			11-30 days			During treatment in the intensive care unit		
	Group 1, Sub-group 1	Group 1, Sub-group 2	Group 1, Sub-group 3	Group 1, Sub-group 1	Group 1, Sub-group 2	Group 1, Sub-group 3	Group 1, Sub-group 1	Group 1, Sub-group 2	Group 1, Sub-group 3
TBI/MVP	0.97	0.87	0.85	0.88	0.87	0.72	0.90	0.86	0.79
TBI/total peripheral vascular resistance	-0.88	-0.75	-0.31	-0.91	-0.84	-0.59	-0.90	-0.78	-0.57

TBI/cardiac output	0.97	0.91	0.78	0.96	0.95	0.86	0.96	0.91	0.86
TBI/YOK	0.90	0.62	0.24	0.85	0.41	0.69	0.82	0.44	0.61
TBI/MAP	-0.37	-0.37	0.50	0.14	0.01	-0.05	0.13	-0.17	0.08
TBI/DAP	0.71	0.72	0.67	0.44	0.75	0.89	0.45	0.74	0.84
TBI/DBP	-0.61	-0.71	0.17	-0.22	0.02	-0.26	-0.24	-0.21	-0.21
TBI/SBP	-0.61	-0.58	0.11	-0.06	-0.20	0.08	-0.15	-0.27	0.02
TBI/T	-0.59	-0.43	0.73	-0.32	0.76		-0.42	0.33	

In Group 1, a statistically significant positive correlation of mitral valve prolapse with changes in TBI was detected in all injured children (Table 3). A statistically significant direct stimulatory effect of increased sympathetic activity on cardiac output was observed in children of Group 1 across all subgroups, accompanied by a negative correlation with total peripheral vascular resistance. This confirms the primary role and leading importance of the hyper-sympathetic response in the pathogenesis of hyperdynamic circulation, corroborating the association with the hyper-sympathetic impact of traumatic stress from the first day throughout the entire duration of intensive care unit treatment. A direct influence of autonomic tone on stroke volume was observed only in subgroup 1 of group 1 (0.9; 0.85; 0.82, respectively). A direct correlation between body temperature and alterations in autonomic tone in TBI was identified in subgroup 3 (0.73). It should be noted that the absence of statistical significance in the correlation between mitral valve prolapse and systolic arterial pressure (SAP) and diastolic arterial pressure (DAP) levels indicates the lack of informativeness of SAP and DAP changes in connection with acute metabolic disturbances that cause an energy-deficient state and the development of acute heart failure.

Table 4. Correlation coefficients throughout treatment in the intensive care unit.

	10 days			11–30 days			Treatment in the intensive care unit		
	Group 2, Sub-group 1	Group 2, Sub-group 2	Group 2, Sub-group 3	Group 2, Sub-group 1	Group 2, Sub-group 2	Group 2, Sub-group 3	Group 2, Sub-group 1	Group 2, Sub-group 2	Group 2, Sub-group 3
TBI/MVP	0.83	0.25	0.77	0.80	0.81	0.98	0.79	0.48	0.96
TBI/total peripheral vascular resistance	-0.93	-0.76	-0.45	-0.73	0.10	-0.34	-0.74	-0.17	-0.34
TBI/cardiac output	0.97	0.93	0.69	0.86	0.45	0.89	0.84	0.60	0.81
TBI/YOK	0.88	0.84	0.62	0.51	0.30	-0.03	0.56	0.38	0.05
TBI/MAP	-0.40	-0.69	0.35	0.02	0.52	0.79	0.18	-0.20	0.73
TBI/DAP	-0.40	0.55	0.77	0.67	0.57	0.89	0.39	0.56	0.78
TBI/DBP	-0.61	-0.74	0.13	0.23	0.38	0.73	0.03	-0.37	0.66
TBI/SBP	-0.64	-0.48	0.49	0.67	0.61	0.85	0.32	0.08	0.79
TBI/T	-0.50	-0.13	0.75	-0.26	0.63		-0.33	0.15	

In the 2nd group of traumatized children, a statistically significant direct correlation was identified between changes in TBI and mitral valve prolapse during the first 10 days in subgroups 1 and 3 (0.83; 0.77), which persisted throughout the entire intensive therapy in the intensive care unit (Table 4). A strong direct correlation between TBI and cardiac output was maintained both in the first 10 days across all three subgroups (0.93; 0.93; 0.69) and throughout the intensive care unit therapy (0.84; 0.6; 0.81). Confirmation of a hyperdynamic hemodynamic pattern was demonstrated by significant negative correlations between TBI and total peripheral vascular resistance during the first 10 days in subgroups 1 and 2 (-0.93; -0.73) and only in subgroup 1 (-0.74) during the stay in the intensive care unit (Table 4). A strong direct correlation between changes in T and TBI was observed in subgroup 3 (0.7).

Fig. 6. Inversion of the circadian rhythm of TBI in group 1 in %.

Fig. 7. Inversion of the circadian rhythm of TBI in group 2 in %.

In group 1, the longest inversion was observed in subgroup 2, constituting 47%, whereas the shift of the acrophase peak to nighttime hours in group 2 occurred in subgroup 3 and accounted for 35% of the duration of treatment in the intensive care unit. The observed difference corresponded to a more prolonged stress response in group 1 following extracranial surgeries, and in group 2, to a more severe course of the early postoperative period during combined cranial and extracranial corrective surgeries.

Conclusion. In subgroup 3 of group 2, a significant increase in the mesor of circadian rhythm of TBI by 60% on day 4, and by 60-110% on days 11-16, was associated with secondary complications such as infection and ventilator-associated pneumonia, primarily due to more severe primary brain injury, with the consequent loss of regulatory functions in the damaged brain regions responsible

for adaptive processes. This led to a corresponding disruption of numerous compensatory mechanisms due to the failure of the regulatory functions of the injured brain. A significant direct excitatory effect of increased sympathetic tone activity on cardiac output and a negative correlation with total peripheral vascular resistance were observed in children of group 1 across all subgroups, reflecting the predominant role of the hypersympathetic response in the formation of the hyperdynamic circulatory type during the acute post-traumatic period. A direct association between TBI and mitral valve prolapse was observed throughout the entire period of intensive care in the intensive care unit.

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后方医疗保障组织：第一次世界大战期间斯拉维亚诺塞尔布斯基区和斯塔罗别尔斯基区的经验

**ORGANIZING MEDICAL CARE IN THE REAR:
EXPERIENCE SLAVYANOSERBSKIY AND STAROBELSKIY
DISTRICTS IN THE YEARS OF THE FIRST WORLD WAR**

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摘要：本文以叶卡捷琳诺斯拉夫省斯拉维亚诺塞尔布斯基县和斯塔罗比尔斯克县为例，考察了第一次世界大战期间俄罗斯帝国后方地区的医疗卫生体系组织情况。文章基于卢甘斯克人民共和国国家档案馆的资料以及1914年至1917年的期刊报刊，重构了医疗机构网络的构建过程。文章重点关注地方自治机构、市级自治政府、工业企业和慈善团体之间的互动机制，分析了资金来源、医院后勤保障以及私人机构和教育界在救治伤员方面所发挥的作用。文章揭示了地方领导人，特别是地方自治医生V. N. Bragin，在医疗基础设施现代化建设中的关键作用。该地区的经验展现了危机时期国家与公民社会开展卓有成效的合作的典范。

关键词：第一次世界大战、医疗保健、叶卡捷琳诺斯拉夫省、地方自治医疗

Annotation. *The article examines the organization of the healthcare system in the rear regions of the Russian Empire during the First World War using the example of Slavyanoserbsky and Starobilsk counties of Yekaterinoslav province. Based on the materials of the State Archive of the LPR and the periodical press of 1914-1917, the process of forming a network of medical institutions has been*

reconstructed. Special attention is paid to the mechanisms of interaction between zemstvo bodies, city self-government, industrial enterprises and charitable societies. The sources of funding, logistical support for hospitals, as well as the role of private initiatives and the educational community in supporting the wounded are analyzed. The key role of local leaders, in particular the zemstvo doctor V. N. Bragin, in the modernization of medical infrastructure is revealed. The experience of the region demonstrates an example of productive cooperation between the state and civil society in a crisis period.

Keywords: *World War I, healthcare, Yekaterinoslav province, zemstvo medicine*

Introduction

The First World War presented a serious challenge to the healthcare system of the Russian Empire, particularly in the rear regions, where local authorities and public organizations bore the brunt of the burden of receiving and treating the wounded, accommodating refugees, and supporting the families of servicemen. The Slavyanoserbksk and Starobelsk districts of the Yekaterinoslav Governorate illustrate the formation of a comprehensive network of medical institutions, based on the interaction of zemstvos, city councils, charitable societies, and industrial enterprises. Studying this experience provides a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of social mobilization under the extreme conditions of wartime [1].

The purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is a systems analysis of the organization of medical care in the Slavyanoserbksk and Starobelsk districts of the Yekaterinoslav Governorate of the Russian Empire during the First World War of 1914-1918. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were addressed:

- to identify the role of zemstvo bodies, city government and public associations in the creation of a system of infirmaries and hospitals;
- characterize the sources of funding and material support for medical institutions;
- consider the contribution of charities, educational institutions and individuals to support wounded and disabled soldiers;
- to examine the role of the chairman of the district zemstvo community, physician Vasily Nikitovich Bragin, in improving the system of assistance to the wounded and sick during the war;
- to assess the effectiveness of interaction between state and public structures in wartime conditions.

Materials and methods

The study is based on archival materials from the LPR State Archives, periodicals from 1914-1917, and scholarly literature. The use of retrospective, comparative-historical, and chronological methods allowed us to analyze the organization of

medical care in the rear districts of the Yekaterinoslav Governorate and identify the role of zemstvos, charitable organizations, and private initiatives during wartime.

Results and discussions

With the declaration of war in August 1914, the zemstvo institutions of the Yekaterinoslav Governorate quickly reoriented their budgets to wartime needs, prioritizing funding for a network of hospitals and infirmaries. Already in the first months of the conflict, rear districts faced its multifaceted consequences. Mobilization measures led to the mass conscription of males into the active army, creating a labor shortage in agriculture. At the same time, periodicals began regularly publishing lists of the province's natives who had died and been wounded, creating an atmosphere of anxiety in society. At the same time, the region faced a large influx of refugees from frontline areas, leading to a significant population increase and additional strain on social infrastructure [2].

Private homes, hotels, furnished rooms, and public buildings were used to accommodate the new arrivals. New medical facilities were established in Luhansk, Slavyanoserbsk, and Starobelsk, the bed capacity of existing hospitals was expanded, and educational institutions, church buildings, and industrial facilities were converted into hospitals. By 1915, sixteen medical facilities were operating in Slavyanoserbsk County, a significant number of which were converted to accommodate wounded soldiers.

Funding was provided by zemstvo budgets, voluntary donations, and assistance from industrial enterprises. The Hartmann Plant and the Donetsk -Yuryevsk Metallurgical Society provided beds, medicine, and medical personnel. The Hartmann Locomotive Plant supplied 25 beds from its factory hospital to the pedagogical infirmary and the People's Teachers' Infirmary. The accounting books of the DYU-MO plant (now the Alchevsk Metallurgical Plant) for 1915 record expenses not only for medicine and dressings, but also for "the maintenance of 5 prisoners of war working as orderlies in the hospital" [2]. After the infirmaries were closed in December 1917, the senior physician of the Hartmann Plant hospital appealed to the Administration with a request to return the beds [2-3].

An important step was the entry Luhansk to the All-Russian Union of Cities, which facilitated supplies medicines and allowed them to receive government subsidies.

Medical institutions were striving for modernization: as early as 1914 The Slavic-Serbian Zemstvo acquired an X-ray machine — a significant achievement for the province. At the same time, courses for nurses and orderlies were actively established, partially offsetting the personnel shortage caused by the mobilization of doctors and paramedics.

During the war years, philanthropy flourished. Women's clubs operated in cities, schoolgirls prepared bandages, teachers contributed from their salaries to support hospitals, and charity concerts and fundraisers were held. Newspapers reported

numerous donations, and hospitals regularly received gifts from residents. The work of physician Evgenia Evgrafovna Skvortsova, whose work in the Luhansk hospital he became a symbol of selflessness.

Charitable societies, individuals, and educational institutions played a key role in organizing medical care and supporting wounded soldiers. Parish trusteeships and various public committees were active in the Slavyanoserbsk district. They collected donations, organized meals in the infirmaries, and manufactured linens and bandages. The newspaper “Lugansk Leaflet” regularly published reports on donations received and their distribution to hospitals.

Luhansk’s educational institutions also made a significant contribution to aiding the wounded. In accordance with a Ministry of Public Education circular dated August 27, 1914, warm clothing and bandages were made during handicraft classes at girls’ gymnasiums. Funds for their purchase were provided by both parents and educational institutions. Some gymnasiums also supported charitable societies that provided support to disadvantaged students and their families.

Luhansk’s teaching staff organized their own infirmary, which was financed through voluntary deductions from teachers’ salaries, charity events, and donation drives established at educational institutions. For example, at the private girls’ gymnasium named after E. K. Loktishcheva regularly held pedagogical meetings at which issues of assistance to the wounded and the distribution of collected funds were discussed.

In addition, in the Slavyanoserbsk and Starobelsk districts of the Yekaterinoslav Governorate, there were special institutions for convalescents — the so-called “patronages”—where the wounded who did not require inpatient treatment but were not yet ready to return to duty or civilian life received food, outpatient care, and recuperation. In Luhansk, the building of an agricultural school (now the site of the Luhansk National Agrarian University) was converted into a patronage center, designed to accommodate 100 people. In Starobelsk, a 15-bed patronage center was opened at the district administration.

To support disabled service members, the Union of Disabled Soldiers was created. The organization facilitated access to medical care, provided referrals to specialists, and provided assistance with travel to treatment and return home. Archival documents confirm the union’s active correspondence with medical institutions and government agencies [4].

Clergy also participated in the relief efforts, providing spiritual and material support to the wounded, organizing fundraising efforts, and providing moral support. All of this demonstrates a high degree of community cohesion and responsibility to those who fought in the war.

V. N. Bragin made a significant contribution to the development of the district’s medical infrastructure. His educational activities contributed to the dissemination

of hygienic knowledge among the population, which, combined with organizational measures, led to a decrease in the incidence of disease [5].

Conclusion

Thus, the experience of the Slavyanoserbbsk and Starobelsk districts of the Yekaterinoslav Governorate demonstrates that, even in the context of a large-scale military conflict in the rear, a balanced and effective system of medical support was established. The coordinated efforts of local governments, public organizations, and private charities ensured reliable support for the army and wounded service members. This example demonstrates a high level of social responsibility, the consolidation of forces, and productive cooperation between the state and civil society.

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老年人和老年痴呆症患者佩戴弹性基托可摘义齿后口腔微生物群组成的变化

**CHANGES IN THE COMPOSITION OF ORAL MICROFLORA
IN ELDERLY AND SENILE PATIENTS WITH REMOVABLE
DENTURES WITH AN ELASTIC BASE LAYER**

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摘要。口腔健康是影响老年人生活质量的重要因素之一。影响老年人群健康的关键因素包括提高正畸治疗效果、保护现有牙齿的完整性以及制作高质量的义齿。对于合并慢性疾病且免疫反应性降低的老年患者，上述问题会更加突出。本研究对60例ICD-10编码为“K08.1——因意外、拔牙或局部牙周炎导致的牙齿缺失”的患者进行了细菌学研究。结果表明，使用弹性基托的活动义齿会破坏老年患者口腔正常菌群与免疫反应之间的平衡。口腔内抗感染能力下降，导致致病菌和条件致病菌的激活。在老年患者中使用弹性基托可摘式义齿配合治疗凝胶和免疫调节剂后，已形成的菌群失衡得到纠正。这表现为致病菌群生长受到抑制，腐生菌群增殖得到促进。

关键词：弹性基托可摘式义齿，老年患者，免疫调节剂，口腔菌群。

Abstract. Dental health, among other factors, determines the quality of life of elderly individuals. Key factors affecting health in this patient group include the

enhancement of orthopedic dental treatment outcomes, preservation of the integrity of existing teeth, and the fabrication of high-quality dental prostheses. The process is exacerbated in elderly patients with concomitant chronic diseases and reduced immunobiological reactivity. A bacteriological study was conducted on 60 patients with ICD-10 coding 'K08.1 — loss of teeth due to accident, extraction, or localized periodontitis.' The results of the bacteriological study demonstrated that the use of removable dentures with an elastic base layer contributed to the disruption of the balance between the normal oral microflora and the immune response in elderly patients. There was a decrease in anti-infective resistance in the oral cavity, leading to the activation of pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microflora. The use of removable dentures with an elastic base layer in elderly and senile patients who used a therapeutic gel and an immunomodulator led to the normalization of the developed imbalance. This was manifested by the suppression of pathogenic flora growth and the stimulation of saprophytic flora proliferation.

Keywords: *removable dentures with an elastic base layer, elderly and senile patients, immunomodulator, oral microflora.*

Relevance

According to forecasts, the population of Russia beyond working age by 2031 will reach 42.3 million people (28.7%). The Government of the Russian Federation has developed and approved the “Strategy of Actions in the Interests of Older Citizens,” the priority of which is to ensure the health of elderly individuals in order to increase life expectancy and improve quality of life. Dental health, among other factors, determines the quality of life of elderly individuals. At present, a pressing issue in dentistry is the maintenance of health in elderly and advanced-age populations. According to WHO data, patients aged 60 to 74 years are classified as elderly, while those aged 75 to 89 years are classified as advanced-age. Key components of health in this patient cohort include enhancing the outcomes of orthopedic dental treatment, preserving the integrity of existing teeth, and fabricating high-quality dental prostheses [3, 7].

Diseases in elderly individuals exhibit several characteristics inherent to the biological process of aging. These are reflected in the nonspecific manifestations of diseases, the presence of multiple somatic pathologies, the unpredictability of disease progression and rapid deterioration of the patient’s condition, a high incidence of complications, and the need for subsequent rehabilitation. With advancing age, owing to desquamation, the oral mucosa becomes more susceptible to injury. Even minor trauma leads to the formation of erosions and the development of persistent inflammatory processes. With a decrease in the number of teeth, the degree of atrophy of the alveolar process of the maxilla and the alveolar part of the mandible increases, up to their complete disappearance. In elderly and older patients with partial and complete edentulism, pronounced deformities of the dental arches are frequently observed [1, 5].

At present, the restoration of dental arch continuity using dental implants is widely practiced. However, the presence of decompensated forms of chronic systemic diseases in patients, along with significant financial costs associated with implantation, ensures ongoing demand for partial and complete removable dentures. Enhancing the functional efficiency of removable orthopedic constructions remains a complex and pressing issue in orthopedic dentistry, as does patient adaptation to them [2, 9].

It is known that the denture base is fabricated from materials that are not entirely biologically inert substances; therefore, both local and systemic effects on the organism are possible. For patients with complex anatomical and topographical conditions of the denture-bearing area, the fabrication of two-layer removable dentures with a soft base layer made of an elastic polymer is required. More than 60% of patients using removable dentures experience candidiasis, which manifests as pain, burning sensation, hyperemia of the mucous membrane in the area of the denture-bearing surface, and angular cheilitis. This process is further exacerbated in elderly and senile patients with concomitant chronic diseases and decreased immunobiological reactivity [4].

A promising approach to the prevention of complications in the tissues of the denture-bearing surface is the comprehensive application of dental gels, allowing anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and immunomodulatory effects. The purposeful development of a comprehensive methodology will enhance the quality of prosthetic treatment using orthopedic dental prostheses in elderly and advanced age patients utilizing removable dental prostheses [6, 8].

Materials and Methods

To address the objectives outlined in the dissertation research, 75 patients were examined and subsequently received orthopedic treatment in the orthopedic dentistry clinic, with disease classification according to ICD-10 “K08.1 — tooth loss due to accident, extraction, or localized periodontitis.” The examination of patients was conducted in accordance with the Clinical Guidelines (Treatment Protocol) for patients with partial or complete tooth loss. The subjective component included assessment of complaints, collection of life and medical history, including obtaining information on the causes and timing of tooth loss (formation of dental arch defects), the presence of removable prosthetic devices, duration of their use, and history of complications from previous treatments. The objective evaluation involved external examination of the skin condition and facial contours, as well as palpation of the masticatory muscles and the temporomandibular joint region. During the oral examination, the condition of the dental arches, occlusion, edentulous areas of the jaws, oral mucosa and vermilion border of the lips, and the periodontal tissues of the teeth were assessed. Each patient signed a voluntary informed consent form for the dental intervention, consented to the orthopedic treatment plan, and completed a questionnaire designed by the authors. All patients were divided into three groups of 20 individuals each:

Group 1 (control) — patients received removable dental prostheses with an elastic base layer;

Group 2 — patients were provided with removable dental prostheses featuring an elastic basal layer; patients were given instructions for the use of the therapeutic gel for the oral mucosa, Asepta with propolis, which should be applied to the mucosa of the denture-bearing area twice daily for one month;

Group 3 — patients were provided with removable dental prostheses featuring an elastic basal layer; patients were given instructions for the use of the therapeutic gel Asepta with propolis, which should be applied to the mucosa of the denture-bearing area twice daily for one month, as well as the immunomodulator Galavit, in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions.

A bacteriological study was conducted at the Higher Education Institution «VOCB No. 1» in Voronezh. All species of oral microorganisms cultivated on prepared specialized nutrient media were taken into account during the study. The study was conducted at various intervals: before treatment initiation (prior to fixation of removable plate dentures with an elastic base layer), at 7 days, and at 1, 3, and 6 months following their fixation.

Methodology of material collection. In the morning, before performing personal oral hygiene and taking food, a swab was taken from the mucous membrane of the denture-bearing area using a cotton swab, placed into test tubes with transport medium, and transported to the bacteriological laboratory within 3 hours. Quantitative assessment of the density of populations of various ecological groups is performed by counting colony-forming units (CFU) during inoculation on nutrient media. The data obtained based on the conducted studies were transferred to the computer using specialized software. A study was conducted on the microbial colonization of the oral mucosa in patients from three groups. Pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microbial flora were cultivated: *Lactobacillus*, *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Neisseria*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Candida albicans*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*. In the first group, after seven days, an increase in the growth of pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic flora was observed, persisting up to six months following the placement of removable dentures with a soft base layer. In the second group of our patients, there was an increase in pathogenic and opportunistic flora; however, the obtained values were more favorable in comparative analysis with those in patients from the first group. In the third patient group, the isolation of pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms after 7 days was minimal. One month following the commencement of the study, the number of pathogenic flora colonies declined or they were not isolated. After 3 and 6 months, the indicators remained virtually unchanged, confirming the validity of the selected program for the prevention of oral dysbiosis associated with the use of removable acrylic dentures.

Results of the conducted study

The results of the bacteriological study demonstrated that wearing removable dentures with an elastic base layer contributed to the disturbance of the balance between the normal oral microflora and the immune response in elderly and senescent patients. There was a decrease in anti-infective resistance in the oral cavity, leading to the activation of pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microflora. The use of removable dentures with an elastic base layer in elderly and senile patients who applied the therapeutic gel Aseptia with propolis to the mucosa of the denture-bearing area twice daily for one month, along with the immunomodulator Galavit administered according to the manufacturer's instructions, led to the normalization of the induced imbalance. This was manifested by the suppression of pathogenic flora growth and the stimulation of saprophytic flora proliferation.

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口腔矫形护理组织质量和可及性的标准和指标
**CRITERIA AND INDICATORS OF THE QUALITY
OF ORGANIZATION AND ACCESSIBILITY
OF DENTAL ORTHOPEDIC CARE**

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摘要：本文对拟纳入领土国家保障计划（TSGP）的区域层面口腔矫形医疗服务组织质量和可及性评估标准及指标进行了科学论证。以梁赞州为例，研究发现，该地区口腔疾病指标（基于医疗服务利用数据）呈下降趋势，2019年至2022年间下降了16.28%，这主要归因于新冠疫情引发的复杂流行病学形势。研究还建立了公立牙科机构接受口腔矫形治疗患者的社会卫生特征，结果显示，该人群主要为60岁及以上低收入的非劳动退休人员。针对社会弱势群体，口腔矫形服务的可及性和组织质量的综合指标计算结果为0.4007，高于区域平均水平0.4545（目标阈值为 $K_{\lim} \circ 1.0$ ）。这些结果为在领土国家保障计划（TSGP）框架内（特别是其预算组成部分）为60岁及以上退休非劳动人口提供口腔矫形服务所需的额外财政支持（每年5.0684亿卢布）提供了依据。该研究证实了将个人牙科保健（PDC）纳入TSGP优于区域社会保障计划的优势，主要在于TSGP强制要求为

纳入的每项医疗服务制定具体标准并达到可及性和质量绩效指标。最后，作者探讨了将已制定的PDC组织和可及性标准及指标应用于欧亚地区国家（包括哈萨克斯坦共和国）医疗保险体系的可能性。

关键词牙科矫形护理、可及性、组织质量、领土国家保障计划、社会卫生患者概况、强制性医疗保险、社会计划、欧亚经济联盟（EAEU）、哈萨克斯坦共和国。

Abstract. *This article presents the results of a scientific substantiation of criteria and indicators for assessing the quality of organization and accessibility of dental orthopedic care at the regional level, proposed for inclusion in Territorial State Guarantee Programs (TSGP). Using the Ryazan region as a case study, a negative trend in dental morbidity indicators (based on healthcare utilization data) was identified, showing a decrease of 16.28% between 2019 and 2022, attributed to the complex epidemiological situation induced by the COVID-19 pandemic. A socio-hygienic profile of patients receiving PDC in public dental institutions was established, revealing that the primary demographic consists of non-working pensioners aged 60 and older with low income levels. An integral indicator of accessibility and organizational quality of dental orthopedic care for socially vulnerable groups was calculated as 0.4007, compared to the regional average of 0.4545 (with a target threshold value of $K_{\lim} > 1.0$). These results allowed the justification and calculation of the required additional financial support amounting to 506.84 million RUB annually to provide dental orthopedic care within the framework of the Territorial State Guarantee Program (specifically its budgetary component) for retired non-working individuals aged 60 and above. The study substantiates the advantages of incorporating PDC into TSGPs over regional social programs, primarily due to the mandatory requirement to define specific criteria and meet accessibility and quality performance indicators for each medical profile included in the TSGP. Finally, the authors discuss the potential for adapting the developed criteria and indicators for the organization and accessibility of PDC to the medical insurance systems of countries in the Eurasian region, including the Republic of Kazakhstan.*

Keywords: *dental orthopedic care, accessibility, quality of organization, territorial state guarantee program, socio-hygienic patient profile, mandatory medical insurance, social programs, Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), Republic of Kazakhstan.*

Introduction

A strategic objective of state policy in the countries of the Eurasian space is to improve the quality of life and the health of the nation by providing the population with accessible and high-quality medical care. To this end, in Russia, in accordance with Federal Law No. 323-FZ of November 21, 2011, ‘On the Fundamentals

of Health Protection of Citizens in the Russian Federation,' state guarantees programs (Territorial Healthcare Programs) for the free provision of medical care to the population are approved, on the basis of which territorial programs of state guarantees are formed in the regions.

The subjects of the Russian Federation have been granted the right to allocate additional budgetary funds to the Territorial Healthcare Program beyond the approved volume and financial norms, which are annually approved by the Government of the Russian Federation within the structure of the Territorial Healthcare Program, in order to increase regional tariffs or to finance additional volumes of medical care. At the same time, despite the steady increase in the cost of dental orthopedic care (DOC), it is not included either in the Territorial Healthcare Program or in the Territorial Healthcare Program, and thus primarily relies on a single financial source — the personal funds of the population, who are in urgent need of this type of care [7,11].

The main paradox of Russian dentistry is as follows: the state finances the provision of primary specialized dental care (PSSP) within the framework of the Territorial Healthcare Program (THP), i.e., dental treatment at the early stages of disease, but denies financial support at the stage of restoring the function of teeth and the oral cavity, when the need for Standardized Care Protocol (SCP) becomes critical [6].

The relevance of scientific substantiation of medico-organizational, financial-economic, and medico-social criteria and indicators of accessibility and quality in the organization of SCP is explained by the inaccessibility of SCP for groups of needy citizens, primarily socially vulnerable populations residing in rural areas, as well as elderly citizens and pensioners [5,22]. In Russia, legislation has established a mechanism of social tax deductions that allows citizens to reclaim part of the paid Personal Income Tax equivalent to expenses on payment for the Standardized Care Protocol. This mechanism does not extend to non-working pensioners, since Personal Income Tax is not withheld from pensions (Article 217 of the Tax Code of the Russian Federation), which reflects inequality in the realization of citizens' rights to healthcare protection.

To address this inequality, Federal Law No. 178-FZ of 17.07.1999 "On State Social Assistance" authorizes the regions of the Russian Federation to develop social programs financing the Standardized Care Protocol from budgetary sources, including for non-working pensioners [7,9]. However, only 12.0% of regions (Moscow city, Moscow region, St. Petersburg city, Republic of Tatarstan, etc.) implement preferential prosthetic care under social programs; In the majority of Russian Federation subjects, social programs are absent [13,18]. The consistently low level of budgetary investments in social programs is due to the absence of at least one of the following three factors: high revenues of regional budgets, adequacy of local legislation, and the adoption of a positive administrative decision at the local level.

Furthermore, the structure of social programs does not provide for the approval of criteria and indicators that would enable evaluation of the accessibility and quality of the organization of Standardized Care Protocols (SOP). Meanwhile, for the inclusion of each medical profile, including SOP, in the Territorial Healthcare Program (THP), defining the respective criteria and indicators is mandatory (Government decrees of the Russian Federation and Ryazan region approving the Territorial Healthcare Program for 2019-2025). Therefore, in our view, inclusion of SOP in the THP is preferable to social programs, as it ensures unified approaches to the assessment of SOP and effective control over its provision at the regional level [14].

Indeed, the absence of unified criteria for assessing the accessibility and quality of the organization of Standardized Care Protocols (SOP) complicates monitoring and expenditure planning for their provision both in the Russian Federation and in the countries of the Eurasian Economic Union, where similar trends exist. For example, within the Mandatory Social Health Insurance system of the Republic of Kazakhstan, despite the high prevalence and severity of dental diseases that generate substantial demand for SOP, state funding remains confined to targeted social programs, such as those for the elderly population [5,10].

At the same time, the provision of medical assistance by the Federal Bailiffs Service is included in the guaranteed, free medical care package for the population, while payment (additional payment) for orthopedic services from state sources, according to the Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated 07.07.2020 No. 360-VI 'On the People's Health and Healthcare System,' is available to privileged categories of citizens and/or provided within the framework of the Mandatory Social Health Insurance system with co-payments by the population [1,19].

Materials and Methods

The purpose of the study was to define and substantiate criteria and indicators for the accessibility and quality of organizing Standardized Care Protocols (SOP) for inclusion in the Territorial Healthcare Program, using the Ryazan region as a case study, while considering the potential for extrapolation at the interregional level. The study was carried out on the basis of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education 'Ryazan State Medical University named after Academician I. P. Pavlov' and public dental institutions during 2019-2022. The methodological foundation was a systems approach and analysis (Bertalanffy, 1969; Sadovsky V. N., 1980), which enables the consideration of ensuring accessibility and quality in organizing SOP as a systemic management object at the regional level. *Research methods*: information-analytical, including content analysis of regulatory legal acts (Federal Laws No. 323-FZ, No. 326-FZ, resolutions of the Government of the Russian Federation and the Ryazan region approving the Territorial Healthcare Program and the Territorial Healthcare Program for 2019-2025), and a review of scientific literature; statistical, involving analysis of

reporting forms No. 12, No. 30, and registries of TFOMS accounts (1,745 accounts, 1,649,046 cases of providing dental orthopedic care); sociological, consisting of a survey of 407 patients (representativeness error $\Delta=5.0\%$, $t=2$), evaluating patient satisfaction and loyalty on a 5-point visual analog scale (VAS) [16]; economic, involving the calculation of the cost for a completed SOP case, as well as volume and financial norms; mathematical, involving the calculation of the integral indicator of accessibility and the quality of SOP organization; The SPSS-26 and STATISTICA-10 software packages were utilized: the presence of associations was determined using the chi-square test (χ^2) and correlation coefficients (r) via Spearman's rank correlation method, evaluated according to Cheddok's scale.

Results and Discussion

Based on the analysis of the dynamics of dental morbidity (measured by patient visits), the demand of the regional population for ПССП and SOP was determined. Analysis of utilization rates of the Federal Bailiffs Service revealed a negative trend in 2020-2022. Dental morbidity during this period decreased by 16.28% (from 322.46 to 269.96‰), which is attributable to restrictive measures imposed during the COVID-19 pandemic. Morbidity determining the need for care under the Standardized Care Protocol (diseases of the pulp, periodontium, etc.) decreased by 17.15% (from 149.16 to 123.58‰) (Table 1). A phenomenon of so-called "hidden" dental morbidity was identified: actual values were 14.0-17.0% lower than predicted (in 2020-2022: 53.25‰, 51.20‰, and 34.06‰, respectively), which led to the accumulation of dental pathology and the development of "deferred" dental morbidity, thereby increasing the need for care under the Standardized Care Protocol in subsequent periods [3,17].

For the first time, the *social and hygienic profile of patients* who received the Standardized Care Protocol in public dental institutions was identified: predominantly non-working retirees aged 60 years and older, with incomes of 1.37 Minimum Wage (17,525.04 rubles) per family member in households of 2-3 people, mainly women, urban residents, without tax benefits for reimbursement of Standardized Care Protocol expenses [14].

Table 1. Population morbidity in the Ryazan region (according to appeal data), determining the need for Standardized Care Protocol

Indicator name	2019	2020	2021	2022
Population size, persons	1 114 137	1 108 847	1 102 810	1 098 579
Completed cases — total, units	359 265	286 146	282 102	296 567
Dental morbidity according to appeal data (per 1,000 persons)	322.46	258.06	255.80	269.96
Growth/decline rate (%)	-	-19.97	-0.87	+5.53

Indicator name	2019	2020	2021	2022
Number of completed cases requiring the provision of Standardized Care Protocol (units)	166 180	139 429	131 838	135 764
Incidence (based on appeal data), determining the need for Standardized Care Protocol (per 1,000 individuals)	149.16	125.74	119.55	123.58
Growth/decline rate (%)	-	-15.70	-4.93	+3.37

A direct correlation was established between family income and expenses on Standardized Care Protocol ($r=0.431$; $p<0.001$): for patients with an income of 1-2 times the Minimum Wage, prosthetics expenses exceed 45,000 rubles. These are available in only 1.45% of cases among patients with such income, compared to 32.65% availability among those earning ≥ 6 times the Minimum Wage, confirming the cost-related inaccessibility of Standardized Care Protocol for low-income citizens. At the same time, the amount of expenses on the Standardized Care Protocol exhibited a negative correlation with satisfaction regarding the quality of its organization ($r = -0.233$) and patient loyalty to state dental organizations ($r = -0.135$).

Medical-organizational (Kmed-org), financial-economic (Kfin-ec), and medical-social (Kmed-soc) criteria and indicators of accessibility and quality of the organization of the Standardized Care Protocol were identified and scientifically substantiated, including: the staffing level of dental clinics with prosthodontists (medical-organizational); comparison of average income per one family member of the patient with the average cost of a completed Standardized Care Protocol case (financial-economic); patient satisfaction in specific groups with the quality of organization and accessibility of the Standardized Care Protocol (medical-social). An integral indicator of accessibility and quality of organization of the Standardized Care Protocol for specific patient groups (at $K_{flim} \text{ o } 1.0$) was calculated by the formula: $K_{fl} = K_{med-org} \text{ imes } K_{fin-ek} \text{ imes } K_{med-soc}$. Among non-working pensioners aged 60 and older, it is the lowest — 0.4007 (average — 0.4545). With the target value of K_{flim} approaching 1.0, the actual value is 2.5 times lower, confirming the status of the most vulnerable group regarding cost affordability of the Standardized Care Protocol [14].

Economic justification and advantage of the Territorial Healthcare Program: the calculation of financial provision needs for the Standardized Care Protocol for non-working pensioners aged 60 and older in the region revealed a requirement for an annual allocation of 506.84 million rubles from the regional budget, ensuring coverage of 18,977 patients given the current staffing of state dental organizations. The draft regional legal act developed by the authors (government resolution on amendments to the Territorial Healthcare Program) establishes a normative volume of 0.01764 completed cases of Standardized Care Protocol

and a normative financial provision of 467.12 rubles. per 1 resident, with the approval of criteria and indicators for accessibility and quality of organization of Standardized Care Protocol for monitoring the fulfillment of the budgetary component of the Territorial Healthcare Program in relation to this profile of dental care. Simultaneously, based on the principle of social justice, budget funds planned according to the total population of the region — the fundamental principle in the formation of the Territorial Healthcare Program — are allocated to reimburse the expenses of state dental clinics that provided Standardized Care Protocol to non-working pensioners aged ≥ 60 years.

An overall amount of financial expenditures totaling 5,537.37 million rubles has been determined. for the provision of the Standardized Care Protocol to this group of pensioners (210,690 individuals in the region), considering the identified staffing capacity and the level of dental morbidity that determines the demand for the Standardized Care Protocol, for the period up to 2033.

Comparative analysis of Standardized Care Protocol financing systems: overall, the financing systems for the Standardized Care Protocol in Russia and Kazakhstan share many similarities, which is explained by the historical development of healthcare in the post-Soviet space. Both countries operate mandatory insurance systems (OMC and Mandatory Social Health Insurance), but the scope of state guarantees differs (Table 2). The systems face similar challenges in ensuring the accessibility of Standardized Care Protocols for socially disadvantaged population groups, as Standardized Care Protocols are not included in the basic free care package for all those in need, and there is no unified assessment of the resource, temporal, and cost accessibility of Standardized Care Protocols. A common issue is the shortage of dental personnel, including in rural areas. Thus, in the Ryazan region, the availability of dental orthopedic services for rural residents is 3.8 times lower than for urban residents. Similar disparities are noted in certain regions of Kazakhstan, where the demand for dental prosthetics among the elderly reaches 85.0-95.0%, while actual coverage, partly due to insufficient specialist staffing, is less than 40.0%, underscoring the need to improve labor regulation and incentivize work in rural areas [5,14,15].

The identified dependence of satisfaction with accessibility and patient loyalty to state dental organizations on the quality of the organization of the Standardized Care Protocol is relevant for both countries currently undergoing primary healthcare reform [2,4,20,21]. The implementation of “lean technologies,” including electronic appointment scheduling with the dental orthopedic specialist ($>90.0\%$ during the study period), made it possible to reduce the duration of patients’ stay at the registration desk from 39 to 14 minutes, thereby increasing patient satisfaction and loyalty [8,14]. The practical experience of digitization of registration and control processes for the fulfillment

of Standardized Care Protocol volumes can be replicated within integration projects of the Eurasian Economic Union [12,15].

Table 2. Comparative Characteristics of Standardized Care Protocol Funding Systems

Comparison Criterion	Russian Federation	Republic of Kazakhstan
Fundamental Law	<i>Federal Law</i> “On the Fundamentals of Health Protection”	<i>Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan</i> “On the People’s Health and Healthcare System”
Funding system	<i>Social programs</i> + population funds	<i>Mandatory Social Health Insurance</i> (Federal Social Health Insurance) + State Budgetary Medical Institution* + population funds
Standardized Care Protocol within state guarantees	Not included in the Territorial Healthcare Program; Rarely — partial inclusion in the Territorial Healthcare Program	Included in Mandatory Social Health Insurance with co-payment; in the State Budgetary Medical Institution — for beneficiaries
Approval of criteria and indicators for accessibility and quality of organization	By resolutions of regional governments — within the Territorial Healthcare Program	By orders of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan and Federal Social Health Insurance
Regional differences	Significant: in 12.0% of regions — social programs; in 88.0% of regions — payment at the expense of citizens	Moderate: uniform federal standards exist; differences in the amounts of budget co-financing

*State Budgetary Medical Institution — guaranteed volume of free medical care

Conclusion. Thus, the criteria and indicators presented in this article, including the integral indicator of accessibility and quality in the organization of dental orthopedic care, can be used for monitoring the efficiency of expenditures, including those of the Social Health Insurance Fund of the Republic of Kazakhstan, and are recommended for adaptation within the mandatory social (health) insurance systems of the Eurasian region countries to improve the targeting and efficiency of spending on dental orthopedic care.

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在磁暴期间单次饮用咖啡对参与体育运动的学生的巴耶夫斯基适应潜能水平的影响

THE INFLUENCE OF A SINGLE CONSUMPTION OF A COFFEE DRINK DURING A MAGNETIC STORM ON THE LEVEL OF ADAPTATION POTENTIAL ACCORDING TO BAYEVSKY IN STUDENTS ENGAGED IN SPORTS**Prokopyev Nikolai Yakovlevich***Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor
Tyumen State University, Tyumen, Russia**ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9525-0576***Gurtovoy Elisey Sergeevich***Student**Tyumen State Medical University, Tyumen, Russia**ORCID ID: 0009-0001-0957-3580***Izvin Stepan Sergeevich***Student**Tyumen State University, Tyumen, Russia**ORCID ID: 0009-0008-1332-6719*

摘要：本文分析了2025年秋季太阳活动高峰期（地磁暴—GMS）期间，单次饮用咖啡对秋明国立大学体育学院36名青年学生适应潜能（AP，常规单位）的急性影响。研究采用R. M. Bayevsky的适应潜能理论。结果表明，即使单次饮用咖啡也会导致心率（HR，bpm）和收缩压（SAD，mmHg）显著升高（ $p < 0.05$ ），并增强心血管适应机制的张力，表明中枢血流动力学对咖啡因有显著反应，但这种反应会在短时间内恢复正常。在组织学生团体体育训练和设计体育活动训练方案时，应考虑这一因素。

关键词：体育大学学生，咖啡饮料，中心血液动力学，适应潜力，磁暴。

Abstract. This article analyzes the acute effects of a single coffee drink intake during a period of high solar activity (geomagnetic storm — GMS) in autumn 2025 on the level of adaptation potential (AP, conventional units) according to R. M. Bayevsky in 36 young adult students enrolled at the Institute of Physical

Culture, Tyumen State University. It was concluded that even a single consumption of a coffee drink causes a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in heart rate (HR, bpm) and elevation of systolic blood pressure (SAD, mm Hg), as well as increased tension of the cardiovascular adaptation mechanisms, indicating a pronounced response of central hemodynamics to caffeine that subsequently normalizes within a short period. This should be taken into account both when conducting physical training sessions in student groups and in designing the training process in sports activities.

Keywords: *students of a physical education university, coffee drink, central hemodynamics, adaptation potential, magnetic storms.*

Relevance

The domestic biophysicist Professor A. L. Chizhevsky first proposed the hypothesis in 1928 concerning the influence of magnetic storms on human health [9]. He noted that the influence of magnetic storms affects 50-70% of the Earth's population. Considerable attention is devoted to the study of the effects of solar geomagnetic activity on human health and its functional systems [3, 6, 7]. Over a number of years, the mechanisms of caffeine action on the functional systems of the human body have been studied [8]. In the available literature, we have not encountered studies reflecting the level of AP according to R. M. Bayevsky, and the impact of a single consumption of a coffee drink on it in students of a physical culture university in Siberia during GMS. We consider that any scientific research aimed at developing regional standards of the functional state of contemporary student youth is not only relevant but also highly sought after. We are firmly convinced that in contemporary higher education it should be established as a mandatory norm that a physical education instructor, prior to commencing classes with students, must possess comprehensive knowledge of their health status, functional condition, and adaptation potential. Moreover, in our view, the instructor's toolkit should comprise simple, safe, and valid assessment methods that permit their application under any conditions of the educational or training process. In practical activities, we employed a straightforward method of determining HR by palpating the radial artery with the subjects seated.

Research by the distinguished Russian physiologist, academician P. K. Anokhin [1], has demonstrated that the human organism inevitably responds with a reaction of functional systems to certain external environmental influences.

In the available literature, we found no studies examining the effects of a single intake of a coffee drink on HR, blood pressure, and AP according to Bayevsky in adolescent students of a sports university in Siberia during periods of high solar activity.

Research hypothesis

We hypothesize, firstly, that during periods of high solar activity, the consumption of a coffee drink by adolescent students significantly alters HR and SAD, thereby affecting the organism's adaptive potential. Secondly, GMS significantly and negatively influence central hemodynamics and AP, especially in male adolescents whose nocturnal sleep duration is less than 6 hours.

It should be noted that, to date, the hypothesis regarding the influence of high solar activity on human health has not been scientifically confirmed and consequently is not recognized by the international medical community.

Aim of the study: to characterize the influence of a single intake of a coffee drink on central hemodynamics and AP in physical education university students during high solar activity in a geomagnetic storm (GMS).

Materials and Methods

On a voluntary basis, using random sampling, 36 students from the Institute of Physical Culture at Tyumen State University were examined. During GMS, central hemodynamics and the level of AP according to R. M. Bayevsky were assessed following a single intake of a coffee drink, administered at a dose of one teaspoon (0.89 grams) per 75 ml of hot water with one teaspoon of sugar (7.14 grams). Sport qualifications — Masters of Sport of the Russian Federation of international class (MSMK), Masters of Sport of the Russian Federation (MS), Candidates for Master of Sport (CMS), and athletes of the first rank. The following formula was used to assess AP:

$$AP = 0.011 \times HR + 0.014 \times SAD + 0.008 \times DAD + 0.014 \times A + 0.009 \times MT - 0.009 \times R - 0.27,$$

where: HR — heart rate (beats/min), SAD and DAD — systolic and diastolic arterial pressure (mm Hg), A — age (years), MT — body mass (kg), R — height (body length, cm), 0.27 — constant term of the equation.

Assessment: less than 2.10 — satisfactory adaptation (reflects adequate functional capacity of the circulatory system); 2.11 to 3.20 — functional tension of adaptation mechanisms; 3.21 to 4.30 — unsatisfactory adaptation indicating a reduction in the functional capacity of the circulatory system accompanied by an insufficient adaptive response to physical exertion; greater than 4.30 — indicates a pronounced decline in the functional capacity of the circulatory system, characterized by a breakdown of the adaptation mechanisms of the whole organism.

HR was measured by the palpation method on the radial artery for one minute, and also determined using the MD300m pulse oximeter in the sitting position. We employed the auscultatory method for measuring blood pressure according to Nikolay Sergeevich Korotkov.

Prior to the study, male students were instructed to refrain from taking medications and strong stimulants, to go to bed at 23:00, and to wake at 07:00.

All measurements were conducted during classroom practical sessions. Baseline indicators of central hemodynamics and AP values were analyzed for the following sports disciplines:

- team sports (football, volleyball, basketball, tennis);
- speed-strength disciplines (jumping, sprinting, throwing, martial arts, weightlifting);
- complex coordination disciplines (acrobatics, gymnastics);
- cyclic disciplines (swimming, cross-country skiing, biathlon).

The results of the study were processed on a personal computer using modern electronic software (Statistica 6.1). The material analysis was performed based on mathematical calculations, including the arithmetic mean, the standard error of the mean, and the standard deviation. The significance of differences was assessed using Student's t-test [5].

Ethics of the study. The principles of voluntariness, and the rights and freedoms of the individual guaranteed by Articles 21 and 22 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, as well as the Order of the Ministry of Health and Social Development of the Russian Federation No. 774n dated August 31, 2010, 'On the Ethics Committee,' were adhered to. The study was conducted in compliance with the ethical standards outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and the European Community Directives (8/609/EEC) and with the informed verbal consent of the students.

Results and Discussion

From the anamnesis, it was established that the young men, firstly, have little knowledge about the influence of high levels of solar activity on human health and, secondly, do not consider themselves to be meteosensitive to solar effects. Through inquiry, it was established that at the peak of the GMS, students subjectively reported lethargy (14.9%), drowsiness (16.4%), poor sleep onset and disturbed nocturnal sleep (11.3%), morning fatigue (16.6%), irritability (9.2%), headache (18.5%), photophobia (1.6%), joint pain (0.68%), nasal bleeding (0.57%), decreased mental performance (8.8%), unwillingness to communicate (7.9%), reluctance to perform morning hygienic gymnastics (8.8%), and to participate in sports training (7.1%).

The values of AP according to Bayevsky in young men on normal days and after a single coffee drink intake during a high level of solar activity in autumn 2025 indicated that with decreasing nighttime sleep duration, the tension in adaptation mechanisms significantly increased ($p < 0.05$). Thus, on normal days with 8 hours of nighttime sleep, AP was 1.812 ± 0.073 conventional units, whereas during the GMS period it was 2.097 ± 0.072 conventional units (difference 0.285 conventional units); At a nighttime sleep duration of 7 hours, AP was 1.894 ± 0.079 arbitrary units and 2.288 ± 0.082 arbitrary units, respectively (difference 0.394 arbitrary units); at 6 hours — 1.967 ± 0.086 arbitrary units and 2.473 ± 0.082 arbitrary units (difference 0.472 arbitrary units); and at 5 hours or

less — 2.002 ± 0.091 arbitrary units and 2.774 ± 0.087 arbitrary units, respectively (difference 0.596 arbitrary units).

Sports qualification also affected the level of adaptation; that is, the higher the skill level, the less pronounced the response of functional systems to GMS. Thus, in MSMK the AP level on regular days was 1.794 ± 0.070 arbitrary units, whereas at the peak of the GMS it was 2.069 ± 0.084 arbitrary units (difference of 0.227 arbitrary units), i. e., it did not exceed normative values. The same was observed in MS — respectively 1.842 ± 0.074 and 2.098 ± 0.083 arbitrary units (difference 0.256 arbitrary units). Regarding CMS, AP values were 1.995 ± 0.082 and 2.403 ± 0.090 arbitrary units, respectively (difference 0.408 arbitrary units). In young men holding the first sports qualification, AP values were 2.082 ± 0.091 and 2.756 ± 0.096 arbitrary units, respectively, with a difference of 0.674 arbitrary units.

Thus, firstly, calculations demonstrated that the shorter the duration of night sleep, the significantly greater ($p < 0.05$) the functional tension of the adaptation mechanisms in the adolescent organism, which confirms our proposed hypothesis. Secondly, we observed that even a single consumption of a coffee drink by adolescents with varying sports qualifications significantly ($p < 0.05$) influences the level of AP during a GMS. Thus, in MSMK, the difference at the peak of solar activity was 0.285 units, whereas in young men holding the I sports category qualification it was 0.596 units. This should be taken into account during classroom sessions and sports or health-promoting training. Thirdly, the calculated values of the AP level during GMS do not significantly ($p > 0.05$) depend on the type of sport.

Based on the analysis of the material presented above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. In male students of a physical education university, the consumption of a coffee beverage during a GMS significantly ($p < 0.05$) influences central hemodynamics and the level of AP, particularly when the duration of nighttime sleep is less than 8 hours, thus confirming our hypothesis. Considering that a nighttime sleep duration of less than 8 hours adversely affects both the overall condition of the adolescent organism and the level of AP, we recommend maintaining its duration at no less than 8 hours to preserve health.

2. Young men holding the sports qualifications of MSMK and MS of Russia demonstrate a high level of central hemodynamic function organization and pronounced adaptive potential of the organism to counteract the negative influence of GMS.

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早期手术矫正创伤对重度合并创伤性脑损伤儿童心率昼夜节律的影响
**THE INFLUENCE OF EARLY SURGICAL CORRECTION
OF TRAUMATIC INJURIES ON THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM
OF HEART RATE IN CHILDREN WITH SEVERE COMBINED
TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURIES**

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摘要：在严重合并性创伤性脑损伤后的最初24小时内，整个综合强化治疗期间心率昼夜节律平均值相对于生理正常值呈现升高趋势。治疗期间，各组及各亚组间最大和最小心率值均无统计学差异。我们认为，观察到的这些变化是由于应激保护疗法对严重合并性创伤性脑损伤患儿血流动力学反应的有效性所致。在第1组中，第1亚组的心率昼夜节律近乎同步波动水平低于第2亚组和第3亚组。第2组中，第3亚组的应激限制矫正效果比第1亚组和第2亚组高5%。24小时内心率过度波动提示急性心力衰竭的发生，此时应在应用各种类型的心律失常阻滞剂的同时，辅以有效的代谢性心肌营养治疗，以对抗急性线粒体心肌功能不全。

关键词：手术矫正，心率昼夜节律，儿童，严重复合型创伤性脑损伤。

Abstract. *Within the first 24 hours after severe combined traumatic brain injury, the mean values of the mesor of heart rate circadian rhythm across the entire period of comprehensive intensive therapy demonstrated a tendency to increase relative to physiological norms. During treatment, no statistically significant differences in the maximum and minimum heart rate values were observed between groups and subgroups. We attribute the observed effects to the efficacy of stress-protective therapy on the hemodynamic response in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury. In group 1, subgroup 1 exhibited a lower level of nearly synchronous fluctuation in the circadian rhythm of heart rate compared to*

subgroups 2 and 3. Stress-limiting correction in group 2 was 5% more effective in subgroup 3 compared to subgroups 1 and 2. Excessive heart rate fluctuations within 24 hours correspond to the development of acute cardiac decompensation, in which the use of various types of heart rhythm blockers should be supplemented by effective metabolic cardiotropic therapy aimed at combating acute mitochondrial myocardial insufficiency.

Keywords: *surgical correction, circadian rhythm of heart rate, children, severe combined traumatic brain injury.*

Relevance. Numerous studies have established that traumatic brain injury (TBI) in children causes a marked disturbance of the circadian (daily) rhythms of cardiac function, manifested by instability, high amplitude fluctuations on the first to second day, and disruption of the normal “day-night” profile. Severe trauma activates the sympathetic nervous system, causing tachycardia and disruption of the physiological rhythm, which necessitates monitoring and timely elimination of factors leading to hemodynamic dysfunction, including heart failure. This is one of the key mechanisms contributing to the development of multiple organ failure, adversely affecting the effectiveness of treatment, outcomes, and prognosis of severe combined traumatic brain injury. This prompted the study of this problem in children [1-5].

Objective of the study. To investigate the influence of early surgical correction of traumatic injuries on the circadian rhythm of heart rate in children with severe combined traumatic brain injuries.

Materials and methods of the study. Patients hospitalized at RNCPMT from 2018 to 2021 (group 1) due to severe combined traumatic brain injuries were admitted following road traffic accidents (23) and falls from height (7). In group 2 (2022-2024), road traffic accidents accounted for 32 cases, and polytrauma involved 4 children. Patients in each group were studied in 3 subgroups. In group 1: patients of subgroup 1 (10) received conservative therapy based on indications; children of subgroup 2 (11) underwent extracranial surgical corrective procedures; and 9 patients of subgroup 3 received simultaneous cranial and extracranial surgical interventions based on indications. In group 1, patients of subgroup 1 without surgery stayed in the Intensive Care Unit for 26 days, subgroup 2 for 30 days, and subgroup 3 for 30 days. Patients examined in group 2 were also studied in three subgroups: Subgroup 1 — traumatized children who underwent conservative therapy without surgery for 29 days (13 children); in subgroup 2, comprehensive intensive therapy including extracranial surgery was performed over 20 days (15 children); children in subgroup 3 (28 days in the Intensive Care Unit) underwent extracranial plus cranial surgeries as indicated (8 children). Surgeries in group 2 were performed within the first hours after the children’s admission to the clinic. A statistically significant difference in

baseline injury severity between the groups was revealed. Thus, according to the ISS scale, children in the 2nd subgroup were in a condition 42% more severe, and in the 3rd subgroup 78% more severe ($p < 0.05$, respectively), compared to those in the 1st subgroup. Meanwhile, no statistically significant differences were identified according to the GI scale. With the improvement of the condition, stabilization of hemodynamics and respiration, and recovery of reflexes and consciousness, patients were transferred to the specialized department. Considering the determining role in the outcome and prognosis of the severity of the pathological condition during the first cycle of the acute systemic inflammatory response, we aimed to study, identify characteristics, and evaluate the influence of the stress-inflammatory response occurring within the first 10 days in children with severe combined traumatic brain injuries. To provide a comparative assessment of the identified deviations during the acute phase: within the first 10 days and the overall duration of intensive therapy in the Intensive Care Unit (up to 30 days). We attempted to analyze and provide a comparative assessment of comprehensive intensive therapy during different time periods: 2018-2021 and 2022-2024. During the latter period, significant organizational measures were undertaken to enhance the emergency service, aimed at minimizing the time from the moment of injury to the provision of urgent specialized care — known as the ‘golden hour’ — through the almost simultaneous execution of necessary resuscitation and surgical interventions.

Results and Discussion.

Table 1. Average amplitude-phase structure of heart rate circadian rhythm in groups 1 and 2

Parameters	Mesor	In the acrophase	In the bathyphase	Amplitude	Daily range
Group 1, Subgroup 1, 10 days	100±4	111±6	91±4	11±3	19±5
Group 2, Subgroup 1, 10 days	101±7	109±6	94±6	8±2	16±5
Group 1, Subgroup 2, 10 days	109±4 ^m	118±3	99±7	9±3	19±6
Group 2, Subgroup 2, 10 days	108±2	117±2	99±6	9±2	18±6
Group 1, Subgroup 3, 10 days	109±5	119±6	102±5 ^m	9±2	17±3
Group 2, Subgroup 3, 10 days	98±6	112±5	85±11*	14±4	27±9
Group 1, Subgroup 1, 26 days	102±4	112±6	92±4	11±4	21±6
Group 2, Subgroup 1, 29 days	102±6	115±7	88±7	13±5	27±11
Group 1 Subgroup 2 30 days	106±5	115±5	96±6	9±2	19±5
Group 2 Subgroup 2 20 days	106±4	116±5	97±6	10±3	19±7
Group 1 Subgroup 3 30 days	107±4	117±5	98±5	10±2	20±5
Group 2 Subgroup 3 28 days	102±9	118±11	86±10	16±4	32±8

* — Significant relative to the indicator in Group 1

^m — Significant difference relative to the indicator in Subgroup 1 of Group 1

The mean values of the mesor of heart rate circadian rhythm showed a tendency towards an increase relative to physiological norms (Table 1). A significant 9% increase in the mesor of heart rate circadian rhythm ($p < 0.05$) was observed in patients operated on for extracranial injuries, indicating a comparatively more pronounced stress response of hemodynamics in children after extracranial surgeries during the first 10 days in Group 1. A significant increase in heart rate by 12% ($p < 0.05$) in the bathyphase during the first 10 days following combined cranial and extracranial surgeries in children of group 1 was attributed to relatively lower protection against traumatic stress in this group. In contrast, in the third subgroup of group 2, a decrease in heart rate in the bathyphase by 16% ($p < 0.05$) was observed during the first 10 days. These observed differences reflect a more effective stress-limiting correction in the injured patients of group 2.

Table 2. Comparative assessment of the dynamics of the mesor of heart rate circadian rhythm

Days	Group 1 Subgroup 1	Group 2 Subgroup 1	Group 1 Subgroup 2	Group 2 Subgroup 2	Group 1 Subgroup 3	Group 2 Subgroup 3
1	107±6	113±7	112±10	108±5	112±6	96±7
2	104±4	109±4	117±4	111±3	117±2	104±4
3	104±4	109±2	115±3	111±2	113±4	103±3
4	100±4	107±2	109±3	109±2	111±4	110±4
5	94±5*	103±4	107±4	103±4	101±4	102±3
6	91±2*	97±3*	105±3	103±4	103±2	97±7
7	95±3*	95±3*	108±3	108±3	99±4*	85±4
8	98±3*	92±3*	113±2	110±3	110±5	90±7
9	100±2	91±3*	104±4	109±4	113±3	95±8
10	106±3	96±3*	105±5	108±7	115±5	98±13
11	101±3	105±3	107±4	106±4	107±5	107±6
12	106±2	106±6	102±3	113±6	110±4	119±6*
13	94±4*	95±10	97±4*	106±8	110±4	127±12*
14	104±3	105±8	95±4*	99±3*	100±4*	121±7*
15	97±5	104±6	100±4	102±2	110±3	120±5*
16	99±6	92±9	103±3	103±5	112±5	121±4*
17	106±6	104±4	96±6	102±4	108±4	103±7
18	96±8	109±7	100±4	108±2	102±3*	103±5
19	99±5	98±8	108±2	111±3	103±4	104±9
20	99±3	98±7	100±5	92±3	105±6	84±5
21	98±5	103±7	99±4		110±7	88±6
22	103±6	102±6	115±9		107±8	102±13
23	109±7	100±6	106±5		106±3	100±10
24	113±7	104±8	108±3		105±3	93±8

Days	Group 1 Subgroup 1	Group 2 Subgroup 1	Group 1 Subgroup 2	Group 2 Subgroup 2	Group 1 Subgroup 3	Group 2 Subgroup 3
25	103±4	116±6	103±8		102±3	106±11
26	112±4	118±9	99±4		103±4	87±7
27		97±11	107±2		109±8	78±7
28		99±10	103±5		101±7	111±11
29		89±6	111±2		98±3	
30			125±7		101±4	

* — significant difference compared to the value on day 1.

On the day of injury, a tendency to increase the mesor of heart rate circadian rhythm was observed in all groups. Under conservative therapy, group 1 showed a significant decrease in the mesor of heart rate circadian rhythm as early as day 5 by 12% ($p<0.05$), and group 2 on day 6 by 14% ($p<0.05$), maintaining this level during days 5 and 6 (Table 2), with subsequent fluctuations within the range of the mesor on day 1 of treatment. In the 2nd subgroup, a decrease in the mesor of heart rate circadian rhythm was detected in the 1st group on days 13 and 14 by 13% ($p<0.05$). Whereas in the 2nd group, heart rate reduction of 9% was observed only on day 14 ($p<0.05$). In the 3rd subgroup of the 1st group, heart rate slowing of 12% ($p<0.05$) was identified on days 14 and 18. Whereas in the 2nd group, an increase in the mesor of heart rate circadian rhythm by 21%, 29%, and 25% was found on days 12 through 16 ($p<0.05$, respectively). The observed difference in the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group corresponds to negative dynamics on days 12-16, caused by the development of secondary complicating factors (infection, emergence of new inflammatory foci, disseminated intravascular coagulation). The finding corresponds to a more severe initial severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Table 3. Average heart rate circadian rhythm over 10 days after severe combined traumatic brain injury

Hours	Group 1, Subgroup 1, 10 days	Group 2, Subgroup 1, 10 days	Group 1, Subgroup 2, 10 days	Group 2, Subgroup 2, 10 days	Group 1, Subgroup 3, 10 days	Group 2, Subgroup 3, 10 days
8	105±6	102±7	114±4	110±4	113±7	102±9
9	103±7	102±8	112±4	111±3	114±5	104±10
10	104±6	101±8	112±4	110±2	112±7	101±9
11	103±6	99±9	111±4	110±4	112±3	99±10
12	101±6	104±7	109±7	110±4	110±5	100±8
13	104±6	103±8	110±6	107±7	109±6	100±7
14	100±5	101±7	108±6	108±5	111±8	97±5
15	98±7	101±8	109±6	108±5	108±7	100±6
16	98±5	101±6	109±5	109±4	108±6	101±7
17	98±4	100±6	111±5	107±4	109±8	99±6

Hours	Group 1, Subgroup 1, 10 days	Group 2, Subgroup 1, 10 days	Group 1, Subgroup 2, 10 days	Group 2, Subgroup 2, 10 days	Group 1, Subgroup 3, 10 days	Group 2, Subgroup 3, 10 days
18	100±5	103±6	109±5	107±4	113±7	97±8
19	101±6	103±6	110±6	108±5	110±6	97±8
20	98±6	99±7	108±7	108±4	110±6	100±9
21	98±6	101±8	111±6	108±4	109±5	100±5
22	96±5	101±8	111±6	106±4	108±7	97±7
23	98±5	100±7	111±6	106±5	110±5	98±8
24	98±5	102±6	107±6	106±5	108±7	98±8
1	97±6	100±7	106±6	107±4	107±6	97±8
2	98±5	102±7	106±5	107±4	107±7	93±10
3	100±5	100±9	107±6	107±5	107±7	96±11
4	100±5	99±8	106±7	107±5	106±7	93±12
5	99±4	100±7	107±4	107±4	107±5	95±13
6	100±4	97±6	110±5	108±5	109±6	94±11
7	102±5	102±6	110±4	109±3	108±7	98±7

The accepted standards for the projection of the acrophase of the heart rate circadian rhythm are between 9 and 11 a.m., and for the bathyphase between 11 p.m. and 2 a.m. When analyzing phase characteristics in Subgroup 1 of Group 1 during the first 10 days, the acrophase projection was identified at 8 a.m. (105±6), and the bathyphase at 10 p.m. (96±5). In Group 2, the acrophase was shifted to 1 p.m. (104±7), and the bathyphase to 6 a.m. (97±6). In Subgroup 2 of Group 1, the acrophase was at 8 a.m. (114±4), and the bathyphase at 1 a.m. (106±6). In Group 2, the acrophase occurred at 9 a.m. (111±3), with the bathyphase at 10 p.m. (106±4). In Subgroup 3 of Group 1, the acrophase projection was noted at 9 a.m. (114±5), and the bathyphase at 4 a.m. (106±4). In Group 2, Subgroup 3, the acrophase was similarly observed within the normal projection at 9 a.m. (104±10), and the bathyphase at 2 a.m. (93±10) (Table 3). Thus, During the first 10 days of intensive comprehensive therapy, no significant differences were observed between groups and subgroups in the maximum and minimum heart rate values. We attribute these findings to the effectiveness of stress-protective therapy in modulating the hemodynamic response to severe combined traumatic brain injury in children.

In Group 1, Subgroup 1 demonstrated a lower amplitude of almost synchronous fluctuations in the circadian rhythm of heart rate compared to Subgroups 2 and 3. Specifically, the heart rate circadian rhythm value in Subgroup 1 of Group 1 was 101±2 beats per minute, in Subgroup 2-106±2 beats per minute, and in Subgroup 3-107±3 beats per minute; thus, heart rate acceleration in the most severely affected children was 6% (p<0.05) (Fig.1). In contrast, Group 2 showed values of 107±1, 107±3, and 102±2 beats per minute in Subgroups 1, 2, and 3, respectively. That is,

stress-limiting correction in group 2 was 5% ($p < 0.05$) more effective in subgroup 3 compared to subgroups 1 and 2 (Figure 2). This possibly had a positive, though insufficiently effective, impact due to the more severe brain injury in children of subgroup 3 within group 2. It should be noted that most patients demonstrated relatively small shifts in the projection of acrophases and bathyphases in both groups, confirming the stress-protective effect of intensive therapy as a whole.

Fig. 1. Circadian rhythm of heart rate in Group 1 in the Intensive Care Unit

Fig. 2. Circadian rhythm of heart rate in Group 2 in the Intensive Care Unit

Fig. 3. Amplitude of heart rate circadian rhythm in Group 1.

Fig. 4. Amplitude of heart rate circadian rhythm in Group 2.

Relatively more extensive complex stress-limiting therapy, which led to less pronounced spikes in the amplitude of heart rate circadian rhythm observed in subgroups 2 and 3, may also be related to the use of mechanical ventilation in the traumatized children of Group 1 (Fig. 3). In Group 2, the initially lower amplitude

of heart rate circadian rhythm during the first 10 days increased in the following days. Initially, the amplitude of the heart rate circadian rhythm on the 1st day in subgroup 3 progressively increased to peak values on days 23 and 28, indicating instability of cardiac function, which we attribute to secondary structural complications and severe apallic syndrome, where the deficit of healthy tissue results in loss of function of the brain's regulatory centers (Fig.4).

Fig.5. Daily fluctuations of heart rate in group 1.

Fig.6. Daily fluctuations of heart rate in group 2.

The indicators of daily fluctuations in heart rate in groups 1 and 2 (Figs. 5 and 6) corresponded to the characteristics of changes in the amplitude of the heart rate circadian rhythm. It is reasonable to conclude that moderate, significant, and excessive daily fluctuations of heart rhythm can be used as reference points. The latter corresponds to the development of acute cardiac decompensation, where the use of various types of heart rate blockers should be complemented by effective metabolic therapy aimed at combating acute mitochondrial myocardial insufficiency. The latter is quite likely to play a positive role by enhancing the effectiveness of nootropic therapy, correcting immunodeficient conditions, and generally increasing the viability of children after severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Conclusion. Within the first 24 hours after severe combined traumatic brain injury, the mean values of the mesor of heart rate circadian rhythm across the entire period of comprehensive intensive therapy demonstrated a tendency to increase relative to physiological norms. During treatment, no statistically significant differences in the maximum and minimum heart rate values were observed between groups and subgroups. We attribute the observed effects to the efficacy of stress-protective therapy on the hemodynamic response in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury. In group 1, subgroup 1 exhibited a lower level of nearly synchronous fluctuation in the circadian rhythm of heart rate compared to subgroups 2 and 3. Stress-limiting correction in group 2 was 5% more effective in subgroup 3 compared to subgroups 1 and 2. Excessive heart rate fluctuations

within 24 hours correspond to the development of acute cardiac decompensation, in which the use of various types of heart rhythm blockers should be supplemented by effective metabolic cardiotropic therapy aimed at combating acute mitochondrial myocardial insufficiency.

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淋巴结老化程度的特征取决于引流区域
**CHARACTERISTICS OF LYMPH NODES AGING INTENSITY
DEPENDING ON THE DRAINED AREA**

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注释：评估区域决定因素原理对衰老过程中内脏淋巴结结构的影响至关重要。实验表明，淋巴结衰老转化的强度存在差异，且与引流区域相关。相对于结构区域和生物元素的基本参数，肠系膜淋巴结的变化比气管支气管淋巴结更为显著。每个区域淋巴结的贡献都十分重要，应在研究中加以考虑。

关键词：实验，淋巴结，隔室，微量元素，衰老。

Annotation. *It is important to assess the impact of the regional determinant principle on the structure of visceral lymph nodes during aging. In the experiment, it was determined that the intensity of the aging transformation of lymph nodes varies and is related to the drainage area. The mesenteric lymph nodes undergo more significant changes than the tracheobronchial lymph nodes, relative to the basic parameters of structural zones and bioelements. The contribution of each regional lymph node is significant, and it should be considered in research.*

Keywords: *experiment, lymph nodes, compartments, trace elements, ageing.*

Relevance. Lymph nodes maintain their efficiency through interaction with the organs they drain. The structure and functions of organs and their lymphoid apparatus change with age, which affects the quality and life expectancy [1]. Opinions

differ in how lymph node restructuring affects the prognosis of aging and depends on the state of its compartments and the level of bioelements-antioxidants. Nevertheless, the topic of studying the specifics of lymph node interaction with drained territories is worthy of discussion and remains an important trend in research.

Objective: it seems important to assess how the principle of regional determinant affects visceral lymph nodes and therefore will affect their restructuring in aging.

Material and methods. The experiment involved 80 white Wistar rats at different ages: young (3-5 months) and old (18-20 months). We investigated lymph nodes regional for the bronchopulmonary system and intestinal tract. Lymph node morphometry information is based on histological method data and statistical analysis of dynamic data series in StatPlus Pro 2009.

System of dynamic series includes characteristics of intensity [2]. The growth coefficient (GC) is the ratio of the initial and final levels of the dynamic series in the time segment (the initial (basic) level is taken as one). The derivatives are growth rate (baseline taken as 100%) and the rate of increase:

$$GR = (P_t / P_b) \times 100\%$$

$$IR = GR - 100\%$$

where GR is the growth rate, IR is the increase rate, P_t is a parameter of the current period, P_b is a parameter of the base (initial) level. The interpretation of the value of the growth coefficient (rate) is as follows: more than 100% — excess; about 100% — stability; less than 100% — declining. The rate of increase in % distinguishes this level from the initial one.

We used the high-tech RFA SI method of the Institute of Nuclear Physics of the SB RAS to determine bioelements (iron, manganese, copper, zinc, selenium) related to antioxidants [3].

Results. The drainage territory acts as a determinant for age-induced processes, putting its imprint on lymph node remodeling. Old age is associated with the specificity of the region, and it is characterized by a deviation in the size of immunoreactive compartments and the concentration of bioelements in lymph nodes. The contribution of each regional lymph node is incredibly significant, and this should be discussed from the perspective of the aging lymphological concept.

The lymphatic territories of the respiratory system and gastrointestinal tract differ from each other in their morphophysiological parameters due to the feature of interaction with the environment. This determines the architecture of senile lymph nodes. Age dependence manifests differently in each of the visceral lymph nodes, judging by the intensity of remodeling their compartments (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Growth coefficient for certain compartments of visceral lymph nodes in aging. C is a capsule; Ss is a subcapsular sinus; Cp is a cortical plateau; P is a paracortex; F1 is a primary follicle; F2 is a secondary follicle; Mc are medullary cords; Ms is a medullary lymphatic sinus; 1 — the mesenteric lymph node; 2 — the tracheobronchial lymph node.

The growth coefficient characterizes the intensity of change in the dimension of compartments in lymph nodes belonging to different drainage regions. The intensity of these changes has common and individual patterns. The growth coefficient exceeds the baseline, showing an increase in the capsular-trabecular compartment in both lymph nodes. The positive increase rate was 61% and 48% for mesenteric and tracheobronchial lymph nodes, respectively. This is due to capsule thickening and organ stroma collagenization [4]. Most compartments are characterized by a lag in the growth coefficient from the base index, it is less than one. The sizes of these compartments decrease, differing in the amount of negative increase rate in visceral lymph nodes. The negative increase rate is for the cortical plateau -52% and -5%, for the brain sinus -48% and -15% in the mesenteric and tracheobronchial lymph nodes, respectively. Almost the same negative increase rate is present in the paracortical area (-12% and -13%), and stronger regression for secondary lymphoid follicles (-48% and -56%) in both lymph nodes. The sizes of subcapsular sinus, primary lymphoid follicles change in the opposite direction, and they acquire a positive increase rate in the tracheobronchial lymph node and a negative increase rate in the mesenteric lymph node. Conversely, the size of medullary cords determines the positive increase rate in the mesenteric lymph node and the

negative increase rate in the tracheobronchial lymph node. It has been determined that age transformation occurs with different intensity in lymph nodes belonging to the broncho-pulmonary system or gastrointestinal tract.

The microelement status of lymph nodes differs from one another, judging by the magnitude of the growth coefficient relative to the base level (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Growth rate for trace elements in visceral lymph nodes undergoing senile changes. 1 — the mesenteric lymph node, 2 — the tracheobronchial lymph node

The growth coefficient for manganese exceeds the baseline, showing a positive increase rate of 26% and 32% in the mesenteric and tracheobronchial lymph nodes, respectively. Aging leads to an increase in manganese concentration in both lymph nodes, and this is an indication of the element's involvement in the formation of excess connective tissue, increasing the area of the stroma [4, 5].

The growth coefficient for iron, copper, zinc, selenium does not reach the baseline in the mesenteric lymph node. We see a negative increase rate in the range from -30% to -17%, as evidence of the development of deficiency of these bioelements in the senile mesenteric lymph node. Aging does not alter the concentration of iron and copper in the tracheobronchial lymph node. The growth coefficient for iron and copper is on the baseline as evidence of stability in aging. This is not the case with zinc and selenium. The growth coefficient is located below the baseline for zinc and selenium in the tracheobronchial lymph node. A deficiency is formed for zinc and selenium, which correlates with the involution of lymphoid tissue.

Obviously, the mesenteric lymph node is more susceptible to senile changes, as its structure and trace element parameters differ significantly from the baseline.

Discussion. Regional lymph nodes are part of the immunoprotective system, and they are responsible for a certain area. The lymphoid apparatus of organs protects against the influx of antigens from the environment using different immunoprotecting factors [6].

Different intensity of age transformation of visceral lymph nodes is accompanied by reduction of drainage-detoxification function in the territory of a certain organ. Each of the drained regions experiences a different antigenic load. The greatest antigenic load is observed in the mesenteric lymph node due to the work of the gastrointestinal tract. Air contact for the tracheobronchial system is inferior to the digestive tract in the volume of antigen intake. This affects the remodeling of visceral lymph nodes and determines their regional individual response when aging.

Thus, the mesenteric lymph node has a greater rate of change for compartments and bioelements compared to tracheobronchial. The difference in aging intensity is due to the original lymph node morphotype and the features of lymphatorium drainage. Senile changes are explained by a feature of the lymph region to which the «organ — lymph node» system refers, where the organ is dominant due to direct contact with the external environment. The results confirm the principle of regional determinant for each of visceral lymph nodes [1] and explain the pathogenesis of coming senile changes of peripheral lymphoid organs.

Conclusion. The belonging of the lymph node to a certain territory determines the process of its age-induced remodeling. Changes in mesenteric and tracheobronchial lymph nodes occur with different intensity, demonstrating the principle of regional determinant. Compartment changes and trace element concentrations of a region-dependent nature are indicative. The mesenteric lymph node is subject to changes to a greater extent than the tracheobronchial one relative to the base level.

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用于稳定小腿-足部距骨的环形三平面系统及其临床意义
**THE RING THREE-PLANE SYSTEM FOR STABILIZING
THE TALUS IN THE LOWER LEG-FOOT SEGMENT
AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE FOR CLINICAL PRACTICE**

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摘要：小腿-足部距骨由三个稳定环固定，防止移位。这三个稳定环分别位于三个相互垂直的平面（额状面、矢状面和轴位面）上，并与三个相互垂直的轴线平行。A型踝关节骨折（下胫腓联合骨折）中，稳定环在一个下胫腓联合水平处断裂。B型踝关节骨折（跨胫腓联合骨折）中，稳定环在两个水平处受损——下胫腓联合水平和胫腓联合水平。C型踝关节骨折（上胫腓联合骨折）中，稳定环在三个水平处受损——下胫腓联合水平、胫腓联合水平和胫腓联合水平。

根据AO/ASIF分类，踝关节骨折分为A、B、C三种类型，根据距骨稳定环（位于小腿-足部节段的不同水平）中骨韧带损伤的数量，可将踝关节不稳定性细分为三个等级。我们将A1型和B1型踝关节骨折归为一级不稳定性，A2型和B2型骨折归为二级不稳定性，A3型、B3型、C1型、C2型和C3型骨折归为三级不稳定性。

关键词：踝关节骨折，距骨，半脱位，骨间韧带联合。

Abstract: *The talus in the lower leg-foot segment is stabilized against displacement by three stabilization rings, which are positioned on three mutually perpendicular planes (frontal, sagittal, and axial) relative to three mutually perpendicular axes. In infra-syndesmotoc ankle fractures type A, the stabilization rings are disrupted at one infra-syndesmotoc level. In a trans-syndesmotoc ankle fracture type B the stabilization rings are damaged at two levels-infra-syndesmotoc and at the syndesmosis level. In a supra-syndesmotoc ankle fracture type C the stabilization rings are damaged at three levels-infra-syndesmotoc, at the syndesmosis level, and supra-syndesmotoc.*

Each ankle fracture type A, B, and C according to the AO/ASIF classification can be subdivided into three degrees of ankle joint instability, based on the number of bone-ligament injuries identified in the stabilization rings of the talus within the lower leg-foot segment located at different levels. To the first degree of instability

we attribute ankle fractures of types A1 and B1, to the second degree fractures of types A2 and B2, and to the third degree fractures of types A3, B3, C1, C2, and C3.

Keywords: *ankle fracture, talus, subluxation, interosseous syndesmosis.*

Aim: to theoretically substantiate the three-plane talus stabilization system in the lower leg-foot segment.

Discussion: In the literature, a talus stabilization ring in the ankle joint is described by J. Shatzker and M. Tile (1987), who conceptualize ankle joint stability as derived from the joint function of four bone-ligamentous structures, namely: the lateral malleolus and the external collateral ligaments; of the medial malleolus and the deltoid ligament; of the anterior inferior tibiofibular syndesmosis ligament and its bony attachments; of the posterior inferior tibiofibular syndesmosis ligament and the posterior border of the tibia [1].

We consider that the role of the lateral malleolus in stabilizing the talus against displacement in the ankle joint cannot be evaluated without accounting for the entire fibula and the function of the tibiofibular syndesmosis, the proximal tibiofibular joint, and the interosseous membrane [2].

When forces acting on the talus occur in the frontal plane from outside to inside or from inside to outside, they are dissipated by the function of the entire fibula. The foregoing allows us to regard as a stabilization ring — preventing displacement of the talus in the frontal plane from the medial and lateral sides during rotation around the foot's longitudinal axis — the medial collateral ligaments, medial malleolus, tibia, proximal tibiofibular joint, fibula, interosseous membrane, lateral malleolus, lateral collateral ligaments, and calcaneus. This stabilization ring we termed the 'large' stabilization ring, positioned in the frontal plane.

When forces acting on the talus occur in the sagittal plane in an anteroposterior or posteroanterior direction, they are counteracted by the posterior edge of the distal metaepiphysis of the tibia, with the overhanging posterior interosseous ligament and the tension of the anterior surface of the ankle joint capsule. Conversely, when forces acting on the talus occur in the sagittal plane in a posteroanterior direction, they are counteracted by the anterior edge of the distal metaepiphysis of the tibia, with the tension of the posterior surface of the ankle joint capsule. This allows us to consider the "large" talus stabilization ring that restrains talus displacement in the sagittal plane as comprising: the tibia, the anterior edge of the distal tibial metaepiphysis, the anterior portion of the ankle joint capsule, the talus, the calcaneus, the posterior portion of the ankle joint capsule, and the posterior edge of the distal tibial metaepiphysis.

The osseous and ligamentous structures located at the level of the interosseous syndesmosis — the fibula, the anterior tibiofibular ligament, the tibia, and the

posterior tibiofibular ligament — are delineated by us as a separate talus stabilization ring of the lower leg-foot segment, positioned in the axial plane.

The axial stabilization ring at the level of the interosseous syndesmosis theoretically divides the ‘large’ stabilization rings, located in the frontal and sagittal planes, into two distinct levels. The stabilization rings that prevent displacement of the talus in the frontal plane within the lower leg-foot segment are situated distal to the interosseous syndesmosis. Anatomical injuries within this specific ring are typical for the infrasyn-desmotic level of ankle fractures according to the AO/ASIF classification.

Stabilization rings located proximal to the tibiofibular syndesmosis, consisting of the fibula, interosseous membrane, proximal tibiofibular joint, and tibia. Anatomical injuries in the specified rings at this level are characteristic of suprasyn-desmotic ankle fractures according to the AO/ASIF classification.

The three specified stabilization rings, arranged in the sagittal, frontal, and axial planes within the lower leg-foot segment, collectively form a unified system for stabilizing the talus in the lower leg-foot segment, which prevents its displacement relative to three mutually perpendicular axes in three mutually perpendicular planes, observed in type A, B, and C fractures according to the AO classification [3,4].

Materials and Methods. Identification of injuries within the stabilization rings of the talus in different planes for infrasyn-desmotic (type A), transsyn-desmotic (type B), and suprasyn-desmotic ankle fractures (type C) is achievable by detecting bone, osteoligamentous, or ligamentous damage during radiological evaluation of the injured lower leg-foot segment: radiography, and especially CT and/or MRI, as these modalities enable assessment of damage to the talus stabilization rings in three planes, particularly in the axial plane, which cannot be accomplished with standard ankle joint radiography [5].

Results and discussion. Ankle fractures of **type A** according to the AO/ASIF classification, involving infra-syn-desmotic injury of the fibula, occur during supination, pronation, and rotational foot movements.

Figure 1 shows photoradiographs of an infra-syn-desmotic ankle fracture (**type A**) taken in various projections of the injured ankle joint, along with diagrams of the damaged stabilization rings.

Figure 1. Infra-syndesmotom ankle fracture (type A) with diagrams of stabilization ring injuries at the same level: infra-syndesmotom (injuries within the stabilization ring are marked by arrows).

A common feature of infra-syndesmotom PL (**type A**) is injury to one to three talar stabilization rings located at the same infra-syndesmotom level (the exception being type A3 ankle fractures with a fracture of the posterior edge of the distal tibial metaphysis, involving damage at two levels). Figure 1 presents photoradiographs of an infra-syndesmotom ankle fracture taken in multiple projections of the injured ankle joint, accompanied by diagrams of the damaged stabilization rings situated in three planes.

During eversion movement of the foot with elements of pronation, an ankle fracture of type B according to the AO-ASIF classification occurs, characterized initially by an avulsion fracture of the medial malleolus or rupture of the deltoid ligament; that is, the talus stabilization ring in the ankle joint, located in the frontal (coronal) plane at the infra-syndesmotom level, is damaged. Subsequently, the second stabilization ring, located in the axial plane at the level of the interosseous syndesmosis, becomes damaged, resulting in a ligamentous (transsyndesmotom) fracture of the fibula, provided that no anatomical injuries are present proximal to the interosseous syndesmosis. Common to infra-syndesmotom ankle fractures (type

B) is damage to the stabilization rings of the talus, which are situated at two levels: the infra-syndesmotic level and the level of the interosseous syndesmosis.

Figure 2 shows photoradiographs of an infra-syndesmotic ankle fracture (**type B**), along with diagrams of the damaged stabilization rings at two levels: infra-syndesmotic and at the level of the interosseous syndesmosis. The detected damages in the stabilization rings are marked with arrows.

Fig. 2. Syndesmotic ankle fracture (**type B**) with diagrams of stabilization ring damage at two levels: sub-syndesmotic and at the level of the syndesmosis (damage to the stabilization rings indicated by arrows).

As shown in the diagram (Fig. 3), ankle fractures of **type C**, characterized by supra-syndesmotic injury to the fibula, result from a pronation force (external rotation of the foot around its longitudinal axis). At the first stage, as a result of tensile stress in the medial compartment of the ankle joint, there is a rupture of the deltoid ligament or an avulsion fracture of the medial malleolus. The talus stabilization ring located at the infra-syndesmotic level is damaged. At the second stage, having gained freedom, the laterally displaced talus exerts pressure on the lateral malleolus, resulting in bending of the fibular shaft and its fracture 5-7 cm proximal to the interosseous syndesmosis, i.e. the talus stabilization ring located proximal to the interosseous syndesmosis level is damaged. At the third stage, the fractured distal part of the fibula is displaced at an angle to its longitudinal axis, which sequentially leads to rupture of the ligaments of the interosseous syndesmosis and the interosseous membrane from bottom to top, corresponding to damage of the talus stabilization ring at the level of the interosseous syndesmosis.

Characteristic of ankle fracture type C is damage to the talus stabilization rings located at three levels: infra-syndesmotiс, at the level of the syndesmosis, and at the supra-syndesmotiс level.

Figure 3 presents photoradiographs of a supra-syndesmotiс ankle fracture (type C), along with diagrams of the damaged stabilization rings situated at different levels; the numbers indicate the identified injuries at these levels.

Fig. 3. Supra-syndesmotiс ankle fracture (type C) showing the damage to the stabilization rings at three levels: infra-syndesmotiс, at the syndesmosis level, and supra-syndesmotiс (the identified damages in the stabilization rings are indicated by arrows and numbers).

Each AO/ASIF ankle fracture type A, B, and C can be divided into three degrees of instability, depending on the severity of the fracture. The severity of the ankle fracture depends on the number of bone-ligament injuries within the stabilization rings that prevent talus displacement, as well as the levels of their involvement in the lower leg-foot segment.

To the first degree of instability — we classified isolated (bony or ligamentous) damage of a single “anatomical element” within one stabilization ring of the talus at one level. For example, ankle fractures of type AI, BI — these injuries are characterized by a single isolated bony or ligamentous damage in one stabilization

ring of the talus at one level. Ankle fracture type AI (characterized by isolated damage in one stabilization ring located at the infra-syndesmotic level). Ankle fracture type BI (there is an isolated injury in one stabilization ring located at the level of the interosseous syndesmosis). The first degree of talus instability is designated by the Roman numeral I.

The second degree of instability includes ankle fractures in which two “anatomical elements” are injured in one or two different stabilization rings located at one or two different levels. Ankle fractures type **A2, B2** — involve injury to two “anatomical elements” in one or two different stabilization rings located at one (infra-syndesmotic) or two different levels (infra-syndesmotic and at the level of the syndesmosis). Type A2 ankle fracture (involving damage to two anatomical elements within a single stabilization ring located at the infra-syndesmotic level). Type B2 ankle fracture (involving damage to two anatomical elements across two stabilization rings positioned at the infra-syndesmotic and syndesmosis levels). The second degree of talus instability is designated by the Roman numeral II.

The third degree of instability encompasses ankle fractures involving damage to three or more osteoligamentous structures within two or three stabilization rings of the talus, situated at one, two, or three distinct levels. Ankle fractures of types **A3, B3, C1, C2, C3** have damage to three or more elements within the three stabilization rings of the talus, located at two or three different injury levels.

Ankle fractures of types **A3, B3** have damage to three anatomical elements across two stabilization rings situated at the infra-syndesmotic level and at the level of the interosseous syndesmosis. Ankle fractures of types **C1, C2, C3** have damage to at least three anatomical elements in all three stabilization rings situated at the infra-syndesmotic level, at the level of the interosseous syndesmosis, and supra-syndesmotic level. The third degree of instability of the talus is indicated by the Roman numeral III. The peculiarity of this group of injuries is that fractures of types C1, C2 do not involve damage to the articular surface of the tibia; displacement of fragments occurs in one or two planes. We have distinguished them as a separate group and propose to designate it with the Roman numeral **IIIA**. Fractures of types A3, B3, and C3 involve damage to the articular surface of the tibia; displacement of fragments occurs in two or three planes. We have distinguished them as a separate group and propose to designate it with the Roman numeral **IIIB**.

Depending on the displacement of the talus relative to the articular surface of the distal metaepiphysis of the tibia, we have distinguished three subtypes of severity of bone-ligament structure damage in ankle fractures. To the first subtype of ankle injury severity (Subtype 1 -Normal), we assigned ankle fractures without subluxation of the talus — **N**; the second subtype (Subtype 2 -Subluxation) is characterized by subluxation of the talus — **S**; the third subtype (Subtype 3 -Dislocation) is characterized by dislocation of the foot — **D**.

Conclusions

1. The spatial stabilization of the talus in the lower leg-foot segment is ensured by stabilization rings arranged in three mutually perpendicular planes (frontal, sagittal, and axial) with respect to three mutually perpendicular axes at each of its stabilization levels (infra-syndesmotiс, syndesmotiс, and supra-syndesmotiс).

2. For each type of ankle injury classified by AO/ASIF, the talar stabilization rings within the lower leg-foot segment, positioned in three mutually perpendicular planes, exhibit specific levels of damage, numbers of injuries, and distinct characteristics of anatomical lesions.

3. The criterion for a stable or unstable ankle fracture depends not only on the number and severity of osseous and ligamentous injuries in the lower leg-foot segment according to fracture types A, B, or C, but also on the number of damaged stabilization rings securing the talus against displacement and the levels of their damage (infra-syndesmotiс, trans-syndesmotiс, and supra-syndesmotiс) within the lower leg-foot segment.

4. All types of ankle fractures according to the AO/ASIF classification can be divided into three degrees of ankle joint instability, depending on the number of osteoligamentous injuries in the identified talus stabilization rings within the lower leg-foot segment, situated at different levels.

5. Every ankle fracture can be differentiated according to fracture type A, B, or C based on the AO/ASIF classification, by the type of instability, and by the severity subtype of injuries to the bone-ligamentous structures in the ankle joint area depending on the pattern of talus displacement, which allows for establishing the necessary criteria for a differentiated approach to selecting their treatment method.

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地方政府医生V. N. BRAGIN对斯拉维亚诺塞尔布斯克区医疗保健系统发展的贡献

**CONTRIBUTION OF ZEMSTVO PHYSICIAN V. N. BRAGIN
TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM
OF THE SLAVYANOSERBSK DISTRICT**

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注释。本文利用20世纪初的档案资料和出版物，重构了地方政府医生瓦西里·尼基托维奇·布拉金（1873年—？）的职业生涯。布拉金是叶卡捷琳诺斯拉夫省斯拉维亚诺塞尔布斯克区医疗卫生史上的关键人物。本研究旨在阐明，在地方政府医疗卫生事业的和平发展时期（1898–1914年），一位医生的个人举措如何成为第一次世界大战极端条件下医疗卫生系统有效运转的基础。本文采用了历史比较研究和文献分析的方法。研究表明，由V. N. Bragin发起的伊万诺沃地方自治医院基础设施现代化改造、外科手术的引入、传染病科的建立以及集中供水系统的建设，使得该地区在1914年后能够迅速扩展其疗养院和医院网络。这位医生的工作被视为机构成功适应的典范：从局部改进到形成可持续的医疗保健模式，能够在危机中迅速扩大规模。结论认为，V. N. Bragin的贡献不仅对医学史具有重要价值，而且对现代医疗保健领域的管理实践也具有借鉴意义。

关键词：地方自治医疗，V. N. Bragin，斯拉维亚诺塞尔布斯克区，第一次世界大战

Annotation. Using archival materials and publications from the early 20th century, this article reconstructs the professional activities of zemstvo doctor

Vasily Nikitovich Bragin (1873–?), a key figure in the history of healthcare in the Slavyanoserbsk district of Yekaterinoslav Governorate. The study aims to demonstrate how the personal initiatives of one doctor, implemented during the peaceful development of zemstvo medicine (1898-1914), became the foundation for the effective functioning of the healthcare system under the extreme conditions of World War I. Methods of historical-comparative and source analysis are employed. It is established that the modernization of the infrastructure of the Ivanovo Zemstvo Hospital, the introduction of surgical care, the creation of an infectious diseases department and a centralized water supply system, initiated by V. N. Bragin, enabled the district to quickly expand its network of infirmaries and hospitals after 1914. The doctor's work is viewed as an example of successful institutional adaptation: from local improvements to the formation of a sustainable healthcare model capable of scaling up in a crisis. It is concluded that the legacy of V. N. Bragin is valuable not only for the historiography of medicine, but also for modern management practices in the field of healthcare.

Keywords: *zemstvo medicine, V. N. Bragin, Slavyanoserbsk district, World War I.*

Introduction

Zemstvo is healthcare system of the Russian Empire, formed in the second half of the 19th century, became one of the most progressive social institutions of its time. It not only provided medical care to the rural population but also acted as an agent of modernization, education, and social consolidation in the provinces [1]. This role was especially significant in the southern Russian regions, where socioeconomic backwardness combined with rapid industrial growth and high population mobility.

The Slavyanoserbsk district of the Yekaterinoslav Governorate (present-day Luhansk People's Republic) was a vivid example of such a “transitional” zone. Here, zemstvo medicine developed amidst a shortage of resources, personnel, and infrastructure. It was in this environment that the phenomenon of the physician-reformer emerged — one capable of transforming limitations into opportunities, and local solutions into systemic change.

One such figure was Vasily Nikitovich Bragin. His name, despite his documented contribution to the development of district healthcare, remains little known in modern historiography. Meanwhile, V. N. Bragin's professional career represents a unique case: from an ordinary district physician to the organizer of a model hospital, whose model was awarded two gold medals at the All-Russian Hygiene Exhibition in St. Petersburg in 1913 [2].

The relevance of this study stems not only from the need to restore historical justice but also from the practical value of V. N. Bragin's experience for modern

healthcare management. His ability to anticipate challenges, invest in infrastructure, and build community engagement remains in demand in any crisis.

The purpose and objectives of the study

Objective: a comprehensive analysis of the professional activities of V. N. Bragin as a factor in the formation of a sustainable model of zemstvo medicine in the Slavyanoserbbsk district, capable of effective functioning in wartime conditions.

Tasks:

1. to reconstruct the biographical and professional path of the doctor;
2. to identify the key innovations introduced by V. N. Bragin into the practice of the Ivanovo Zemstvo Hospital;
3. to analyze how the infrastructure prepared in peacetime was used during the First World War;
4. to assess the role of the physician's personality in mobilizing public resources to solve medical problems;
5. to formulate conclusions about the mechanisms of institutional adaptation of medicine in a provincial district.

Materials and methods

The study is based on the principles of historical-comparative and source study analysis. The empirical basis consists of the following: collection documents of the State Archive of Luhansk Oblast (reports of zemstvo councils, meeting journals, estimates); publications of local periodicals from 1898-1917 (Ekaterinoslav Provincial Gazette, Zemsky Vrach, Lugansk Leaflet); memoirs and works of V. N. Bragin himself, in particular his Essay on the History of the Development of Zemstvo Medicine in the Slavyanoserbbsk District (1916); materials from the exposition of the Museum of the History of Medicine of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education Luhansk State Medical University named after St. Luke; scientific literature on the history of zemstvo medicine and medical care during the First World War.

The use of a retrospective method allowed us to trace the evolution of the county's medical infrastructure; a comparative analysis allowed us to compare the peacetime and wartime periods of the system's operation; and a source-based approach allowed us to critically evaluate the reliability and representativeness of the documents used.

Research results

Becoming a Doctor: From Idea to Infrastructure

Vasily Nikitovich Bragin was born on January 1, 1873, in the village of Ivanovka, Slavyanoserbbsk district. His career choice was predetermined by the times: his graduation from the medical faculty of Kharkov University in 1897 coincided with the active implementation of zemstvo reform in the southern provinces. On January 28, 1898, he assumed his duties as a district physician at the Ivanovo zemstvo hospital [3].

Even at an early stage, V. N. Bragin demonstrated not only clinical competence but also systems thinking. He understood that the quality of medical care in rural areas is determined not so much by the skill of an individual physician, but by the state of the infrastructure, logistics, and the public health culture.

The first large-scale project was the reconstruction of the Ivanovo Hospital (1903-1905). Under Bragin's direction, the complex included: a main building with 12 beds; a separate outpatient clinic (the first specialized building of its kind in the district); staff quarters; a utility block with a laundry and kitchen; and a water tower.

Particular attention was paid to sanitary equipment: hot and cold water supply systems were installed in the operating room and dressing room, and a fireplace was used for thermal disinfection of materials — a solution ahead of its time [3].

Surgery as a Breakthrough: Making Care Available on the Ground

In 1903, V. N. Bragin completed specialized training in St. Petersburg and received official permission to perform surgical procedures. This event was of fundamental importance: for the first time, residents of the Slavyanoserbsk district had access to qualified surgical care without having to travel to Yekaterinoslav [3].

This step not only increased the survival rate of patients with acute conditions, but also changed the public perception of zemstvo medicine: it ceased to be associated exclusively with therapy and prevention, becoming a full-fledged clinical service.

Infectious Disease Ward and Water Supply: Response to Epidemiological Challenges

The next strategic decision was the construction of an infectious diseases (“contagious”) ward (1910-1912). The barracks, commissioned on July 15, 1912, met advanced sanitary standards: four isolated wards (with two beds each); separate staff quarters; a disinfection chamber; a ventilation system; and central hot water heating (as opposed to local heating in the other buildings).

The calculated indicators (10.1 m² of floor and 39 m³ of air per bed) exceeded current standards, which minimized the risk of nosocomial spread of infections [3].

At the same time, a centralized water supply system was implemented: in 1912, an oil-powered pumping station was built, supplying water to all buildings. This solution radically improved hygiene and became the basis for the implementation of new protocols for instrument processing and patient care.

Recognition and Education: From Local Success to Social Impact

V. N. Bragin's efforts received high recognition: in 1913, the model of the Ivanovo Hospital was awarded two gold medals at the All-Russian Hygiene Exhibition in St. Petersburg [4]. This achievement was not only a personal award for the doctor but also confirmation that provincial zemstvo medicine was capable of meeting national and European standards.

Alongside infrastructure projects, Bragin actively engaged in educational outreach: lectures for the public, publications in the local press, and training in

sanitation skills. These efforts contributed to the development of basic hygiene practices and, consequently, a reduction in disease rates.

An important contribution to science was his 1916 publication, “An Essay on the History of the Development of Zemstvo Medicine in the Slavyanoserbsk District” — a work based on unique archival materials and remaining a valuable source on the history of medicine in the South of Russia [3].

Tested by War: Infrastructure as the Foundation of Resilience

The outbreak of World War I in August 1914 presented a serious challenge to the healthcare system. The mobilization of doctors, the influx of wounded, and the shortage of medicines — these challenges required immediate solutions. This is where the value of the infrastructure prepared by V. N. Bragin became apparent.

The Ivanovo Hospital, thanks to its specialized facilities, water supply, and heating systems, became a key hub in the extensive network of hospitals. By 1915, 16 zemstvo medical institutions, some reoriented to treating the wounded, were operating in the Slavyanoserbsk district; the zemstvo provided up to 170 beds for military personnel, 16 of which were at the Ivanovo Hospital [5].

Moreover, the experience of organizing an infectious diseases ward allowed us to quickly adapt the facilities for isolating patients with infectious complications from wounds. The water supply system ensured compliance with sanitary protocols even under increased pressure.

V. N. Bragin, while remaining in his post, participated in the coordination of medical care, the training of nurses, and the distribution of resources. His authority and management experience facilitated effective cooperation between the zemstvo, the Red Cross, industrial enterprises, and volunteer organizations.

The region’s industrial giants — the Hartmann Plant and the Donetsk -Yuryev Metallurgical Company — provided beds, medicine, and medical personnel, including prisoners of war [5]. Luhansk’s accession to the All-Russian Union of Cities in 1915 facilitated the supply of medicines at discounted prices.

Thus, the infrastructure created during peacetime became the “framework” upon which the emergency medical system was built during the war. This confirms the thesis that the resilience of healthcare in a crisis is determined not so much by emergency measures as by the quality of preliminary preparation.

Conclusions

V. N. Bragin’s professional work exemplifies a systems-based approach to the development of zemstvo medicine: from clinical practice to infrastructure reforms, from local improvements to the creation of a sustainable model capable of scaling during a crisis.

The key areas of his contribution were: the institutionalization of surgical care at the district hospital level; the formation of a specialized infectious disease service that complied with epidemiological standards; technological modernization

(centralized water supply, sanitation systems); and preventive orientation through educational work.

The infrastructure created under the leadership of V. N. Bragin during peacetime became the foundation for the effective deployment of medical care during the First World War, confirming the thesis on the priority of preventive investment in healthcare.

The physician's personality acted as a catalyst for institutional change: his professional authority, managerial competencies, and ability to cooperate enabled him to mobilize the resources of the zemstvo, business, and society to address complex medical challenges.

V. N. Bragin's legacy is valuable not only for medical historians but also for contemporary practitioners: his experience demonstrates how, in the face of resource constraints, sustainable healthcare systems can be built through strategic planning, innovation, and public engagement.

Thus, V. N. Bragin deserves a place in the pantheon of Russian healthcare organizers. His work is not just a page in local history, but an instructive lesson on how a well-thought-out organizational system fosters highly effective medical care not only in everyday work but also during a military crisis.

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血小板血浆在牙周治疗中的作用理论基础
**THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE ACTION OF PLATELET PLASMA
IN DENTISTRY IN PERIODONTAL TREATMENT**

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Tambov, Russian Federation

所有患者均在托木斯克国立大学德尔扎文牙科系接受检查。排除标准如下：

采用自体血浆每六个月一次进行预防性保守治疗，以延长缓解期并缩短治疗时间，用于治疗轻度慢性广泛性牙周炎。所有患者均在俄罗斯坦波夫市托木斯克国立大学德尔扎文牙科系接受检查。

根据本研究的目标，采用了临床、临床实验室、实验室和统计学研究方法。

自体血浆的治疗效果可归因于其中含有的血小板和生长因子（GF），但血浆的作用也可能基于其他定性成分，例如微量元素、常量元素和维生素，这些成分以最易被组织利用的状态存在。因此，该方法的作者R. R. Akhmerov教授并未排除血浆作用的其他假设（营养、环境等）（表）[1, 3]。

关键词：临床实验室，用于研究牙周疾病口腔卫生状况的实验室和统计方法，富血小板血浆在牙周治疗中的作用原理。

All patients were examined at the Derzhavin Dental Department of Tomsk State University. The following were exclusion criteria:

Preventive conservative treatment of mild chronic generalized periodontitis using autologous plasma once every six months to prolong remission and reduce treatment time. All patients were examined at the G. R. Derzhavin Tomsk State University, Department of Dentistry, Tambov, Russia.

In accordance with the objectives of this research, clinical, clinical laboratory, laboratory, and statistical research methods were used.

The therapeutic effect of autologous plasma is explained by the presence of platelets and growth factors (GF) contained in them, but the effect of blood plasma

can also be based on other qualitative components, for example micro- and macro-elements, vitamins, which are in the most bioavailable state for tissues, therefore the author of the method, Professor R. R. Akhmerov, does not reject other hypotheses of the action of plasma (nutrient, environmental, etc.) (Table) [1,3].

Keywords: *clinical laboratory, laboratory and statistical methods for studying oral hygiene in periodontal diseases, the principles of platelet-rich plasma action in dentistry for periodontal treatment.*

The results are in Table 1.

№	Name of the scale	Meaning
1	The scale «Platelets contain a variety of risk factors and cytokines».	FRs that promote the restoration of damaged tissues.
2	The scale «There are more than 30 RFs in the alpha granules of platelets».	FRs that simultaneously influence the processes of periodontal tissue regeneration.

Currently, the main goal of research into regeneration processes is the need to identify RFs, know the mechanism of their action and the possibilities of their use to improve the regeneration of the wound surface (Table 2) [7, 9, 8, 11].

The results are in Table 2.

1	The most important ones are: the “IGF (insulin-like growth factor)” scale.	FR — promotes differentiation of stem cells, increases bone metabolism and collagen production.
2	The most important ones are: the “PDGF (platelet growth factor)” scale.	FR — stimulates the proliferation and movement of mesenchymal (osteogenic) cells, stimulates angiogenesis.
3	The most important are: the “PDE-GF (platelet-derived endothelial cell growth factor)” scale.	FR — has a stimulating effect on endothelial cells and has an angiogenic effect.
4	The most important are: the scale “VEGF or PDAF (vascular endothelial growth factor): there are 4 types of factor VEGF-A, -B, -C and -D”	They participate in angiogenesis and induce proliferation of vascular endothelial cells.
5	The most important ones are: the “EGF (epidermal growth factor)” scale.	FR — promotes the proliferation of fibro- and osteoblasts, increases the synthesis of fibronectin.
6	The most important are: the TGF- β (Family of Transforming Growth Factor) scale.	GFs are multifunctional factors, since they not only induce differentiation of mesenchymal cells, but also cause a large number of cellular and intercellular responses, including the production of other GFs.

7	The most important are: the scale «(KMB-2, osteogenin or KMB-3, KMB-4,—5,—7,—8 and -9)».	Transforming growth factors include bone morphogenetic proteins, some of which are pronounced osteoinductors, modulating cell proliferation and differentiation of poorly differentiated cells into osteoblasts.
8	The most important ones are: the scale “PLGF-1/-2 (placental growth factors)”.	FR — potentiate the action of VEGF, increase the permeability of the vascular wall.
9	The most important ones are: the «FGF (fibroblastic growth factor)» scale.	FR — causes expression in bone tissue, angiogenesis, ossification, induces the production of TGF in osteoblastic cells Osteonectin «culture shock protein».

Furthermore, it is non-toxic and non-immunoreactive. Obtaining autologous plasma involves separating plasma and platelets from red blood cells using both a density gradient and specialized laboratory filters. The use of autologous platelet plasma today represents one of the few opportunities to trigger and accelerate natural regeneration mechanisms through the growth factors contained in platelets.

TGF production in osteoblast cells. Osteonectin, a “culture shock protein,” accounts for 15% of the organic component of the bone matrix and regulates proliferation and cell interaction with the matrix. Thrombospondin mediates bone cell adhesion [6].

As a result, metabolic processes are restored, microcirculation and metabolism in tissue cells are improved, tissue respiration is normalized, and local immunity is activated [9, 10].

Platelet-rich plasma also inhibits osteoclasts and stimulates osteoblast proliferation, which inhibits further bone loss and promotes its regeneration. Platelet-rich plasma is delivered to tissues via injected autologous plasma and is concentrated by introducing larger quantities of autologous plasma.

This increases fibroblast activity and stimulates their formation. Fibroblasts produce collagen fibers, hyaluronic acid, and elastin, all of which leads to the formation of new connective tissue and capillary growth.

Platelet-rich plasma is harmless to a person’s own tissues and is bioavailable in the biochemical ratio of components that is characteristic of a given organism [1, 4].

The action of platelet-rich autologous plasma can be simplified to the following pathophysiological (pathological, since a pathological condition is “simulated”) process: due to the loss of contact between the platelet and the endothelium upon exiting the bloodstream, it changes shape, stimulating α -granules, which in turn release FR into the wound [1].

S. E. Haynesworth demonstrated that increasing the platelet count to 1 million/ μ l enhances the tissue regeneration phase [10].

Based on these data, it is necessary to obtain not only platelet-rich autologous plasma, but also to achieve an increase in the absolute platelet count in tissues. The advantage of the Plasmolifting™ method is the ability to increase the platelet count in tissues by increasing the volume of injected plasma, activating all regenerative processes simultaneously and acting synergistically on them.

Platelet-rich autologous plasma becomes a simple and safe biological method that accelerates regenerative processes. This property is inherent only to the natural, liquid state of plasma in accordance with the law $m=Vq$, where m is the mass of the absolute number of platelets, V is the volume of plasma, q is the concentration of platelets; in practice, this means the introduction of not 0.2-0.3 ml, but 1-2 teaspoons, which is quite easily accomplished in soft tissues and large joints [1, 4, 5].

The experimental study was conducted at the Department of Dentistry at Tambov State University named after G. R. Derzhavin in 2026.

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儿童关节炎中免疫系统与止血系统相互作用的特征
**FEATURES OF THE INTERACTION OF THE IMMUNE SYSTEM
AND THE HEMOSTASIS SYSTEM IN JUVENILE ARTHRITIS
IN CHILDREN**

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摘要。研究目的：旨在明确不同类型幼年特发性关节炎中免疫系统与止血系统相互作用的特征。材料与方法：回顾性多中心研究，纳入247例患儿的病历资料，并将其分为7组。评估止血系统和免疫系统的相关参数。采用Kruskal-Wallis检验 ($p < 0.05$) 确定统计学意义。采用Spearman秩相关系数进行相关性分析，并根据Cheddock量表进行校正。结论：IL-10与止血参数之间存在显著的中度至强相关性。未检测到IL-4对血小板活性的直接影响。免疫炎症相关的止血系统激活会导致微循环障碍，并加剧疾病进展。

关键词：幼年特发性关节炎，免疫，止血，IL-10，儿童。

Abstract. Objective of the study. To identify features of the interaction between the immune system and the hemostasis system in different forms of juvenile arthritis. Materials and methods. Retrospective multicenter study of the medical records of 247 children divided into 7 groups. Parameters of the hemostasis and immune systems were assessed. Statistical significance was determined using the

Kruskal-Wallis test ($p < 0.05$). Correlation analysis was performed using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient with correction according to the Cheddock scale. Conclusion. Significant correlation interactions of moderate and strong magnitude were revealed between IL-10 and hemostasis parameters. No direct effect of IL-4 on platelet activity was detected. Activation of the hemostasis system associated with immune inflammation leads to disruption of microcirculation and exacerbates disease progression.

Keywords: *juvenile idiopathic arthritis, immunity, hemostasis, IL-10, children.*

Introduction

Juvenile idiopathic arthritis is one of the most common rheumatic diseases in childhood, which in most cases results in disability. According to the 2025 clinical guidelines, the prevalence of juvenile idiopathic arthritis in various countries ranges from 3.8 to 400 cases per 100,000 children [1]. Accordingly, a substantial volume of research is underway to resolve issues related to the pathogenesis, effective treatment, and prevention of complications of both the disease itself and its therapy. Despite the significant number of emerging drugs, including gene-engineered biological therapies (GIBT), remission is not achieved in all children, which primarily may be attributed to an incompletely elucidated pathogenesis of the disease, exhibiting specific features in each form of juvenile arthritis [2]. For example, a sufficient number of studies have confirmed disorders of the hemostasis system in adults with rheumatoid arthritis, indicating the presence of a chronic hypercoagulable state that contributes to an increased risk of thrombotic complications [3]. There is evidence of similarities in hemostasis disorders between rheumatoid arthritis and juvenile arthritis [4, 5, 6]. Research investigating the influence of the immune system on hemostasis has demonstrated that neutralization of IL-10 by monoclonal antibodies in vitro alters lymphocytes' capacity to produce procoagulants, anticoagulants, and fibrinolytic agents into the surrounding environment, as well as modifies IL-10's ability to bind heparin [7, 8]. Regarding juvenile arthritis, there are only limited data on the relationship between immune and hemostasis disorders, as well as on the impact of the patient's coagulation status on disease progression. It is important to specify that hemostasis disorders are most pronounced during high disease activity; therefore, they may not always be clearly detectable at moderate or low activity levels, complicating their diagnosis and suggesting that such disorders may occur more frequently than currently diagnosed [9, 10]. It should be noted that studies using the thrombodynamics test have already been conducted in adults with RA, which represents a critically important aspect in understanding the pathogenesis of the disease itself; however, analogous studies have not been carried out in juvenile idiopathic arthritis (JIA) [11, 12]. Therefore, in pediatric practice, unresolved issues remain concerning the pathogenetic processes of juvenile idiopathic arthritis (JIA).

Objective. To identify the features of the interaction between the immune system and the hemostasis system in different forms of juvenile arthritis.

Materials and methods

We conducted a retrospective multicenter study during which data from the medical records of children and form 112/u were evaluated. The main inclusion criteria were the presence of an established diagnosis and the required set of laboratory data. Thus, the patients (247 individuals) were divided into the following groups: ‘Oligoarthritis’ (83 (33.6%) individuals), ‘Systemic onset juvenile arthritis’ (17 (6.9%) individuals), ‘Seronegative juvenile arthritis’ (48 (19.4%) individuals), ‘Rheumatoid factor (RF) positive juvenile arthritis’ (4 (1.6%) individuals), ‘Spondylitis, spondyloarthritis’ (27 (11.0%) individuals), and ‘Psoriatic arthritis’ (7 (2.8%) individuals). Additionally, a separate group of children (61 (24.7%) individuals) who lacked one of the key inclusion criteria was distinguished. The total number of boys was 105 (42.7%), and girls 141 (57.3%). The mean age was calculated separately for each group. Assessment was performed of hemostasis system parameters (PTT, TT, prothrombin by Quick, INR, fibrinogen, APTT, platelets, bleeding time, blood clotting time according to Sukharev, D-dimer, plasminogen, antithrombin III, protein C, platelet aggregation, platelet adhesion, platelet aggregation with UIA, platelet aggregation with ADP, platelet aggregation with ristocetin) and immune indicators (ACPA, CICs, T-helpers, T-activators, T-suppressors, B-lymphocytes, immunoreactive insulin, IgA, IgM, IgG, phagocytosis, LCB, seromucoid, ASLO, IL-1, IL-6, IL-10, IL-4, TNF), with additional parameters comprising anthropometric measurements, disease duration and age at onset, date of disease onset, as well as clinical and biochemical blood test results. Statistical significance was determined using the Kruskal-Wallis test and considered significant at $p < 0.05$. Correlation analysis was performed using Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient, and the strength of association between the obtained data was evaluated according to Cheddock scale.

Results and Discussion

The oligoarthritis group comprised 83 patients, including 32 (38.6%) boys and 51 (61.4%) girls; the mean age of the children was 8.99 ± 0.43 years, the age at disease onset was 5.36 ± 0.33 years, and the disease duration was 3.73 ± 0.32 years. The majority of children (38 (45.8%) patients) exhibited moderate disease activity, and the most significant etiological factor was bacterial infection (76 (91.6%) patients), which in some cases was concomitant with viral pathology and/or trauma or surgical intervention. In this group, the following correlations were observed: with an increase in ACPA, IL-4 levels increased ($r = -0.68$; $p < 0.01$); An increase in IL-10 concentration was associated with enhanced prothrombin activation ($r = 0.56$; $p < 0.05$) and a decrease in INR values ($r = -0.54$; $p < 0.05$), indicative of aggravated microcirculatory disturbances. Levels of TNF-alpha ($r = 0.68$; $p < 0.01$) and IL-6 ($r = 0.79$; $p < 0.01$) increased with elevated platelet adhesion. Thus, upon stimulation

of the immune system at the peak activity of plasmocytes, a significant amount of ACPA is released, which leads to neutrophil activation and the initiation of Netosis, facilitating microcirculation impairment through platelet activation and fibrinogen synthesis accompanied by increased TNF-alpha and IL-6, thereby enhancing the destruction of cartilage and bone tissue. Simultaneously, IL-4 delivers an inhibitory signal to type 1 T-helper cells, thereby suppressing the activation of type 2 T-helper cells and facilitating the limitation of the inflammatory response and reduction of microcirculatory disturbances. This is likely why the oligoarticular variant manifests with the least severe joint involvement compared to other forms of juvenile arthritis.

The systemic-onset juvenile arthritis group included 17 patients (11 boys [64.7%] and 6 girls [35.3%]) with a mean age of 9.47 ± 0.86 years, mean age at disease onset of 7.06 ± 0.67 years, and disease duration of 2.71 ± 0.45 years. Most of the children we studied exhibited high arthritis activity (11 (64.7%) individuals). As in the previous group, bacterial infection was the predominant factor (6 (35.3%) individuals). Correlational dependencies were as follows: with an increase in ACPA, levels of IL-6 ($r = 0.97$; $p < 0.01$) and TNF-alpha ($r = 0.90$; $p < 0.01$) increased. IL-10 and APTT were inversely correlated ($r = -0.82$; $p < 0.01$), which explains the disruption of microcirculation and pronounced inflammatory processes in juvenile arthritis with systemic onset. We found that protein C levels and TNF-alpha were positively correlated ($r = 0.91$; $p < 0.01$). Interpretation will be withheld as this correlation is likely incidental, given that the sample in this group is not representative, making definitive conclusions difficult and inconsistent with the established pathogenetic mechanisms of autoimmune diseases; similar observations have not been reported in the literature.

Parameters were analyzed in 48 children with seronegative juvenile arthritis, with a mean age of 11.4 ± 0.53 years. The age of disease onset in this group was 8.02 ± 0.55 years, with a disease duration of 3.44 ± 0.42 years. The majority of children with the seronegative variant exhibited a moderate degree of disease activity (20 (41.7%) individuals); the most significant etiological factor was bacterial infection (45 (93.8%) individuals), including cases combined with viral pathology and/or trauma or surgery. A statistically significant correlation was found only for ACPA, with its increase associated with a rise in TNF-alpha levels ($r = 0.54$; $p < 0.05$).

The JIA group with spondylitis/spondyloarthritis included 27 children with a mean age of 14.07 ± 0.41 years, an age at disease onset of 12.48 ± 0.49 years, and a disease duration of 2.01 ± 0.28 years. In contrast to all previous groups, the majority of patients (13 (48.1%)) exhibited minimal arthritis activity; however, disease onset also followed a bacterial infection in most cases (24 (88.9%)). The following correlations were identified: with increasing IL-10, D-dimer levels increased ($r = 0.65$; $p < 0.05$); An increase in platelet adhesion is associated with a decrease in IL-4 synthesis ($r = -0.65$; $p < 0.05$). It is established that IL-10 does not influence

the concentration of D-dimers. However, the presence of D-dimer in blood plasma indicates the formation and degradation of a fibrin clot within the vascular bed and reflects activation of hemostasis and fibrinolysis. The rheumatoid factor (RF)-positive juvenile arthritis group consisted of 4 patients with a mean age of 15.25 ± 0.88 years, age at disease onset of 12.75 ± 0.69 years, and disease duration of 2.75 ± 0.63 years. Half of the subjects exhibited a pronounced degree of disease activity. In all 4 patients, medical histories indicated an association between disease onset and a bacterial infection. The group of children with psoriatic arthritis comprised 7 patients with a mean age of 14.29 ± 1.06 years, age at disease onset of 13.17 ± 1.02 years, and disease duration of 2 ± 0.41 years. As in the previous cohort, minimal disease activity and onset associated with bacterial infection predominated, observed in 4 (57.1%) and 5 (71.4%) patients, respectively. Due to the small sample size in this group, all correlations were not statistically significant.

Thus, the analysis of immune system and hemostasis parameters and their interrelationships with respect to clinical manifestations in children with JIA indicates the significant role of cytokines in regulating immunoinflammatory processes and related alterations in the hemostasis system. In our study, statistically significant correlations of medium and strong strength were observed between IL-10 and hemostasis parameters. In children with oligoarthritis, an inverse correlation was established between the concentration of IL-10 and the international normalized ratio (INR) values. In children with systemic-onset juvenile arthritis, a strong inverse correlation was found between the level of IL-10 and activated partial thromboplastin time, reflecting the influence of the immune system on the stimulation of hemostasis. Furthermore, in the oligoarticular variant, a positive correlation between IL-10 and prothrombin was recorded. In the group of children with spondylitis, a moderate positive correlation was observed between IL-10 and D-dimer levels. Although IL-10 does not directly influence the D-dimer level, it stimulates fibrinolysis [13, 14, 15]. In this same group, IL-4 synthesis decreased in children with increased platelet adhesion. There is no direct effect of IL-4 on platelet activity; however, studies demonstrate a relationship between platelet activation processes and IL-4 synthesis (in patients with ischemic stroke, IL-4 levels increased concurrent with a reduction in platelet aggregation) [16]. Thus, in children with JIA, during the process of immune inflammation, activation of the hemostasis system occurs, resulting in microcirculatory disturbances that exacerbate the degenerative impact on cartilage and bone tissue.

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评估使用保持器维持正畸治疗效果的有效性：系统评价
**EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING RETAINERS
TO MAINTAIN THE RESULTS OF ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT:
A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**

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摘要：本研究旨在通过分析现代文献数据，评估不同类型保持器在稳定正畸治疗效果方面的临床疗效。**材料与方**法：对30篇文献（1992–2025年）进行了系统分析，其中包括俄罗斯和白俄罗斯的研究（n=12）以及来自PubMed、Scopus和Cochrane图书馆数据库的国外文献（n=18）。研究考虑了三种主要的保持器类型：固定式（多排、CAD/CAM、镍钛）、可摘式（Hawley、Essix/VFR）和联合方案。评估的参数包括：Littl不规则指数（LII）、牙弓宽度变化、咬合适宜性以及复发和并发症的发生率。**结果：**CAD/CAM多排钢保持器在维持前牙段稳定性方面表现出最高的疗效（PBB——最有可能成为最佳保持器）[10]。真空成型保持器（VFR）在维持牙列宽度方面与Hawley保持器效果相当，但在稳定下前牙区方面不如不可拆卸保持器[2, 6]。不可拆卸保持器能更快地促进后牙区的咬合适宜，而Hawley保持器则能更好地促进前牙区的咬合形成[5, 8]。仅有25.6%的研

究评估了以患者为中心的疗效；平均随访时间为13.04个月，且脱落率高达10%以上[1, 4, 7]。结论：保持器的选择应根据患者的初始情况进行个体化。CAD/CAM多股保持器是长期稳定最有效的保持器。联合方案（固定保持器+夜间护齿器）能为高危患者提供最大限度的复发保护。临床研究中有必要实施标准化的疗效评估方案并延长随访时间。

关键词：正畸保持器、保持器、固定保持器、可摘式保持器、复发、结果稳定性、Littl 指数。

Abstract. *The purpose of the study is to evaluate the clinical effectiveness of different types of retainers for stabilizing the results of orthodontic treatment based on the analysis of modern literature data. Materials and methods. A systematic analysis of 30 literature sources (1992-2025) was conducted, including Russian and Belarusian studies (n=12) and foreign publications from the PubMed, Scopus, and Cochrane Library databases (n=18). Three main groups of retention devices were considered: fixed (multi-row, CAD/CAM, NiTi), removable (Hawley, Essix/VFR), and combined protocols. The following parameters were evaluated: Littl's Index of Irregularity (LII), changes in the width of the dental arches, occlusal adaptation, and the frequency of recurrences and complications. Results. CAD/CAM multi-row steel retainers demonstrated the highest effectiveness in maintaining the stability of the anterior segment (PBB — the highest probability of being the best) [10]. Vacuum-molded retainers (VFR) are comparable in efficiency to Hawley in maintaining the width of the dentition, but are inferior to non-removable ones in stabilizing the lower frontal region [2, 6]. Non-removable retainers provide faster occlusal adaptation in the posterior segment, while Hawley provides better occlusion formation in the anterior region [5, 8]. Patient-targeted outcomes are evaluated in only 25.6% of studies; the average follow-up duration is 13.04 months, with a high dropout rate exceeding 10% [1, 4, 7]. Conclusions: the choice of retention devices should be individualized based on the patient's initial condition. CAD/CAM multi-strand retainers are the most effective for long-term stabilization. Combined protocols (fixed retainer + night guard) provide maximum protection against relapse in high-risk patients. The implementation of standardized outcome assessment protocols and increased follow-up duration in clinical studies is necessary.*

Keywords: *orthodontic retention, retainers, fixed retainers, removable retainers, relapse, stability of results, Littl index.*

Introduction

The completion of the active phase of orthodontic treatment is invariably followed by the retention period. This stage plays a crucial role in stabilizing the achieved correction of anomalies and deformities of the dentoalveolar system, involving the use of both removable and fixed retainers [3, 6, 14]. In terms of the long-term stability of orthodontic treatment outcomes, retention is considered not

merely as a concluding procedure but as an indispensable element determining the success of the entire therapeutic process [6].

The problem of relapse following orthodontic treatment remains one of the most significant challenges in modern orthodontics. Immediate relapse following debonding of fixed appliances is attributed to multiple factors, including the elastic recoil of periodontal collagen fibers, instability of tooth position after crowding correction, continued jawbone growth, and soft tissue pressure [5,8,15]. Restoration of the periodontal ligament requires 3-4 months, while reorganization of gingival collagen fibers takes 6-12 months, underscoring the critical importance of the retention period [5].

Despite the widely recognized necessity of retention, significant variability persists in international clinical practice regarding the choice of retainers and the duration of their application [1, 4]. Retainers are recommended lifelong, which significantly impacts the patient's social engagement and requires ongoing monitoring [1, 7,16]. The late emergence of complications associated with fixed retainers and declining compliance with removable devices dictate the need for prolonged follow-up [1, 4].

In recent years, a substantial number of randomized controlled trials have been published dedicated to the comparative effectiveness of various types of retainers. However, the systematization of these data with the aim of developing clear clinical recommendations remains a pertinent issue.

The objective of the present study is, based on an analysis of current literary data, to assess the clinical effectiveness of various types of retainers for the stabilization of orthodontic treatment outcomes.

Materials and Methods

A literature search was performed in the databases PubMed, Scopus, Cochrane Library, eLibrary, CyberLeninka, as well as in repositories of scientific publications for the period 1992-2025. The search covered 33 years, with an emphasis on the most recent studies from 2020 to 2025. Keywords: «orthodontic retention», «retainers», «bonded retainers», «Hawley retainers», «vacuum-formed retainers», «Little's irregularity index», «orthodontic retention», «retainers», «fixed retainers», «removable retainers».

Inclusion criteria:

— Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and systematic reviews with meta-analysis.

— Cohort studies with a follow-up duration of at least 6 months.

— Publications containing quantitative data on the effectiveness of retention (Little's index, changes in dental arch width, relapse rates, complications).

Exclusion criteria: descriptions of single clinical cases, studies with a follow-up duration of less than 3 months, and studies lacking comparative analysis.

The final analysis included 30 sources, consisting of 12 domestic and Belarusian studies and 18 international publications. The aggregated data are presented in the comprehensive table (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The analysis allowed the identification of three primary groups of retainers used in contemporary orthodontics and the evaluation of their effectiveness according to key clinical parameters.

1. Comparative Effectiveness of Removable and Fixed Retainers

A systematic review with meta-analysis (2024), encompassing 22 prospective studies involving 1,797 patients, demonstrated that vacuum-formed retainers (VFR) are comparable in effectiveness to Hawley retainers in maintaining dental arch width (intercanine and intermolar distances) and arch length in both jaws ($p > 0.05$) [2]. However, according to Little's Irregularity Index (LII) for the maxilla, VFR showed a statistically significant advantage over Hawley retainers (SMD = -0.42 ; 95% CI: -1.03 to -0.09 ; $p = 0.02$) [2,17].

When comparing vacuum-formed retainers (VFR) with fixed bonded retainers (FBR), no significant differences were observed in most parameters, except for the lower Little's Irregularity Index (LII), where VFR proved less effective (SMD = 1.49 ; 95% CI = 0.26 - 2.7 ; $p = 0.02$) [2,17]. This suggests that for stabilizing the lower anterior segment, the use of fixed retainers is preferable.

2. Assessment of occlusal adaptation

Occlusal adaptation (the establishment of teeth in a position of functional equilibrium) is an important component of the retention phase. Systematic review by Shoukat Ali U. et al. (2023) demonstrated that fixed retainers ensure faster and higher-quality occlusal adaptation in the posterior segment compared to the Hawley retainer [5, 8]. At the same time, the Hawley retainer showed superior occlusal establishment in the anterior segment of the dental arches. Vacuum-formed retainers (Essix) demonstrated a reduction in occlusal contacts during the retention period, which is considered an adverse effect [5, 8].

The meta-analysis did not identify statistically significant differences between fixed and removable retainers regarding the overall measure of occlusal adaptation; however, a high heterogeneity was observed among the included studies ($I^2 > 90\%$) [5,18].

3. Modern CAD/CAM technologies

A network meta-analysis (2025), which included 18 randomized controlled trials, analyzing 15 of them, assessed the effectiveness of 14 different retention protocols [10]. The results indicated that CAD/CAM multistranded steel retainers have the highest probability of being the best (PBB — probability of being the best) for maintaining a low Little's index. These are followed by laboratory-fabricated multistranded steel and rectangular flexible steel retainers [10]. For maintaining

intercanine width, the greatest effectiveness was demonstrated by CAD/CAM multi-stranded steel, CAD/CAM nickel-titanium, and spring-type rigid wire retainers [10,19].

It is important to note that removable retainers showed a low probability of being the most effective in terms of both LII scores and intercanine width stability [10]. Changes in intermolar width were not dependent on the type of retention [10,20].

4. Quality of Clinical Studies and Outcomes

A large-scale review (2025), encompassing 1,526 publications with the inclusion of 129 randomized controlled trials (RCTs), identified significant methodological issues in retention studies [1, 4, 7]. The most frequently used primary outcome was the dental arch status (n=38), whereas the secondary outcome was the alteration in dental arch width (n=30). Patient-centered outcomes were evaluated in only 33 studies (25.6%) [1, 4, 7].

The average follow-up period was 13.04 months, with a moderate dropout rate exceeding 10% observed in 27.9% of the studies [1, 4, 7]. Most participants were adolescents (n=63; 48.84%), and comparisons were primarily made between different types of removable retainers (n=38; 29.5%) [1, 4, 7].

5. Retention protocols and clinical recommendations

In the Belarusian study by Rubnikovich S. P. et al. (2025), it is emphasized that the choice of the optimal retention technique should be based on a comprehensive evaluation of the clinical situation and take into account the complexity of the initial dentoalveolar system anomaly [3, 6]. The obtained data indicate a strong correlation between the severity of the initial orthodontic pathology and the effectiveness and longevity (survival rate) of the retention devices used [6].

Table 1. Comparative Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Various Types of Retainers (Based on Literature Data)

Assessment Parameter	Fixed Retainers (FBR)	Hawley (HR)	Vacuum-Formed Retainers (VFR/Essix)	CAD/CAM Retainers
Little’s Irregularity Index (LII) — Maxilla	No Data	Reference Group	More Effective than HR Retainers (SMD = -0.42; p = 0.02)	Highest RVV
Little’s Irregularity Index (LII) — Mandible	Reference Group	No Data	Less Effective than FBR (SMD = 1.49; p=0.02)	
	Highest RVV			

Assessment Parameter	Fixed Retainers (FBR)	Hawley (HR)	Vacuum-Formed Retainers (VFR/Essix)	CAD/CAM Retainers
Dental arch width (intercanine/intermolar distance)	Comparable to VFR	Comparable to VFR	Comparable to HR and FBR (p>0.05)	CAD/CAM — highest RVV for ICW
Occlusal adaptation (posterior segment)	Faster and better than HR	Less effective than FBR	Reduction of occlusal contacts	Data are limited
Occlusal adaptation (anterior segment)	Less effective than HR	Better than FBR	Data are limited	Data are limited
Relapse frequency	Low when properly fixed	Depends on compliance	Depends on compliance	The lowest
Patient-oriented outcomes	High aesthetic satisfaction	Low aesthetics, high reliability	High aesthetics, compliance-dependent	High aesthetics, high reliability
Complications	Dental plaque accumulation, gingival recessions	Caries, fractures	Caries, deformation, loss	Minimal
Level of evidence	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low to moderate

*Note: PBB — probability of being the best (highest probability of being the best); ICW — intercanine width; LII-Little's Irregularity Index.

Conclusion

The retention phase is a critically important component of orthodontic treatment that determines the long-term stability of the achieved results. The selection of retention appliances should be strictly individualized, considering the severity of the initial pathology, the patient's age, and relapse risk factors [3, 6].

CAD/CAM multistranded steel retainers demonstrate the highest efficacy in maintaining a low Little's Irregularity Index and stability of the intercanine distance. They represent the most promising direction in modern retention orthodontics [10].

Vacuum-formed retainers are an effective alternative to Hawley retainers for preserving dental arch width; however, they are inferior to fixed appliances in stabilizing the lower anterior segment. Their use is appropriate with good patient compliance [2, 6].

Fixed retainers ensure more rapid occlusal adaptation in the posterior segment, whereas Hawley retainers are preferable for occlusal establishment in the anterior

region. These differences should be taken into account when selecting a retention protocol [5, 8].

The quality of current clinical retention research requires enhancement. An increase in follow-up duration, the adoption of standardized outcome evaluation protocols, and broader inclusion of patient-centered parameters are necessary [1, 4, 7].

Combined protocols (fixed retainer + night splint) ensure optimal protection against relapse, particularly in patients at high risk (initial crowding, tooth retention, parafunctional habits). This approach is recommended as the 'gold standard' for complex clinical cases.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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分析及利用神经网络模型制定个性化营养计划的前景
**ANALYSIS AND PROSPECTS OF USING NEURAL NETWORK
MODELS FOR CREATING INDIVIDUAL NUTRITION PLANS**

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摘要：本文分析了将神经网络模型应用于个性化营养规划的潜力和风险，并探讨了当代人工智能系统的技术能力。一项针对74名医学生的社会学研究评估了他们对健康营养的态度、接受基于人工智能的饮食方案的意愿以及对自动化系统的信任程度。研究结果显示，人们对人工智能的应用有着很高的需求（89.3%的受访者认为使用人工智能是可以接受的），同时他们对自主系统的信任度也保持在平均水平（5分制，平均分为3.9分）。主要风险包括：算法透明度不足、语言模型中可能出现的“幻觉”现象、个人数据泄露的风险以及生成缺乏临床背景的平均化推荐。

关键词：人工智能，神经网络模型，卫生，个性化营养，学生

Abstract. *This article presents the results of an analysis of the potential and risks of applying neural network models for personalized nutrition planning. The technological capabilities of contemporary AI systems are examined. A sociological study was conducted among 74 medical students to evaluate their attitudes towards healthy nutrition, their willingness to adopt AI-based diets, and their level of trust in automated systems. A high potential demand has been revealed (89.3% of respondents consider the use of AI acceptable) alongside a sustained average level of trust in autonomous systems (3.9 out of 5). The principal risks have been identified as follows: lack of algorithmic transparency, the 'hallucination' phenomenon in language models, the risk of personal data leakage, and the generation of averaged recommendations lacking clinical context.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, neural network models, hygiene, personalized nutrition, students*

Introduction

The contemporary development of digital technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), exerts a significant influence on the nutrition hygiene of the population. Individual dietary recommendations, traditionally formulated by specialists based on clinical data and observations, are increasingly supplemented by algorithmic solutions capable of analyzing large data sets. Traditional approaches to dietary assessment, formulation of dietary recommendations, and management of nutrition-related diseases face several limitations: high subjectivity of patient self-reports, inability to account for individual metabolic variability, and the labor-intensive nature of analyzing extensive data arrays. Artificial intelligence provides solutions to these issues through machine learning methods, integrative processes, and generative language models. Such systems promise a more precise, convenient, and timely approach to developing individualized dietary strategies, making the assessment of their safety, efficacy, and appropriateness a pertinent issue in nutritional hygiene, particularly clinical (dietary) nutrition.

Research objective: to analyze and assess the potential capabilities and risks of employing artificial intelligence for the formulation of personalized nutrition plans, and, based on survey data, to determine medical students' attitudes toward the integration of neural network technologies into dietology practice.

Materials and Methods of Research. The study comprised two components: an analytical block (literature review) and an empirical block (cross-sectional survey). An analysis was performed of peer-reviewed scientific publications concerning the application of neural network models and machine learning methods in personalized dietetics, the assessment of eating behavior, and nutritional support. Data from systematic reviews and clinical trial outcomes (Precision-Health, FOOD-4ME projects) were examined. To gather opinion data, a survey was conducted with a target sample of 74 students from the 1st to 6th years of the therapeutic and pediatric faculties at Kuban State Medical University. The questionnaire included questions on dietary behavior, attitudes toward AI, and the level of trust in automated systems. The survey was conducted on a voluntary and anonymous basis in a remote format. The primary database was created in MS Excel. Absolute (n) and relative (%) values were calculated. The level of trust was assessed by calculating the arithmetic mean (M) on a 5-point scale. Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistica software package.

Results and Discussion

One of the primary tasks of artificial intelligence (AI) employed in nutrition planning is the collection of data and the incorporation of individual standards and

characteristics of the human organism. The process of developing a personalized nutrition plan involves several consecutive stages: data collection (age, weight, height, activity level, goals), calculation of caloric intake and the ratio of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates, and the consideration of taste preferences along with individual characteristics (allergic history, chronic diseases, genetic features).

According to data from systematic reviews, computer vision and deep learning methods enable the automation of actual food consumption assessment. Correlation coefficients above 0.7 have been achieved for estimating the energy value and macronutrient content of the diet. For micronutrients, such a high level of accuracy has been demonstrated only in a few studies [1]. Therefore, AI-based systems are already capable of assessing the energy value and macronutrient composition of diets.

The development of multi-omics technologies combined with computational biology has led to the creation of personalized nutrition strategies. The accuracy of predicting metabolic responses to dietary interventions exceeds 90% when using multilayer neural networks. Large-scale clinical trials have demonstrated improvements in weight control and glycemic regulation when using AI-optimized recommendations [2-4].

The prediction of postprandial glycemic response deserves particular attention. Modern models that take into account food composition, data from continuous glucose monitoring, the microbiome, anthropometry, and physical activity are capable of predicting the glycemic peak with high accuracy. Published research results have confirmed that this leads to a significant improvement in glycemic control in patients with prediabetes and type 2 diabetes mellitus [5-8].

In the field of nutritional support for patients undergoing treatment in medical institutions, machine learning models demonstrate high accuracy in identifying the risk of malnutrition based on data from electronic medical records. As studies have shown, implementing such systems has reduced the time to the initiation of nutritional support by an average of 40% and lowered the incidence of potential complications [9].

Thus, the analysis of scientific literature and the technical capabilities of neural network models demonstrates their substantial potential in the field of personalized nutrition. However, it is equally evident that the effectiveness and safety of these technologies' implementation depend not only on their algorithmic sophistication but also on end-user perception and the willingness to trust automated recommendations. Therefore, to evaluate the prospects of applying neural network models, it is necessary to examine the opinions, preferences, and degree of trust among potential consumers — particularly medical students, who are simultaneously active users of digital technologies and future clinicians.

To this end, a survey was conducted involving 74 students from a medical university. The gender distribution of the sample was as follows: 78.6% women (n=58) and 21.4% men (n=16).

An analysis of attitudes toward healthy nutrition revealed that the majority of students express interest in this topic: 64.3% (n=47) of respondents show intermittent interest, while 30.4% (n=22) follow and track information in this area daily. This creates a favorable environment for the implementation of new technologies in the field of nutrition.

When evaluating readiness to use AI, it was established that the overwhelming majority of respondents (71.4%, n=53) are willing to adopt personalized AI-based diets, but only as an auxiliary tool. An additional 17.9% (n=13) are ready to use it as the primary source of recommendations for composing their diet. Only 8.9% (n=7) responded that they do not trust such a diet. Thus, a total of 89.3% of respondents (n=66) accept the use of AI for diet planning in one form or another, indicating a high potential demand for such services among the target audience.

Meanwhile, the level of trust in a diet composed exclusively by a neural network (without physician involvement), assessed on a five-point scale, averaged 3.9 points. This value is only slightly above the average, highlighting a key challenge in the integration of AI in dietetics: full trust in autonomous systems among medical students has yet to be established. Meanwhile, attitudes toward the use of neural networks by dietitians as a tool for dietary planning are predominantly positive (52.7%, n=39). This suggests a preferred ‘hybrid intelligence’ model: the physician as the accountable expert, with artificial intelligence serving as an efficient assistant for computations and generating options.

With regard to the specific function — automatic estimation of the caloric content of dishes from photographs — students either express distrust (46.4%, n=34) or trust it but are not prepared to use it as the primary tool (46.4%, n=34). The majority of respondents perceive this function merely as a guideline rather than an exact instrument, favoring manual data input. This corroborates the overall conclusion emphasizing the need for cautious and supplementary application of neural network AI technologies in nutritional hygiene.

Despite impressive progress, serious challenges persist that limit the widespread implementation of AI in routine dietetic practice. Many deep learning algorithms operate as “black boxes” — clinicians often do not understand why the model produced a given prediction, which undermines trust [10]. Generative language models can generate plausible but factually incorrect responses — a phenomenon referred to as “hallucinations.” Models are trained on data that may contain systematic biases [11]. The use of cloud services for processing confidential medical information entails risks of personal data breaches.

Furthermore, neural network models exhibit risks of generating generalized recommendations, possible errors in micronutrient balance, and lack of clinical context, which may result in potential breaches of nutritional safety and adequacy principles. A model trained on data from one population may demonstrate low

accuracy when applied to other populations. Most research is conducted in highly developed countries, whereas the implementation of AI in low- and middle-income countries encounters infrastructural challenges.

Conclusions

Medical students recognize significant potential in neural network models for addressing the issue of unbalanced nutrition. A high level of readiness to utilize personalized AI-based diets was revealed: 89.3% of respondents are open to such utilization, predominantly in a supportive capacity.

Complete trust in autonomous AI has not been established (average score 3.9 out of 5). The key issues remain insufficient algorithm transparency and the risk of ‘hallucinations’ in generative models.

The most promising and hygienically justified model appears to be the ‘hybrid intelligence’ model, in which the neural network serves as an auxiliary tool for routine calculations, while the physician retains responsibility for clinical decisions. Only through such interaction can safe and effective nutrition be ensured, in accordance with hygiene principles.

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门诊患者潜在缺铁症对公共卫生的影响
**IMPACT OF LATENT FORMS OF IRON DEFICIENCY
IN PATIENTS IN OUTPATIENT PRACTICE ON PUBLIC HEALTH**

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引言。铁缺乏及其导致的贫血影响着全球近三分之一的人口。铁缺乏患者的整体健康状况较差，与工作效率降低、认知功能受损、不良妊娠结局以及合并症病情加重有关。隐性或潜在性铁缺乏需要特别关注，因为它们并非总能在初次筛查中被发现。在门诊实践中，由于统计报告通常基于基础疾病，而贫血通常被视为并发症，因此很难估计贫血和潜在性铁缺乏（LID）的真实发生率。因此，铁缺乏现已被视为一项重大的全球性健康问题，未能识别铁缺乏可能会加重潜在的躯体疾病，并导致暂时性甚至永久性残疾。目的：评估门诊患者潜在性铁缺乏对公共卫生的影响。材料与方法：对164例患者的2021年门诊病历进行回顾性分析。纳入标准为全血细胞计数中红细胞计数和血红蛋白降低，以及血清铁蛋白低于30 ng/mL。在选定的队列（ $n = 102$ ）中分为两组：第1组包括有缺铁性贫血（IDA）体征的患者，第2组包括潜在性缺铁（LID）患者。对所有纳入的患者进行性别、年龄、导致缺铁的原因及其与IDA和LID的关联性评估。结果：在选定的队列中，86例患者（52.4%）患有IDA，16例患者（9.7%）患有LID（ $\chi^2 = 22.2$, $p = 0.001$ ）。平均年龄为 47.6 ± 6.27 岁。女性占多数，占样本的93%。男性缺铁的主要原因是痔疮和消化性溃疡。在女性中，最常见的病因是妇科疾病、月经过多和肾脏疾病。结论：在所分析的样本中，几乎每十名缺铁患者中就有一名患有潜在性缺铁（LID），其发生率远低于缺铁性贫血（IDA）。LID患者以女性为主。女性LID和IDA的最常见病因均为妇科疾病（24.2%）。

关键词：缺铁，缺铁性贫血，潜在性缺铁，病因，性别特征，妇科疾病，肾脏疾病，胃肠道疾病。

Abstract.

Introduction. Iron deficiency and the anemia that develops as a consequence affect nearly one in three people worldwide. Poor general well-being in patients with iron deficiency is associated with reduced work productivity, impaired cognitive performance, adverse pregnancy outcomes, and a less favorable course of comorbid diseases. Hidden, or latent, forms of iron deficiency require special attention because they are not always recognized during primary screening. In outpatient practice, it is difficult to estimate the true frequency of anemia and latent iron deficiency (LID), since statistical reporting is usually based on the underlying disease, whereas anemia is commonly treated as a complication. Consequently, iron deficiency is now regarded as a major global healthcare problem, and failure to identify it may aggravate underlying somatic disease and lead to temporary or even persistent disability. **Aim.** To assess the impact of latent iron deficiency in outpatients on public health. **Materials and methods.** A retrospective analysis of outpatient medical records from 2021 was performed for 164 patients. Inclusion criteria were reduced red blood cell count and hemoglobin in the complete blood count, together with serum ferritin below 30 ng/mL. Two groups were formed within the selected cohort ($n = 102$): Group 1 included patients with signs of iron deficiency anemia (IDA), and Group 2 included patients with latent iron deficiency (LID). For all included patients, sex, age, causes contributing to iron deficiency, and their association with IDA and LID were assessed. **Results.** In the selected cohort, 86 patients (52.4%) had IDA and 16 patients (9.7%) had LID ($\chi^2 = 22.2$, $p = 0.001$). The mean age was 47.6 ± 6.27 years. Women predominated and accounted for 93% of the sample. In men, the leading causes of iron deficiency were hemorrhoids and peptic ulcer disease. In women, the most frequent causes were gynecological disorders, heavy menstrual bleeding, and kidney disease. **Conclusion.** LID was identified in almost every tenth patient with iron deficiency and occurred considerably less frequently than IDA in the analyzed sample. Women predominated among patients with LID. The most common causes of both LID and IDA in women were gynecological disorders (24.2%).

Keywords: iron deficiency, iron deficiency anemia, latent iron deficiency, etiology, sex characteristics, gynecological disorders, kidney disease, gastrointestinal disease.

Introduction

The problem of iron deficiency, especially its latent forms, lies in the fact that it is still infrequently recognized at the first outpatient visit.

Iron deficiency is a condition characterized by insufficient intake and absorption of iron, which is required to produce an adequate amount of hemoglobin, the protein that transports oxygen to body tissues [1,2]. According to global estimates, the prevalence of iron deficiency in 2019 was 23,176.2 per 100,000 population (95% CI: 22,943.5-23,418.6), while anemia among persons with disability was recorded in 828 per 100,000 population (95% CI: 550.5-1,200.0) [3]. Kuche et al. reported that anemia affects nearly one in three people worldwide, which makes it a serious public health problem [4].

The most common manifestations of iron deficiency are iron deficiency anemia (IDA) and latent iron deficiency (LID). IDA is the most severe form of iron deficiency and develops when iron levels become too low to support adequate hemoglobin synthesis [5]. Common causes of IDA include insufficient intake of iron-rich foods such as red meat, poultry, seafood, leafy greens, and legumes; increased iron requirements during pregnancy, childhood and adolescence, or intense physical activity; blood loss due to heavy menstrual bleeding, gastrointestinal ulcers, hemorrhoids, or colorectal cancer, as well as postsurgical blood loss; and impaired iron absorption in celiac disease, Crohn's disease, and malignancies [6-8]. As a rule, IDA can be suspected from symptoms and confirmed by a complete blood count during the first visit or at preventive examinations.

LID represents depletion of iron stores while hemoglobin remains within the reference range. International authors often describe LID as iron deficiency without anemia [1]. Thus, despite normal complete blood count parameters, patients may present with symptoms typical of IDA. The absence of clear abnormalities in the complete blood count often delays the diagnosis of LID, and therefore postpones the start of pathogenetically justified treatment [9]. Long-standing latent iron deficiency reduces endurance, increases fatigue, and impairs concentration, thereby lowering work performance and potentially affecting both the economy and the health of the population.

Aim

To assess the impact of latent iron deficiency in outpatients on public health.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective analysis of outpatient medical records for 2021 was performed for 164 patients.

Inclusion criteria were abnormalities in blood test results, specifically reduced red blood cell count and hemoglobin in the complete blood count, together with serum ferritin below 30 ng/mL. Patients with severe somatic pathology and oncological diseases were excluded from the study.

Based on the selection results, two groups were formed within the selected cohort (n = 102): Group 1 included patients with signs of iron deficiency anemia, and Group 2 included patients with latent iron deficiency.

For all patients included in the study, sex, age, causes contributing to iron deficiency, and the association of these factors with the development of IDA and LID were assessed. We also evaluated the frequency of detecting IDA and LID at the first visit and analyzed physician questionnaires regarding the reasons for ordering a complete blood count and serum ferritin measurement.

There is no universally accepted classification of anemia; however, in clinical practice it is convenient to distinguish anemia by severity: severe anemia (Hb < 70 g/L), moderate anemia (Hb 70-100 g/L), and mild anemia (Hb > 100 g/L). For treatment planning, anemia can also be divided into deficiency anemia, anemia of chronic disease, and hematological anemia. In the present study, all identified anemia cases were iron deficiency anemia of mild severity.

Statistical processing was performed using STATISTICA 12.0. Exact Fisher's test and the chi-square test were used to compare the proportions of dichotomous variables. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results

According to the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 102 patients (62.2%) with iron deficiency were identified in the analyzed outpatient cohort.

Within the structure of iron deficiency conditions ($n = 102$), patients with IDA predominated and outnumbered patients with LID by 86 to 16 cases ($\chi^2 = 22.2$, $p = 0.001$) (Figure 1). Notably, in 9 patients with LID (56.2%), mostly women, iron deficiency was not recognized immediately. In these cases, patients visited a physician with characteristic complaints, but since the complete blood count was normal, anemia was not diagnosed at the first visit. Ferritin measurement was performed only during subsequent visits, and the decreased ferritin level ultimately made it possible to establish the diagnosis of LID and prescribe iron-containing therapy.

Figure 1. Distribution of patients by type of detected iron deficiency.

Women with IDA significantly outnumbered men: 84 (98.9%) versus 2 (1.1%), respectively ($\chi^2 = 49.5$, $p = 0.001$). In the LID group, women also predominated: 15 patients (93.8%) versus 1 man (6.2%) ($\chi^2 = 11.1$, $p = 0.001$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of patients with iron deficiency by sex.

The mean age of men with iron deficiency was 40.1 ± 9.3 years, whereas the mean age of women with iron deficiency was 41.1 ± 6.7 years.

The distribution of patients according to the identified etiology of iron deficiency is shown in Figure 3. In men, the causes of iron deficiency were hemorrhoids ($n = 2$) and peptic ulcer disease ($n = 1$). In women, the most common causes were gynecological disorders ($n = 24$; 24.2%), gastrointestinal diseases ($n = 9$; 9.1%), and kidney disease ($n = 15$; 15.2%). In 13 cases (13.1%), women with iron deficiency had a combination of several nosological conditions. In the remaining patients ($n = 23$; 23.2%), the etiology could not be established.

Discussion

In most cases, iron deficiency is the predominant cause of anemia, accounting for more than 60% of all anemia cases [10]. Approximately 60% of total body iron is contained in erythrocyte hemoglobin and about 7% in myoglobin. Therefore, nearly two-thirds of body iron is associated with proteins responsible for oxygen transport or storage. Around 12-13% of total body iron is incorporated into iron-containing enzymes. Iron is thus an essential trace element involved in oxygen delivery and numerous metabolic reactions [11].

Figure 3. Distribution of patients according to the identified etiology of iron deficiency (multiple etiologies were possible in some patients).

Iron deficiency states are a widespread public health problem. According to published data, anemia affects nearly half a billion women worldwide. In Southeast Asia, about 42% of women are affected by IDA; in Africa the prevalence exceeds 50%, and in India it ranges from 50% to 90% [12].

The prevalence of iron deficiency varies by age, sex, diet, socioeconomic status, and the presence of concomitant disease [8,13,14]. Among women of reproductive age in South Asia, the prevalence of anemia was 41%; among pregnant women it reached 48%, and among non-pregnant women 49% in 2019 [15]. In young and middle-aged men, iron deficiency occurs in fewer than 1% of cases, whereas among people over 50 years of age it reaches 2-4% [6].

A population-based study from the United States demonstrated that the prevalence of anemia in women of reproductive age is about 8%, with LID accounting for 52-65% of these cases [16]. In Canada, the prevalence of LID and IDA among socially disadvantaged groups was 25% and 14% in women, and 0.8% and 1.8% in men, respectively [17]. In Russia, the prevalence of LID has been reported to range from 7.9% to 31.0%, and the frequency of iron deficiency differs markedly between women and men [18].

Our study showed that iron deficiency conditions were present in 64.8% of patients in the selected cohort. IDA was markedly more common than LID. In 23.2%

of cases, the etiology of iron deficiency could not be established. In the remaining patients, the main causes of iron loss were hemorrhoids in men and gynecological disorders, heavy menstrual bleeding, and kidney disease in women.

Among all patients with iron deficiency, we identified 9 individuals (5.4%) whose diagnosis was not established immediately. Only during repeated visits, after persistent complaints of weakness, impaired memory, and reduced concentration, together with detection of low serum ferritin, was LID diagnosed. This finding demonstrates the existence of a clinically relevant group of patients with unrecognized iron deficiency and indicates the need for greater vigilance in outpatient care.

At the same time, diagnostic performance at the outpatient stage remains limited, with an overall detection rate of IDA and LID of only 37.1%.

Thus, iron deficiency is more than a nutritional problem. LID, as a concealed form of iron deficiency, may remain masked for a long time by normal complete blood count parameters while contributing to progression of asthenic symptoms. Therefore, identifying groups at risk of LID and developing screening approaches suitable for the primary outpatient visit is an urgent issue for both national and global health systems.

Conclusion

Low diagnostic recognition and poor detection of latent iron deficiency constitute a widespread but often overlooked problem with serious public health implications.

In the analyzed sample, LID was identified in almost every tenth patient with iron deficiency and was observed substantially less frequently than IDA. Women predominated among patients with LID. The most common causes of both LID and IDA in women were gynecological disorders (24.2%).

Clinical guidelines for physicians in therapeutic and surgical outpatient practice should therefore be updated to improve the early detection of IDA and LID. Considering the major risk factors for LID, better awareness of preventive measures against iron deficiency, especially its latent forms, is needed.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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一项关于单束牙刷在老年人和接受支持性牙周治疗且口腔卫生状况较差的患者中的有效性的研究

A STUDY OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SINGLE-TUFT TOOTHBRUSHES IN CONDITIONS OF POOR ORAL HYGIENE IN THE ELDERLY AND THE AGED, UNDERGOING SUPPORTIVE PERIODONTAL THERAPY

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摘要：本文对成人和老年人在家使用单束牙刷进行口腔卫生维护的有效性进行了全面的比较分析。该研究在阿尔泰国立医科大学（ASMU）治疗口腔医学系进行，旨在评估单束牙刷在牙周疾病患者口腔护理方面的益处。研究开始和结束时，使用以下指标对牙周状况进行了全面评估：SPR、SBI 和 Green-Vermillion 指数。结果显示，与对照组相比，使用 Revyline SM1000 单束牙刷的受试者各项指标均有统计学意义上的显著改善（ $p < 0.05$ ）。研究结果强调了使用专用口腔卫生用品的重要性，尤其对于牙周疾病患者而言。

关键词：炎症性牙周疾病，支持性牙周治疗，单束牙刷 Revyline SM1000 Single, SPR, SBI, 格林-朱砂指数，应用效果。

Abstract. This article presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of the effectiveness of single-tuft toothbrushes used by both adults and elderly individuals for maintaining oral hygiene at home. The study was conducted within the Department of Therapeutic Dentistry at Altai State Medical University (ASMU) to evaluate the benefits that single-tuft toothbrushes may provide in oral care for patients with

various diseases of the periodontium. At the beginning and at the end of the study, a comprehensive assessment of the periodontium condition was performed using the following indices: SPR, SBI, Green-Vermillion. In all cases, the use of the Revyline SM1000 Single single-tuft toothbrush demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in indicators compared to the control group, as confirmed by $p < 0.05$. The results of the study highlight the importance of using specialized oral hygiene aids, particularly for individuals suffering from periodontium diseases.

Keyword: *Inflammatory periodontal diseases, supportive periodontal therapy, single-tuft brush Revyline SM1000 Single, SPR, SBI, Green–Vermillion Index, application effectiveness.*

Introduction

Inflammatory periodontal disease is a chronic process affecting the complex of tissues surrounding the tooth and providing its fixation in the bone [1]. Initially, the pathological process affects the gums (gingivitis) and, in more severe cases, the periodontium that retains the teeth in place (periodontitis), with the underlying typical pathological mechanism being inflammation induced by various pathogens [2, 3]. This is the main cause of tooth loss, considered one of the two greatest threats to oral health [4, 5]. Statistics on the prevalence and incidence of SPT vary due to assessment bias, incorrect classification of individual disease cases, as well as the quality of the conducted examination [6]. Treatment of SPT consists of active therapy and supportive periodontal therapy (SPT). The latter is recommended for the prevention and control of periodontium disease recurrence after active treatment. Patient adherence to SPT is considered one of the most important factors influencing the long-term status of periodontium health [1, 4, 6]. The use of a multi-tuft toothbrush enables the completion of the domestic hygiene phase. This instrument is designed for targeted cleaning of hard-to-reach sites, such as the distal surfaces of the last molars, as well as for thorough cleansing of the cervical areas of the teeth and interdental spaces, which cannot always be reached with a conventional toothbrush.

Objective: to conduct a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of using single-tuft toothbrushes in home oral hygiene among adults and elderly patients undergoing SPT.

Materials and Methods

A study to assess SPT was carried out at the Department of Therapeutic Dentistry of the FSBEI HE Astrakhan State Medical University of the Ministry of Health of Russia, within the polyclinic of the FSBEI HE Astrakhan State Medical University ‘Dental Polyclinic,’ enabling clinical evaluation of the benefits of using single-tuft toothbrushes for home oral hygiene in patients with periodontium pathology.

The study involved 100 patients aged from 35 to 74 years, divided into two main groups: experimental and control. Each group was further subdivided into

two subgroups by age: 35-44 years and 65-74 years. This approach allowed for the analysis of the application of single-tuft toothbrushes across different age categories and the identification of possible age-related characteristics in the response to innovative oral hygiene technologies.

Experimental group: patients in this group (25 individuals in each age subgroup) used single-tuft toothbrushes Revyline SM1000 Single in home oral hygiene in addition to the primary hygiene products.

Control group: patients in the control group (also 25 individuals in each age subgroup) continued using the standard, widely recommended toothbrushing protocol based on global dental guidelines, employing only the primary hygiene products (toothpaste and toothbrush).

For the evaluation of SPT effectiveness, the observation period for the patients was 3 months. At the beginning of the study and at its conclusion, a comprehensive assessment of the periodontium tissues was carried out, including the evaluation of periodontal indices using the SPR index in the modification by C. Parm (1960): the gingiva in the region of each tooth was stained with Schiller-Pisarev solution. The presence of inflammation was assessed in three zones of the gingiva: interdental papillae and marginal gingiva (R); attached gingiva — (M); movable mucosa, alveolar gingiva — (A). Scoring: 0 — no inflammation; 1 — inflammation of the interdental papilla (P); 2 — inflammation of the marginal gingiva (M); 3 — inflammation of the alveolar gingiva (A). Criteria for evaluating the obtained result (degree of inflammation): up to 30% — mild; 30-60% — moderate; above 60% — severe.

The degree of gingival inflammation was assessed using the Sulcus Bleeding Index (SBI) (H. R. Mühlemann, C. R. Cowell, 1975). A periodontal probe was used, with its tip inserted into the gingival sulcus to assess bleeding intensity as follows: 0 — absence of bleeding; 1 — bleeding after more than 30 seconds; 2 — bleeding during probing or within 30 seconds; 3 — patient reports spontaneous bleeding when brushing teeth or eating. Interpretation of results: 0-1.5 — absence of inflammation; 1.5-2.5 — mild severity; 2.6-3.5 — moderate severity; > 3.5 — severe severity.

The evaluation of the hygiene index involved a quantitative assessment of the presence of dental plaque and calculus, using the commonly employed Green–Vermillion Oral Hygiene Index, which includes the assessment of plaque on smooth tooth surfaces and dental calculus. Application of the Green–Vermillion Index involved identifying the presence of dental plaque and calculus on the vestibular surfaces of teeth 1.6 and 2.6, the lingual surfaces of 3.6 and 4.6, and the vestibular surfaces of teeth 1.1 and 3.1. The overall oral hygiene score was obtained by summing the individual results. Interpretation of the hygiene level scores is as follows: 0-0.6 — good; 0.7-1.6 — satisfactory; 1.7-2.5 — unsatisfactory; 2.6-3.0 — poor.

In the examination of the adult and elderly population of the Altai Krai, various statistical processing methods were used depending on the type of random

variables and the research objectives. To assess the distribution type of the variables, skewness and kurtosis indicators characterizing the shape of the distribution curve were used. To assess the distribution type of the variables, the Shapiro-Wilk test was used. Normally distributed continuous variables are presented as $M \pm SD$, where M is the sample mean and SD is the standard deviation. In cases of normal distribution, paired Student's t -test was used to compare means. For distributions not following normal distribution, the nonparametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test (for paired samples) was employed. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$, where p represents the probability of a Type I error when testing the null hypothesis. When comparing multiple groups, Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons was applied.

Results

On the day of examination, in the adult population, the mean SPR index was $45.40 \pm 3.43\%$ in the control group and $49.40 \pm 4.23\%$ in the experimental group, corresponding to a moderate degree of gingivitis, where inflammation involves the marginal (free) gingiva. After 3 months of observation in the group using the Revelyne SM1000 single-tuft toothbrush, the index significantly decreased to $14.80 \pm 2.25\%$, corresponding to a mild degree of gingivitis — inflammation affecting only the interdental papillae. In the control group, the reduction in the index was less pronounced, amounting to $33.70 \pm 3.48\%$, which also corresponds to a moderate degree of gingivitis but is significantly higher than the values in the study group ($p < 0.05$). Among the elderly population, the average SPR index in the control group was $55.40 \pm 6.78\%$, while in the experimental group it was $64.80 \pm 5.46\%$. These values also indicate a moderate degree of pathology, underscoring the significance of the SPT problem within this age category. After three months, the SPR index in the experimental group decreased to $29.30 \pm 3.35\%$, corresponding to a mild degree of periodontium damage. In the control group, the SPR index was $45.80 \pm 4.52\%$, which, as in the previous case, indicates a moderate degree of pathology but significantly higher values compared to the experimental group ($p < 0.05$).

In the adult population group, the average SBI index in both groups at baseline did not differ statistically and was 2.80 ± 0.56 in the experimental group and 2.60 ± 0.48 in the control group, corresponding to moderate inflammation. At the conclusion of the three-month observation period, the SBI index in the group using single-tuft toothbrushes significantly decreased to 1.80 ± 0.16 , corresponding to a mild degree of inflammation (gingivitis). In the control group, the reduction in the index was less pronounced — 2.20 ± 0.87 , which is statistically significantly higher than the values observed in the experimental group ($p < 0.05$). Among the elderly population, baseline values were higher, measuring 3.90 ± 0.67 in the experimental group and 4.00 ± 0.73 in the control group, which is interpreted as a severe degree of inflammation. After three months of using single-tuft toothbrushes, the SBI index

decreased to 2.80 ± 0.45 , indicating an improvement in gingival condition and progression to a moderate level of inflammation. In the control group, the reduction was less marked — down to 3.30 ± 0.26 , which remains statistically significantly higher than the experimental group's values ($p < 0.05$).

At the onset of the study, the average Greene-Vermillion index values among the patients were 2.40 ± 0.49 in the control group and 2.50 ± 0.78 in the experimental group. These indicators correspond to an unsatisfactory level of oral hygiene, indicating the necessity to improve oral hygiene methods. In the elderly group, the results were 2.60 ± 0.53 in the control group and 2.80 ± 0.45 in the experimental group, reflecting unsatisfactory and poor levels of hygiene, respectively. After three months of using the Revelyne SM1000 Single single-tuft toothbrush in the experimental group of adults, a significant decrease in the Green-Vermilion index to 0.50 ± 0.76 was observed, indicating a good level of oral hygiene. In the control group, improvement was also observed but was less pronounced — the index decreased to 1.50 ± 0.67 , corresponding to a satisfactory level of hygiene. The statistical significance of these differences was confirmed ($p < 0.05$), indicating the high efficacy of the single-tuft toothbrush. In the elderly group, the index in the experimental group decreased to 1.60 ± 0.48 , which likewise reflects a satisfactory level of hygiene. The control group exhibited a less pronounced improvement with an index of 2.50 ± 0.53 , which still corresponds to an unsatisfactory level. Statistically significant differences were also observed here ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

The obtained data underscore the importance of selecting appropriate items for home oral care. The Revelyne SM1000 single-tuft toothbrush demonstrated its effectiveness, particularly in the group of adults, where indices improved significantly. This phenomenon may be attributed to the design features of the brush, which enable more thorough cleaning of hard-to-reach areas between the teeth and along the gingival margin. For elderly individuals who frequently experience mobility and coordination impairments, the use of such brushes may represent an optimal oral hygiene solution. Although the results in this group were less robust, they still demonstrate a positive trend, which may contribute to improving the quality of life in elderly patients. The use of this toothbrush promotes more thorough oral hygiene, which, in turn, leads to a significant reduction in inflammatory processes of the gums. It is important to note that the regular use of specialized oral care instruments, such as single-tuft toothbrushes, can significantly enhance the condition of the periodontium and prevent the progression of more severe pathology.

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低温下肝脏肥大细胞群形态功能活性的研究
**STUDY OF THE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL ACTIVITY
OF THE LIVER MAST CELL POPULATION IN HYPOTHERMIA**

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摘要: 本文描述了实验动物在经历一次深度浸没式低温后肝脏肥大细胞群的染色和形态特征。

关键词: 肝脏, 低温, 适应, 适应过程, 肝素。

Abstract This article describes the tinctorial and morphometric features of the liver mast cell population in experimental animals after a single episode of profound immersion hypothermia.

Keywords: liver, hypothermia, adaptation, adaptive processes, heparin.

Mast cells (MC) are among the most extensively studied cells of the immune system. They originate from pluripotent CD34+/CD117+ hematopoietic stem cells of the bone marrow [1]. Following migration from the bone marrow, immature MC circulate through the microcirculatory bed until they reach peripheral tissues, where they mature and undergo growth and differentiation [2, 3]. MCs are consistently present in small amounts in the liver, primarily localized within the portal tracts near blood vessels and bile ducts. These cells have a crucial role in liver tissue injury. Following exposure to damaging factors, cholangiocytes actively synthesize stem cell factor (SCF), a potent chemoattractant that induces the migration of MCs into the liver. Notably, after 70% hepatectomy, SCF levels gradually increase and reach their peak at 7 days post-operation [4]. Mast cells (MC) that have migrated to the liver become activated, with their numbers increasing; they degranulate by secreting numerous mediators such as heparin, histamine, tryptase, chymase, TNF, TGF- β 1, TNF- α , IL-33, cytokines, basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF), leukotrienes, and matrix metalloproteinases, which promote regeneration, angiogenesis, and hepatocyte proliferation [5, 6]. Routine hematoxylin and eosin staining provides limited information regarding MC activity and morphology, whereas toluidine blue staining permits only the quantitative evaluation of MC numbers and the extent of their degranulation. Thus, a combined staining method of MCs using alcian blue and safranin O was developed. The advantage of this method lies in its ability to differentiate young and mature MCs based on their heparin content. Specifically, young immature MCs containing weakly sulfated glycosaminoglycans (precursors of heparin) stain blue, whereas mature and active MCs, due to their high heparin content, stain red [7]. Therefore, using this method, it is possible to identify immature MCs that have migrated from the microcirculatory bed. Currently, there is evidence that MCs are important cellular regulators in human liver diseases. MCs significantly increase and remodel liver tissue in primary biliary cholangitis, primary sclerosing cholangitis, bile duct obstruction, hepatitis, alcohol-induced liver injury, steatosis, steatohepatitis, fibrosis and liver cirrhosis, hepatocellular carcinoma and cholangiocarcinoma, liver rejection following transplantation, and liver aging [8]. Heparin, released from MC upon their activation, is capable of eliciting important homeostatic effects that limit the progression of inflammation and facilitate the regeneration of damaged tissue [9]. This mucopolysaccharide, by binding to numerous proteins involved in various stages of the inflammatory cascade, has been shown to exert multiple effects, including the stimulation of fibrinolytic and anticoagulant activities, the inhibition of recruitment of proinflammatory cells to the injury site and neutrophil adhesion to vascular endothelial cells, as well as the promotion of angiogenesis [10, 11]. The involvement of MCs in organ regeneration following exposure to various stress-inducing damaging factors, including hypothermia, is the subject

of active research [12-24]. At the same time, the morphofunctional activity of MCs in liver adaptation and regeneration following cold exposure stress remains insufficiently studied.

The aim of the study was to investigate the morphofunctional activity of MC populations during liver adaptation after hypothermia exposure.

Materials and methods of the study

The experiment was conducted on 30 healthy six-month-old male Wistar rats weighing 255 ± 15 grams, bred in the vivarium of the Federal State Budgetary Scientific Institution 'Federal Research Center Institute of Cytology and Genetics of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences' (Novosibirsk, Russian Federation). Deep immersion hypothermia (DIH) was modeled by placing the animals individually in cages into water at a temperature of 5°C , with ambient air temperature maintained at 7°C . The criterion for achieving deep immersion hypothermia was a rectal temperature of $20\text{-}25^\circ\text{C}$. The exposure duration averaged 40 ± 7 minutes. The animals were randomized into five experimental groups of five rats each: Group 1 — animals were sacrificed immediately after cessation of cooling; Group 2 — after 2 days; Group 3 — after 7 days; Group 4 — after 14 days; and Group 5 — after 30 days. Chloroform was used for anesthesia in all experimental groups. The animals were euthanized by cervical dislocation. The control group comprised 5 intact animals.

For histological examination, liver samples were fixed in 10% neutral formalin and Carnoy's solution for 24 hours. To identify MCs, toluidine blue (BioVitarum, Russia) was used; specimens were stained according to the manufacturer's instructions. The density distribution of MCs was quantified using the Image Tool 3 software in 10 fields of view (field area 0.12 mm^2) at a microscope magnification of $\times 400$. Based on morphological criteria, the percentage of non-degranulated (compact) and degranulated (including those undergoing lysis) MC forms was calculated. To determine the degree of MC maturity, histological sections were sequentially stained with 1% alcian blue solution in 3% acetic acid (pH 3.2) and 0.5% safranin solution in 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.5), and the numbers of immature (alcian-positive), intermediate (containing both blue and red granules), and mature (safranin-positive) MC forms were evaluated. Morphometric studies were performed using a Nikon Eclipse e200 microscope and the MC-LCD 4K imaging system (Russia), along with the VideoTest-Morphology 5.2 morphometric software. The obtained dataset was processed using the Statistica 12.0 statistical package. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results of the Study

MC in the livers of intact rats were localized in the portal tracts adjacent to vessels and bile ducts. They were typically found singly and exhibited a rounded shape. Safranin-positive (safranin +) MC

No MC synthesizing heparin were detected using alcian blue-safranin staining; MC with granules of both blue and red hues (intermediate) constituted $27.4 \pm 8.5\%$, whereas alcian-positive (alcian +) MC accounted for $72.6 \pm 8.5\%$. The average number of MC was 1.2 ± 0.2 per 10 fields of view, with their area measuring $34.0 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{m}^2$. The proportion of MCs with compact granule distribution was $83.2 \pm 0.3\%$, while the degranulating forms accounted for $16.8 \pm 0.5\%$ (Tables 1, 2).

Table 1. Number of mast cells according to their maturity stage.

Duration of experiment	Alcian (+) MCs (%)	Intermediate MCs (%)	Safranin (+) MCs (%)
Intact animals	$72.6 \pm 8.5^*$	-	$27.4 \pm 8.5^*$
Immediately after hypothermia	$43.1 \pm 12.4^*$	$24.8 \pm 9.7^*$	$32.1 \pm 12.4^*$
After 2 days	-	$27.8 \pm 8.7^*$	$72.2 \pm 8.7^*$
After 7 days	$7.9 \pm 3.7^*$	22.6 ± 7.0	69.4 ± 8.7
After 14 days	$10.0 \pm 4.7^*$	$22.2 \pm 8.1^*$	$67.8 \pm 10.5^*$
After 30 days	$32.7 \pm 5.1^*$	$56.3 \pm 5.2^*$	$10.9 \pm 3.8^*$

Note: compiled by the authors based on data obtained during the study; * — data are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2. Morphometric parameters of mast cells depending on the experiment duration.

Duration of experiment	Mast cell parameters			
	Number of MC	Percentage of compact MC forms (%)	Percentage of degranulating MC forms (%)	MC area (μm^2)
Intact animals	$1.2 \pm 0.2^*$	$83.2 \pm 0.3^*$	$16.8 \pm 0.5^*$	$34.0 \pm 0.7^*$
Immediately after hypothermia	$4.0 \pm 0.5^*$	$64.5 \pm 5.1^*$	$35.5 \pm 5.1^*$	$40.2 \pm 3.2^*$
After 2 days	$10.2 \pm 1.4^*$	$54.4 \pm 0.9^*$	$45.6 \pm 0.9^*$	$51.5 \pm 1.9^*$
After 7 days	10.8 ± 0.9	$43.2 \pm 1.9^*$	$56.8 \pm 0.19^*$	$73.3 \pm 3.2^*$
After 14 days	$9.0 \pm 1.4^*$	$66.7 \pm 3.1^*$	33.3 ± 3.1	$57.9 \pm 2.3^*$
After 30 days	$4.5 \pm 0.6^*$	$72.6 \pm 4.6^*$	27.4 ± 4.6	$47.9 \pm 2.8^*$

Note: compiled by the authors based on data obtained during the study; * — data are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Immediately after induced hypothermia (HIH), compared to intact animals, the number of alcian-positive MCs decreased by 1.7 times, intermediate forms of

MCs appeared ($24.8 \pm 9.7\%$), and the number of safranin-positive MCs increased to $32.1 \pm 12.4\%$.

The number of MC increased by 3.3 times, their area increased up to $40.2 \pm 3.2 \mu\text{m}^2$, the number of degranulating forms increased by 2.1 times, while the content of compact forms decreased by 1.3 times (Tables 1 and 2).

On day 2 after induced hypothermia compared to the previous experimental time point, alcian blue-positive MC were not detected, the number of intermediate MC forms increased up to $27.8 \pm 8.7\%$, and the content of safranin-positive MC increased by 2.25 times. The number of MC increased by 2.55 times, their area increased by 1.3 times, the number of degranulating forms increased by 1.3 times, and the content of compact forms decreased by 1.2 times (Tables 1 and 2).

On day 7 after CHI, the proportion of alcian + MCs was $7.9 \pm 3.7\%$, the proportion of intermediate MC forms decreased to $22.6 \pm 7.0\%$, and the proportion of safranin + MCs slightly decreased to $69.4 \pm 8.7\%$. The MC count was 10.8 ± 0.9 ; the area occupied by MCs and the number of degranulating forms increased by factors of 1.4 and 1.25, respectively, while the proportion of compact forms decreased by a factor of 1.3 (Tables 1 and 2).

On day 14 of the experiment, compared to day 7, the proportion of alcian + MCs slightly increased to $10.0 \pm 4.7\%$, the proportion of intermediate MC forms remained nearly unchanged ($22.2 \pm 8.1\%$), and the proportion of safranin + MCs decreased to $67.8 \pm 10.5\%$. The number of MC decreased to 9.0 ± 1.4 , the MC area declined 1.3-fold, the number of degranulating MC forms decreased 1.7-fold, while the content of compact forms increased 1.5-fold (Tables 1 and 2).

On the 30th day of the experiment, compared to the 14th day, the number of alcian-positive MC increased 3.3-fold, the number of intermediate MC forms increased 2.5-fold, and the content of safranin-positive MC decreased 6.2-fold. The number of MC decreased by half to 9.0 ± 1.4 , the area of MC decreased by 1.2 times, the number of degranulating MC forms decreased by 1.2 times, while the proportion of compact forms increased to $72.6 \pm 4.6\%$ (Tables 1 and 2).

Discussion

The results of the conducted study showed that the liver mast cell population in intact rats was represented by a small number of predominantly compact MC forms, with degranulating forms accounting for $16.8 \pm 0.5\%$. The majority of MCs were represented by alcian blue-positive forms ($72.6 \pm 8.5\%$) synthesizing weakly sulfated glycosaminoglycans. This may be related to the low maturation rate of MCs or the insufficient levels of factors stimulating their maturation in rats. Immediately following hypothermia exposure, both the size and number of MCs began to increase sharply, alongside an increase in the proportion of intermediate MC forms, indicating the initiation of heparin synthesis necessary for active liver tissue regeneration after injury. Meanwhile, MC degranulation increased. On the 2nd day of

the experiment (the period of most pronounced damage), the number of safranin-positive MC forms was highest, the number of intermediate forms continued to increase, resident alcian-positive forms were absent, and degranulation intensified. By day 7, active adaptive regenerative compensatory processes were occurring in the liver tissue. At this experimental stage, both the number and area of MCs were at their highest, associated with elevated synthetic activity. Heparin was synthesized by $67.8 \pm 10.5\%$ of MCs, with intermediate forms comprising $22.6 \pm 7.0\%$, and alcian-positive forms constituting only $7.9 \pm 3.7\%$; these MCs likely represent immature forms that migrated into the liver tissue from the bloodstream. After 14 days, the staining properties of MCs changed minimally, indicating the persistence of regenerative compensatory-adaptive processes in the liver tissue. On the 30th day of the experiment, safranin-positive cells accounted for only $10.9 \pm 3.8\%$, while the number of intermediate forms reached its maximum ($56.3 \pm 5.2\%$). It cannot be ruled out that this phenomenon is associated with the reverse transition process of safranin-positive forms of mast cells, through intermediate stages to alcian-positive mast cells, which synthesize weakly sulfated glycosaminoglycans.

Conclusions. Thus, the identified dynamic rearrangements of mast cell populations following a single episode of deep immersion hypothermia represent regenerative and adaptive compensatory processes, with heparin being one of the active participants.

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实验性深浸低温下甲状腺的病理形态学
**PATHOMORPHOLOGY OF THE THYROID GLAND
IN EXPERIMENTAL DEEP IMMERSION HYPOTHERMIA**

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摘要：本文探讨了甲状腺滤泡、滤泡上皮和肥大细胞的形态特征和形态功能变化。

关键词：甲状腺，低温，适应性过程，肥大细胞。

Abstract. *This article examines the morphological features and morphofunctional changes of thyroid gland follicles, follicular epithelium, and mast cells.*

Keywords: *thyroid gland, hypothermia, adaptive processes, mast cells.*

Low temperature is one of the most significant factors disrupting the body's homeostasis [1, 2]. The body responds to cold exposure with complex physiological reactions aimed at maintaining thermal homeostasis. In the past 10 years, several researchers have established important patterns in the body's response and the pathomorphological features of organs and tissues under cold stress [3, 4, 5]. However, many aspects of this issue remain insufficiently studied. This

particularly applies to the pathomorphology of the thyroid gland under cold stress and the mechanisms of hormonal regulation of temperature homeostasis. Endocrine glands play an active role in adaptation to the impact of traumatic environmental factors. The thyroid gland, as a key element of the neuroendocrine system [6, 7, 8], is involved in energy metabolism, thermogenesis, and the development of adaptive responses to extreme environmental factors of varying intensity and duration, manifesting functional and morphological changes in response [9, 10, 11]. Thyroid hormones and the pituitary-thyroid system actively participate in shaping the organism's adaptive response to environmental factors. They are engaged in the stress response from the early stages, playing an important role in the development of the general adaptation syndrome described by H. Selye. At the same time, the hormonal activity of the thyroid gland is largely determined by the nature, characteristics, and intensity of the stimulus. However, the question of the patterns of change in the functional reserves of the thyroid gland depending on the prevailing cold factor remains unresolved. Mast cells (MC) actively participate in the regeneration of organs and tissues following exposure of the organism to various damaging factors, including thermal factors [12]. Thus, following hyperthermia exposure, MCs actively release serotonin, histamine, $TNF\alpha$, $IL1\beta$, and $IL6$, which lead to activation of the microcirculatory bed and proliferation of macrophages; at later stages, MCs secrete VEGF, which activates fibroblasts and promotes collagen synthesis. Serotonin secreted by TC enhances fibroblast survival and migration while reducing apoptosis in cells damaged by the thermal factor [13].

The thyroid gland stroma is exceptionally rich in TC compared to other organs; these cells exhibit high functional activity and produce a broad spectrum of active mediators [14, 15, 16]. Current understanding indicates that TC are essential for the functioning of the thyroid gland. Alongside parafollicular cells, they are capable of maintaining the homeostasis of biogenic amines within the gland. TC mediators can influence the follicular apparatus of the thyroid gland as well as the stromal component both under normal and pathological conditions. Specifically, TC can activate fibroblasts, endothelium, and the vessels of the microcirculatory network, as well as affect the processes of formation, accumulation, activation, and secretion of thyroid hormones in thyrocytes [17]. There are also studies in the literature demonstrating the involvement of TC in the regulation of regenerative processes in the pathology of various organs [18-30]. However, studies of the morphofunctional activity of these cells under hypothermia remain scarce; therefore, the role of TC in response to cold stress warrants further investigation.

Aim of the study

To investigate the pathomorphological changes and activity of mast cells in the thyroid gland during a single episode of deep immersion hypothermia.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted on 20 sexually mature male Wistar rats weighing 200-240 g, obtained from the vivarium of the Federal State Budgetary Scientific Institution 'Federal Research Center Institute of Cytology and Genetics of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences' (Novosibirsk, Russian Federation). The animals were divided into two groups: Group 1 — control (n = 10), rats in this group were maintained in a thermoneutral zone; Group 2 — experimental, in which animals were subjected to deep immersion hypothermia (60 minutes at -20°C) (n = 10). Thyroid glands designated for pathomorphological examination were fixed in 10% buffered formalin solution (pH 7.2) for 24 hours. Histological sections 5-7 μm thick were prepared using a semi-automatic rotary microtome Accu-Cut SRM (Sakura, Japan) and stained with hematoxylin and eosin. Histochemical staining for neutral glycosaminoglycans was performed using Schiff reagent according to McManus, with control sections treated with amylase. Morphological parameters of the follicles and follicular epithelial cells were analyzed. For each animal, 20-30 follicular epithelial cells were studied at $400\times$ magnification across 3-5 fields of view. The density distribution of TC was assessed on stained specimens using the BioVitrum kit (St. Petersburg) at $400\times$ magnification. Counting was conducted in 10 random fields of view (field area — 0.12 mm^2). The functional activity of TC (degree of degranulation) was assessed as the ratio of the number of degranulated cells to the total number of cells examined, expressed as a percentage. Digital microphotographs of micro-preparations were obtained using a Nikon Eclipse E200 microscope (Japan) and an MC-LCD 4K imaging system (Russia). Morphometric analysis was carried out using the morphometric software VideoTest — Morphology 5.2. Statistical processing of the obtained results was performed using Microsoft Excel and the Statistica 10.0 statistical package. Experimental data were presented as mean values with indication of the standard error of the mean ($M\pm m$). Differences were considered statistically significant at $p<0.05$.

Results of the study and their discussion

The results of the conducted study showed that in the control group (intact animals), the follicle shape was oval or round. The average area of the follicles was $1393.6\pm 146.2 \mu\text{m}^2$. The colloid in the follicles had a homogeneous structure and appeared eosinophilic, while supraepithelial resorption vacuoles were small and infrequently observed. The follicular epithelial cells within the follicles were cuboidal, less frequently cylindrical, and arranged in a single layer. The nuclei of the follicular epithelium were round with coarse granular chromatin. The height of the thyroid follicular epithelium was $7.0\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$; the nuclear area of the follicular epithelium was $18.6\pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}^2$; and the cytoplasmic area of the follicular epithelium was $57.5\pm 3.2 \mu\text{m}^2$ (table).

Table. Morphometric parameters of the thyroid gland in the study groups (M±m).

Parameters	Intact animals	Hypothermia	P
Epithelial height (µm)	7.0±0.1	5.2±0.1	p = 0.0000001
Nuclear area (µm ²)	18.6±0.5	13.6±0.9	p = 0.00001
Cytoplasmic area (µm ²)	57.5±3.2	45.5±3.2	p = 0.01
Follicle area (µm ²)	1393.6±146.2	621.4±102.2	p = 0.0006
Number of TC	10.1±0.6	16.0±2.8	p = 0.03
Number of compact TC (%)	83.8±2.0	52.3±5.6	p = 0.00002
Number of degranulating TC (%)	16.2±2.0%	47.7±5.6	p = 0.00002

Note: compiled by the authors based on the data obtained during the study.

Using toluidine blue staining, TC were detected in the thyroid stroma, both perivascularly and interfollicularly. They were small in size and predominantly round or elongated in shape. The average number of TC was 10.1±0.6 per field of view. The number of TC containing compactly arranged granules was 83.8±2.0%, while degranulating forms accounted for 16.2±2.0% (table).

After a single deep immersion hypothermia procedure, compared to control, there was a 2.2-fold decrease in follicle area (p = 0.0006) (Fig. 1). The basal membrane of the follicles appeared thickened and delaminated, with occasional ruptures observed. The colloid in the follicles became sharply PAS-positive, acquired a basophilic tint, and appeared finely reticulated. The cytoplasm of the thyrocytes was also intensely stained in a pinkish-crimson color. Marginal vacuolization was noted in the vast majority of follicles. Desquamated follicular cells were often seen in the follicular lumens, forming clusters of 4-6 cells. Alongside this, pronounced dystrophic changes in thyrocytes were observed, manifested by vacuolar dystrophy and cellular swelling. Dystrophic changes in the form of intranuclear vacuoles were also observed in the trabeculae. Large resorptive vacuoles were also clearly visible above the epithelium. The follicular epithelial cells within the follicles exhibited a flattened shape; the height of the follicular epithelium was reduced by 1.35-fold compared to intact animals (p = 0.0000001), the cytoplasmic area was 1.3 times smaller (p = 0.01), and the nuclear area decreased by 1.4-fold (p = 0.00001) (table).

The average number of TC during hypothermia increased by 1.6 times (p = 0.03). TC were predominantly small in size, elongated in shape, and primarily located around markedly dilated capillaries. The number of cells with compact granule arrangement

decreased by 1.6 times ($p = 0.00002$), while degranulation phenomena increased; the number of degranulating TC forms rose 1.6 times ($p = 0.00002$) (table).

Conclusion

The results of the present study demonstrated that a single episode of deep immersion hypothermia had a significant impact on the thyroid gland tissue of experimental animals. Meanwhile, changes reflecting a decline in the gland's function became prominent. Morphometric parameters of the follicles and follicular epithelium significantly decreased: follicle area was reduced 2.2-fold, and the height of the follicular epithelium by 1.35-fold, indicating a high degree of functional stress on the gland. Therefore, measuring follicle area and performing karyometry of the follicular epithelium represent highly precise methods for assessing the effects of rapidly developing pathological processes, such as hypothermia.

It is known that the regulation of body temperature homeostasis and adaptation to cold stress are important functions of the thyroid gland. This study observed adaptive responses in the thyroid gland tissue aimed at enhancing hormone synthesis. Specifically, this was manifested by an increased number of TC and their active degranulation. As is well established, TC regulate thyroid gland function and serve as sources of histamine, serotonin, catecholamines, and other active mediators. These substances are capable of regulating the functional state of the thyroid gland microcirculatory network, as well as stimulating endocytosis of the colloid by follicular cells and secretion of thyroid hormones into the bloodstream. Thus, it can be concluded that TC play an important role in restoring gland function and normalizing hormone synthesis after exposure to cold stress.

The pathomorphological changes identified in this study, on the one hand, indicate damage to the thyroid gland tissue following a single episode of deep immersion hypothermia, and on the other hand, reflect processes within the gland tissue aimed at adaptation and normalization of its hormone-synthetic and secretory activity.

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根管治疗中的多模式抗应激支持
MULTIMODAL ANTI-STRESS SUPPORT FOR ENDODONTIC INTERVENTIONS

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摘要。广义上的适应是指生物体通过进化对外部环境的调整，它涵盖了形态生理和行为两个方面。加拿大科学家汉斯·塞利对生物体暴露于外部因素的一般性非特异性适应反应进行了最全面的描述。自主神经系统交感神经分支的激活和儿茶酚胺的过度产生被认为是应激反应最重要的机制之一。脂质过氧化在应激状态下被激活。所有针对复杂龋齿病变的根管治疗都是侵入性操作。其可预见的后果是引发伤害性、神经自主和心理情绪反应。多模式镇痛和预防性镇痛的现代理念已在介入性普通躯体医学的各个领域专家中得到广泛认可，代表了一种有前景的方法，可以应对门诊牙科中类似的挑战。

关键词：适应，多模式镇痛，预防性镇痛

Abstract. *Adaptation, in a broad sense, refers to the organism's adjustment to external conditions developed through evolution and encompasses both morpho-physiological and behavioral components. The most comprehensive description of*

the general non-specific adaptive response of the organism to exposure to external factors was provided by the Canadian scientist Hans Selye. Activation of the sympathetic division of the autonomic nervous system and excessive production of catecholamines are considered among the most important mechanisms of the stress response. Lipid peroxidation is activated during stress. All endodontic interventions in complicated forms of carious lesions are invasive procedures. A predictable consequence of this is the initiation of nociceptive, neurovegetative, and psycho-emotional responses. Contemporary concepts of multimodal and preventive analgesia, which have received widespread recognition among specialists in various domains of interventional general somatic medicine, represent a promising approach to addressing analogous challenges in outpatient dentistry.

Keywords: *adaptation, multimodal analgesia, preventive analgesia*

The capacity to adapt to continuously changing external environmental conditions is one of the fundamental characteristics of biological systems. Adaptation, in a broad sense, refers to the organism's adjustment to external conditions developed through evolution and encompasses both morphophysiological and behavioral components. Adaptation to the influence of external factors is essential not only for the development but also for the survival of any organism. Adaptation is also defined as the ability of any system to acquire new information to bring its behavior and structure closer to optimal conditions. Systems are considered adaptive if they respond to changes in the external or internal environment that reduce their functional efficiency in a manner that enhances this efficiency. The concept of adaptation encompasses changes that lead a living system to reinforce its anti-entropic processes, i. e., self-repair, stabilization, and biological progression. Adaptation is permanent and intrinsic to the organic world at all stages of its development. Research on this issue indicates that the general adaptive responses of the organism are nonspecific, with a fundamental role in adaptation played by the interconnected functioning of the central nervous and endocrine systems [7].

Of paramount interest to clinical anesthesiology and resuscitation is the so-called *physiological adaptation* — a combination of physiological reactions that form the basis of the organism's adjustment to changing environmental conditions and aim to maintain the relative constancy of its internal milieu (homeostasis). The most comprehensive description of the general non-specific adaptive response of the organism to exposure to external factors was provided by the Canadian scientist Hans Selye. It has been established that in response to stimuli differing in nature but intense in strength, approximately the same complex of stereotyped changes develops in the organism. This biological phenomenon has been designated as the '*adaptation syndrome*' or '*stress response*' [2, 5].

Adaptation syndrome comprises three consecutive stages: the alarm stage (mobilization of the organism's available compensatory neuroendocrine reserves occurs); the stage of resistance and the stage of exhaustion (depletion of the organism's compensatory neuroendocrine reserves occurs). The stage of exhaustion is observed in the following situations (or their combinations): exposure to a stimulus exceeding the threshold intensity; prolonged exposure to a stimulus of moderate intensity; an initial 'functional weakness' of the body's adaptive mechanisms. In all these situations (exhaustion stage), the adaptation syndrome acquires a pathogenic character, i.e., the state of eustress (adaptive level) transitions into *distress* (maladaptive level). The disturbances occurring in the latter case were described by Hans Selye as "adaptation failure" [4].

The first stage of stress (the "alarm stage") is characterized by activation of the sympathoadrenal system, suppression of thymic activity, activation of the lymphatic system, and stimulation of ACTH secretion by the pituitary gland, which leads to increased production of glucocorticoid hormones by the adrenal cortex. At the same time, secretion of mineralocorticoids, as well as the activity of the thyroid and gonadal glands, is suppressed. The second stage of stress ('stage of resistance') is characterized by a partial normalization of the activity of the endocrine glands and the thymic-lymphatic system. Occasionally, there is hyperactivation of the glands that were suppressed during the first stage. The biological significance of the resistance phenomenon apparently consists in an adaptive increase in the organism's resilience to the continued influence of stress factors. The third stage of stress ('stage of exhaustion'), as noted above, develops when the stimulus is either very strong or repetitive. Simultaneously, the organism's protective systems are suppressed. This stage exhibits diverse clinical manifestations [1].

Activation of the sympathetic division of the autonomic nervous system and excessive production of catecholamines are considered among the most important mechanisms of the stress response. Under the influence of catecholamines, readily accessible energy sources are rapidly formed. Catecholamines act via the liver phosphorylase system, which activates glycogenolysis and promotes the release of glucose into the bloodstream. The most pronounced initial biochemical changes in the adrenal cortex lead to an increase in plasma corticosteroid levels within minutes after exposure to the stimulus. Concurrently, the content of ascorbic acid in the adrenal glands decreases. Several hours after severe or prolonged stress, the levels of cholesterol and its esters decrease [2].

Glucocorticoids stimulate the mobilization and catabolism of proteins, as well as the synthesis of carbohydrates from non-nitrogenous products of deaminated amino acids, leading to a negative nitrogen balance. Free fatty acids, formed from triglycerides under the influence of glucagon, also serve as an energy source. The mobilization of energy resources is accompanied by their redistribution. Stress

induces activation of lipid peroxidation (LPO). It has been established that uncontrolled amplification of LPO leads to rapid toxic effects on cell membranes, resulting in a reduction of their barrier function. This underlies severe disruptions of vital cellular functions and cell necrosis. This mechanism occurs, for example, during hypoxia, ischemia, and exposure to chemical agents [5].

In addition to stress, there are other, less ‘aggressive’ types of adaptive responses. In the 1920s, G. Selye drew attention to the fact that the onset of clinical manifestations of the vast majority of infectious diseases is practically identical (febrile response, general weakness). This well-known fact demonstrates a distinctive property — the universality or nonspecificity of the organism’s response to injury. This concept was refined in the theory of *nonspecific adaptive reactions of the organism* (NARO) by domestic scientists L. Kh. Garkavi and E. B. Kvakina (1990). Experimental studies conducted by these authors established that, depending on the intensity (dose) of the stimulus, three types of adaptive responses may develop in the organism: to weak stimuli — the “training reaction”; to stimuli of moderate intensity — the “activation reaction”; and to strong, extreme stimuli — the “stress reactions.” In contrast to stress, training and activation reactions occur at the level of adaptation and thus represent variants of the physiological norm. As a result, the concept of ‘stress norm’ was introduced, understood as alterations in homeostasis [3].

A comprehensive analysis of the data from this current theoretical review highlights the existence of an issue concerning the provision of antinociceptive support during endodontic procedures for complicated forms of carious lesions. This issue can be characterized by the following theses. Acute periodontitis is a typical ‘model’ disease within the group of complicated carious lesion forms, necessitating urgent correction, typically in the form of endodontic intervention. All endodontic interventions performed for complicated forms of carious lesions are invasive: a mechanical traumatic effect is exerted on the complex of periapical tissues, pulp tissues, and periodontium, which have rich innervation. A predictable consequence of this is the initiation of nociceptive, neurovegetative, and psychoemotional responses [1].

This is practically confirmed by the fact that the absolute number of patients operated on for complicated forms of carious lesions exhibit pronounced postoperative pain manifestations and associated emotional discomfort during the early postoperative period. The antinociceptive technique employed solely through local anesthesia in this case does not completely address the issue: local anesthetics, by inducing reversible blockade of nociceptors, do not influence the factors underlying their sensitization (primarily the prostaglandin cascade molecules released during tissue injury in the operative field), rendering postoperative pain syndrome virtually inevitable [6].

Thus, modern concepts of multimodal and preventive analgesia, which have gained absolute recognition among specialists in various fields of interventional general somatic medicine, represent a promising direction for solving analogous

problems in outpatient dentistry. However, despite the rationale of such an approach, its implementation in a format adapted for endodontic interventions remains practically undeveloped.

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布鲁氏菌病的分类结构和来源特征：以贾拉拉巴德地区查特卡尔县私人畜牧养殖中急性型布鲁氏菌病的优势地位和小型反刍动物的作用为分析

FEATURES OF THE NOSOLOGICAL STRUCTURE AND SOURCES OF BRUCELLOSIS: ANALYSIS OF THE PREDOMINANCE OF THE ACUTE FORM AND THE ROLE OF SMALL RUMINANTS IN THE CONTEXT OF PRIVATE LIVESTOCK FARMING IN THE CHATKAL DISTRICT OF JALAL-ABAD REGION

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摘要：本研究对2020–2024年贾拉拉巴德地区查特卡尔县的布鲁氏菌病发病率进行了回顾性流行病学分析。该地区被确定为高流行区，其发病率显著高于区域平均水平。儿童（0–14岁）人群的发病率极高，是区域平均水平的5–11倍，预计2024年将急剧上升（每10万人87.0例）。明显的季节性（高峰期在5月至8月）以及急性病例的绝对优势（该地区100%的病例）表明该感染正在活跃传播。主要感染源是小型反刍动物（53.6%），而主要的传播途径是私人农场的职业接触和家庭接触。研究发现，有相当一部分病例（26.8%）的感染源不明，且由于缺乏当地实验室，细菌学诊断面临严峻挑战。所得数据凸显了制定和实施全面、有针对性的兽医卫生和防控措施迫切需要。

关键词：布鲁氏菌病，高流行区，查特卡尔县，贾拉拉巴德地区，儿童发病率，人畜共患病源，小型反刍动物，急性型，流行病学监测，实验室诊断。

Abstract. *A retrospective epidemiological analysis of brucellosis incidence in the Chatkal District of the Jalal-Abad Region for 2020-2024 was conducted. The district was identified as a hyperendemic area, where incidence rates significantly exceed the regional average. A critically high incidence among the pediatric population (0-14 years) was observed, exceeding regional indicators by 5-11 times, with a sharp increase in 2024 (87.0 cases per 100,000 population). Pronounced seasonality (peak in May–August) and the absolute predominance of the acute form (100% of cases in the district) indicate active transmission of the infection. The primary source of infection is small ruminants (53.6%), while the leading transmission mechanism is occupational and household contact in private farms. A high proportion of cases with unidentified sources (26.8%) was revealed, along with critical challenges in bacteriological diagnostics due to the absence of a local laboratory. The obtained data highlight the urgent need for the development and implementation of comprehensive, targeted veterinary-sanitary and anti-epidemic measures.*

Keywords: *Brucellosis, hyperendemic area, Chatkal District, Jalal-Abad Region, pediatric incidence, zoonotic sources, small ruminants, acute form, epidemiological surveillance, laboratory diagnostics.*

Objective of the Study

The aim of this study was to conduct a comprehensive retrospective epidemiological analysis of brucellosis incidence among the population of the Chatkal District of the Jalal-Abad Region for the period 2020-2024, in order to identify specific features of the epidemic process, determinants of high risk, and to substantiate the need for the development of targeted, enhanced anti-epidemic and veterinary-sanitary measures.

Materials and Methods

This study is based on data obtained from district and city Centers for Disease Prevention and State Sanitary and Epidemiological Surveillance. The analysis utilized reporting Form No. 1 (monthly and annual) “On Infectious and Parasitic Diseases” submitted by district and city Centers of State Sanitary and Epidemiological Surveillance to the Regional Center.

Analytical research, statistical processing, and mathematical analysis were carried out using a personal computer with Microsoft Excel 2002 and its Analysis ToolPak for Windows XP.

Introduction

Brucellosis is a zoonotic infection that poses a significant threat to human health and the economy of livestock-breeding regions. The disease is caused by bacteria of the genus *Brucella*, which are transmitted to humans primarily through contact with infected animals or their products, as well as through occupational and household exposure in farming settings [1, 3, 10].

Globally, brucellosis remains a relevant public health problem in countries with both developed and developing livestock sectors. In the Russian Federation, in epidemiologically unfavorable regions such as the Astrakhan Region and the North Caucasus, persistent outbreaks among the rural population are reported [10, 11]. A similar situation is observed in Central Asian countries, including the Kyrgyz Republic, where disease foci are recorded in mountainous and agricultural areas, particularly in the Jalal-Abad Region [1, 3, 5, 8].

Of particular epidemiological concern is the high incidence among the pediatric population (0-14 years), who are involved in animal care and agricultural activities within household farms [1, 5]. This indicates active circulation of the pathogen and insufficient effectiveness of existing preventive measures [1, 5, 7].

Thus, in Kyrgyzstan, especially in the Jalal-Abad Region, the epidemiological situation of brucellosis requires continuous monitoring, analysis of risk factors, and the implementation of comprehensive anti-epidemic and veterinary-sanitary measures in endemic areas [1, 3, 5].

Results and Discussion

The retrospective epidemiological analysis conducted over a five-year period (2020-2024) established the hyperendemic status of the Chatkal District of the Jalal-Abad Region for brucellosis [2,3,5]. The observed incidence rate is critically high and consistently exceeds the regional average throughout the entire study period.

In the incidence dynamics, the peak value in the Chatkal District was recorded in 2021, reaching 156.6 cases per 100,000 population. Over the subsequent two years, a fluctuating decline was observed: 148.7 cases in 2022 and 130.1 cases in 2023, the latter representing the lowest level within the five-year period (excluding 2020, when the rate was 128.4) [1,5]. By 2024, a reversal of the trend was noted, with an increase to 143.6 cases per 100,000 population [6] (Figure 1).

At the regional level (Jalal-Abad Region as a whole), incidence rates remain significantly lower, indicating a comparatively more favorable epidemiological situation than in the Chatkal District [2,3,5]. The regional trend demonstrated a moderate increase at the beginning of the period — from 18.7 cases per 100,000 population in 2020 to 25.2 cases in 2021—followed by stabilization and slight stagnation, with rates ranging between 23.5 and 24.2 cases per 100,000 population during 2022-2024 [3,5].

Thus, the Chatkal District represents a key epidemic focus of brucellosis, necessitating the urgent development and implementation of targeted, intensified anti-epidemic and veterinary-sanitary measures to control the spread of infection [2,4,6].

The high incidence of brucellosis among the pediatric population (age group 0-14 years) in the Chatkal District is of particular epidemiological concern. Incidence rates in this group exceed the regional average by 5-11 times, representing a critical indicator of active pathogen circulation and the insufficient effectiveness of existing preventive measures [1,3,5].

Figure 1. Overall incidence of brucellosis among the population of the Chatkal District, Jalal-Abad Region, 2020-2024 (rate per 100,000 population).

In terms of incidence dynamics in the Chatkal District, the highest rate among children was recorded in 2021, reaching 104.7 cases per 100,000 population [1,5]. During 2022-2023, a marked decline was observed, with rates decreasing to 51.9 and 42.1 cases per 100,000 population, respectively [3]. However, in 2024, a two-fold sharp increase occurred, with the rate rising to 87.0 cases per 100,000 population, highlighting the urgent need to assess underlying causes and strengthen anti-epidemic measures [6] (Figure 2).

The regional dynamics of pediatric incidence (Jalal-Abad Region as a whole) demonstrated a wave-like pattern. At the beginning of the period (2020), the lowest rate was recorded at 7.8 cases per 100,000 children [3,5]. By 2022, a significant increase to 24.2 cases was observed, followed by a sharp decrease in 2023 (2.8-fold) to 8.5 cases, and a slight increase in 2024 (1.5-fold) to 12.9 cases per 100,000 population [3,5].

Thus, the Chatkal District represents a hyperendemic zone for brucellosis. Persistently high incidence rates among children necessitate the urgent development and implementation of comprehensive, targeted anti-epidemic and veterinary-sanitary measures, with priority given to specific risk factors affecting the pediatric population [4,6].

The initial phase of the epidemic process in the Chatkal District began in January, with an incidence rate of 10.1 cases per 100,000 population. In February, the rate decreased to 6.7 cases per 100,000, but in March it returned to the January level of 10.1. A further decline to 6.7 cases was observed in April. In May, the incidence of brucellosis increased sharply by 2.3 times, reaching 23.3 cases per 100,000 population.

Figure 2. Incidence of brucellosis among children under 14 years of age in the Chatkal District, Jalal-Abad Region, 2020-2024 (rate per 100,000 population).

The critical period occurred in July, when the peak incidence rate of 30.0 cases per 100,000 population was recorded. A consistently high level persisted in August, with 23.3 cases per 100,000. From September to October, the rate declined to 6.7 cases per 100,000, no cases were reported in November, and in December, 3.3 cases per 100,000 population were recorded (Table 1).

The seasonal pattern of the disease is clearly pronounced: the spring–summer period (May–August) represents the highest epidemiological risk. This is associated with increased human interaction with agricultural animals and is supported by a parallel rise in brucellosis incidence among livestock [7].

Table 1. Monthly incidence of brucellosis among the population of the Chatkal District, Jalal-Abad Region, in 2024 (rate per 100,000 population)

Months	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Total
Absolute number of cases	3	2	3	2	7	3	9	7	2	2	-	1	41
Incidence rate (per 100,000)	10.1	6.7	10.1	6.7	23.3	10.1	30.0	23.3	6.7	6.7	-	3.3	143.6

In the Chatkal District, absolute uniformity of the nosological structure was observed: 100% of all brucellosis cases were represented by the acute form of the disease. This indicates either the predominant detection of patients at the early stages of the infectious process and/or an intensive transmission of the pathogen during the current epidemic season.

At the same time, the overall structure of morbidity in the Jalal-Abad Region demonstrated a certain degree of heterogeneity, with the dominance of the acute form (92% of cases) and the presence of 8% of cases classified as chronic

brucellosis. Importantly, in 2024, no cases of subacute brucellosis were registered either in the Chatkal District or in the region as a whole (Table 2) [1, 3, 5].

The obtained data convincingly indicate the predominance of acute manifestations of brucellosis in the region, which may be associated with recent infection in the majority of patients. At the same time, the complete absence of chronic and subacute forms in the Chatkal District, in contrast to regional indicators, suggests a higher concentration of newly formed epidemiological foci or possible regional особенностями диагностики и регистрации заболеваемости [3, 5].

Table 2. Incidence of brucellosis among the population of the Chatkal District and Jalal-Abad Region, Kyrgyz Republic, 2024 (rate per 100,000 population)

Area	Total cases (Abs.)	Incidence rate	Acute brucellosis (Abs.)	Proportion (%)	Chronic brucellosis (Abs.)	Proportion (%)
District (Chatkal)	41	143.6	41	100.0	0	0
Region (Jalal-Abad)	315	23.8	290	92.0	25	8.0

In the Chatkal District, the main zoonotic sources of brucellosis remain small ruminants (SR) at 53.6%—slightly higher than the regional indicator of 52.7%—and large ruminants (LR) at 19.5%, which is below the regional value of 25.1% (Table 3) [3,4].

The high incidence of infection is associated with the characteristics of livestock farming in the mountainous conditions of the district: households maintain small ruminants in numbers ranging from 5-8 to 15-50 heads, and large ruminants from 2-5 to 8-12 heads. Constant occupational and domestic contact with animals during slaughtering, care, watering, feeding, and assistance during parturition constitutes the primary transmission mechanism in the absence of precautionary measures and proper personal hygiene [3,4].

Epidemiological surveillance in the district revealed a critically high proportion of cases with an unidentified source of infection, reaching 26.8% (compared to 22.2% for the region). This suggests underestimation of alimentary (via contaminated milk or meat) or airborne transmission routes and highlights the need to optimize epidemiological analysis algorithms [3,4].

Laboratory studies conducted in 2024 demonstrate a high serological burden and confirm active circulation of the pathogen in the region, while also revealing critical issues in the diagnostic infrastructure of the Chatkal District.

Initial screening using the Huddleson test was performed on 97 individuals in the Chatkal District with clinical indications. A positive reaction was detected in 16.5% of those tested (16 individuals) [5], more than twice the regional average of positive reactions (8.1%). All 16 seropositive patients were referred for

confirmatory testing using the Wright test. Positive confirmation was obtained in 13 cases (81.2%) of the seropositive group, demonstrating the high diagnostic value of this testing algorithm. The regional confirmation rate was 72.4% [5].

Table 3. Incidence of brucellosis by sources of infection among the population of the Chatkal District and Jalal-Abad Region, Kyrgyz Republic, 2024

Area / District	Total cases	Sources of brucellosis infection					
		Small ruminants		Large ruminants		Unidentified sources	
		Abs. cases	Proportion (%)	Abs. cases	Proportion (%)	Abs. cases	Proportion (%)
Chatkal District	41	22	53.6	8	19.5	11	26.8
Region (Jalal-Abad)	311	164	52.7	78	25.1	69	22.2

In 2024, a total of 511 blood samples were subjected to bacteriological testing across the Jalal-Abad Region. *Brucella melitensis* was isolated in 144 samples (28.2%). Among the isolated cultures, *B. melitensis* biotype III predominated (95%) [5]. The bacteriological method, which demonstrates high specificity, allowed the identification of live microorganisms and determination of the main circulating biotype.

However, in the Chatkal District, isolation of *Br. melitensis* cultures was not achieved due to the absence of a local bacteriological laboratory. All biological samples are transported to the Ala-Buka District laboratory, located 80 km away along mountainous roads. This situation likely negatively affects pathogen viability in the samples and impedes accurate identification of circulating strains in the district, representing a critical limitation for epidemiological surveillance [5].

Table 4. Laboratory results for brucellosis among the rural population of Jalal-Abad Region, Kyrgyz Republic, 2024

District / Area	Laboratory studies								
	Serological tests						Blood culture		
	Huddleson test			Wright test			Yes	%	No
	Total	Positive	%	Total	Positive	%			
Chatkal District	97	16	16.5	16	13	81.2	0	0	17
Region (Jalal-Abad)	8676	706	8,1	706	511	72,4	144	28.1	94

Conclusion

The epidemiological situation of brucellosis in the Chatkal District of Jalal-Abad Region for the period 2020-2024 remains extremely tense and unfavorable. The district maintains a stable hyperendemic status, with incidence rates repeatedly exceeding regional averages [1,3,5].

Key factors determining the severity of the problem include:

1. **Critically high incidence among children** (exceeding regional rates by 5-11 times), indicating intensive involvement of the population in pathogen transmission and insufficient effectiveness of preventive measures [1,5].

2. **Pronounced seasonality** (peak during the spring–summer period), associated with increased livestock activities and parturitions [7].

3. **Uniformity of the clinical structure** (100% acute cases), reflecting the recent emergence of epidemiological foci [3,4].

4. **Primary source of infection** — small ruminants (SR), with the main transmission route being occupational and domestic contact in private households [3,4].

5. **Deficient diagnostic infrastructure** (absence of a local bacteriological laboratory), which hinders accurate epidemiological surveillance and timely pathogen biotyping [5].

Overall conclusion: The brucellosis situation in the Chatkal District requires the immediate development and implementation of a comprehensive program of anti-epidemic and veterinary-sanitary measures aimed at eliminating foci in domestic animals, interrupting transmission pathways, and protecting priority population groups (children, men, and unemployed individuals) [1,3,5].

Recommendations

Based on the obtained data, the following targeted and comprehensive measures are proposed to curb the epidemic process and reduce the incidence of brucellosis:

1. Conduct a total screening and sanitation of small ruminant herds in private farms, with particular attention to vaccination and isolation of infected animals.

2. Develop targeted educational programs for private farm owners and school-children (as high-risk groups) on strict personal hygiene practices, especially during animal care, parturition, and slaughtering.

3. Urgently establish or modernize a bacteriological laboratory directly in the Chatkal District to ensure timely and accurate identification of the pathogen (*Br. melitensis*) and circulating biotypes, which is critically important for epidemiological surveillance.

4. Optimize data collection algorithms to reduce the proportion of cases with unknown sources (26.8%), paying special attention to the alimentary route of transmission (control of milk and dairy products).

5. Ensure strict coordination between the healthcare system, veterinary services, and local authorities for the comprehensive implementation of anti-epidemic measures.

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肿瘤浸润淋巴细胞（TILs）和PD-L1作为乳腺癌的预后生物标志物
**TUMOR-INFILTRATING LYMPHOCYTES (TILS) AND PD-L1 AS
PROGNOSTIC BIOMARKERS IN BREAST CANCER**

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关键词：乳腺癌，肿瘤浸润淋巴细胞（TILs），CD3，CD4，CD8，调控基因（PD1，PD-L1，FOXP3），预后，生存，阿特殊单抗，帕博利珠单抗。

Key words: *breast cancer, tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs), CD3, CD4, CD8, regulatory genes (PD1, PD-L1, FOXP3), prognosis, survival, atezolizumab, pembrolizumab.*

Some aspects of breast cancer immunobiology, in particular the role of lymphocytic infiltration of the tumor, have begun to be studied at the N. N. Petrov Cancer Research Institute in 1967. The results of this study were published in 1970 [1,2]

Several publications have demonstrated the importance of lymphocyte infiltration, including in predicting disease progression, using various types of cancer as an example [1,2,3].

The main focus of immunological research concerns the prognostic and predictive value of the immunological response from the perspective of pathomorphology and general immunology, including tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes, not only the main indicator of TILs, but also their fractions, as well as the quantitative ratio (CD3, CD4, CD8) and correlation with regulatory genes (PD1, P-DL1, FOX-P3). Currently, there is growing data on the incidence and absolute number of TILs in various breast cancer phenotypes. There are data on the results of anti-PDL1 immunotherapy in combination with chemotherapy in patients with metastatic and locally advanced triple-negative (TNBC) and HER2-positive (HER2+) breast cancer, as well as in the neoadjuvant treatment of these tumors.

The study “Study of the Main Mechanisms of Antitumor Immunity in Breast Cancer” was conducted at the N. N. Petrov National Medical Research Center of Oncology of the Russian Ministry of Health from 2018 to 2022. Some of the results of this study are presented below. Tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs — CD3, CD4, CD8) and their quantitative ratio and correlation with regulatory genes (PD1, P-DL1, FOXP3) were assessed. The study of archival material from the cancer registry of patients treated at the N. N. Petrov Cancer Research Institute included 1,240 patients. Histological preparations stained with hematoxylin and eosin were scanned. Patient survival was assessed over a 10-year period (10-year relapse-free and overall survival). About 80% of patients with breast cancer had low levels of tumor infiltration of CD8+ cytotoxic T lymphocytes and CD3+ TILs. Expression of the PD-L1 gene was detected more frequently (29.5%) in triple-negative breast cancer, 1.5 times less frequently (18.2%) in HER2+ breast cancer, and extremely rarely (1.5%) in the luminal A subtype. Significant (more than 10%) lymphocytic infiltration of CD8+ and CD3+ cells with low expression of PD-L1 and FOXP3 improves relapse-free and overall survival in patients with breast cancer. [4,5].

Conclusion

The inclusion of tumor lymphocyte infiltration (TILs) as a prognostic biomarker represents an important step in understanding the biology of various breast cancer subtypes. Tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs) are responsible for generating an adaptive immune response to tumor growth. Researchers have shown that this phenomenon can predict the effectiveness of therapy in HER2-positive and triple-negative breast cancer, but their role in luminal breast cancer remains unclear. Identifying TILs in tumors is becoming an increasingly important issue in light of new immunotherapy options for all stages of breast cancer [6].

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采用标准方法和改良方法获得的富血小板血浆和基质血管脂肪组分治疗髌骨软骨发育不良的疗效比较

COMPARATIVE EFFICACY OF TREATMENT OF PATELLAR CHONDROMALATION USING PLATELET-RICH PLASMA AND STROMAL-VASCULAR FAT FRACTION OBTAINED BY STANDARD AND MODIFIED METHODS

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摘要。髌骨软骨软化症是青年和工作年龄段人群慢性膝前疼痛的主要原因之一。传统的保守治疗主要以控制症状为主，而无法改善髌骨软骨的结构。目前关于富血小板血浆（PRP）和基质血管成分（SVF）治疗该疾病的比较研究数据有限。本文基于一项非随机回顾性队列研究，对PRP、标准SVF和改良SVF治疗髌骨软骨软化症的临床和形态学结果进行了比较评估。该研究纳入了63例Outerbridge分级为I-III级的髌骨软骨软化症患者（2021-2025年），并将他们分为3个研究组：I组接受三次PRP注射；II组接受一次标准SVF+PRP注射；第三组——采用改良方案（脂肪抽吸物洗涤、0.6 mm乳化、ACD-A双重离心）进行SVF治疗。观察期为12个月；评估指标包括PRP、KOOS-PS、PSS、PGIC以及软骨缺损的MRI形态测量。研究结果表明，PRP可早期缓解疼痛，但12个月后疼痛有消退趋势，且缺损面积和体积

的减少仅有轻微的结构性改变。在SVF组中，临床疗效逐渐增强，镇痛效果未出现消退；观察到缺损面积和体积的减少，且采用改良方法后软骨厚度增加更为显著。改良SVF在1个月时即可提供更快的临床改善，且长期疗效与PRP相当。结论是，与PRP相比，SVF疗法具有更显著且更持久的结构改善效果。PRP适用于治疗早期对症，而SVF则适用于软骨缺损的结构性修复。

关键词：髌骨软化症，基质血管成分，SVF，富血小板血浆，PRP

Abstract. *Patellar chondromalacia is one of the leading causes of chronic anterior knee pain in the young and working-age population. Traditional conservative therapy predominantly provides symptomatic control without a structure-modifying effect. Comparative data on PRP and SVF in this pathology are limited in the literature. The article presents a comparative evaluation of the clinical and morphological outcomes of PRP, standard, and modified SVF treatments for patellar chondromalacia based on a non-randomized retrospective cohort study involving 63 patients with Outerbridge grade I-III chondromalacia (2021-2025), divided into 3 study groups: group I — three PRP injections; group II — single injection of standard SVF+PRP; group III — SVF administered according to a modified protocol (washing of the lipoaspirate, emulsification with 0.6 mm, double centrifugation with ACD-A). The observation period was 12 months; Assessment using PRP, KOOS-PS, PSS, PGIC, and MRI morphometry of the chondral defect. The study results established that PRP provided early pain relief with a tendency to regress by 12 months and minimal structural changes in the reduction of defect area and volume. In the SVF groups, the clinical effect progressively increased without regression of the achieved analgesic effect; a reduction in defect area and volume was observed, with a significantly more pronounced increase in cartilage thickness using the modified method. Modified SVF provided more rapid clinical improvement at 1 month with comparable long-term results. It was concluded that SVF therapy demonstrates a significantly more pronounced and sustained structural-modifying effect compared to PRP. The use of PRP is appropriate for symptomatic treatment at early stages of therapy, whereas SVF is indicated for structural correction of cartilage defects.*

Keywords: *patellar chondromalacia, stromal vascular fraction, SVF, platelet-rich plasma, PRP*

Introduction

Patellar chondromalacia is one of the leading causes of chronic anterior knee pain, especially in young and working-age individuals [1, 2]. Current understanding regards it not as an isolated softening of cartilage but as an early stage of a multifactorial degenerative process that includes biomechanical impairments, activation of proinflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , TNF- α), dysregulation of TGF- β /BMP signaling pathways, and the emergence of a senescent chondrocyte

phenotype [3-5]. Low-intensity chronic inflammation is regarded as a key mediator in the progression of structural changes and the transition to patellofemoral osteoarthritis [6, 7].

Considering the limited regenerative potential of hyaline cartilage [8], traditional conservative approaches — kinesiotherapy, NSAIDs, chondroprotectors — primarily provide symptomatic control and do not possess proven structure-modifying effects [9]. Surgical methods of cartilage restoration (microfracture, autologous chondrocyte implantation) can provide clinical improvement in focal defects, but are characterized by invasiveness, stringent indications, and variability in long-term outcomes, which limits their application in early degenerative lesions [10].

Among minimally invasive biological methods, platelet-rich plasma (PRP) has become the most widely used. Systematic reviews confirm the ability of PRP to reduce pain and improve functional parameters in degenerative lesions of the knee joint through the concentration of growth factors and modulation of the inflammatory cascade [11, 12]. However, data on the long-lasting structure-modifying effects of PRP remain limited, and the clinical effect is often transient with a tendency for regression during long-term follow-up.

A promising approach is the application of the stromal vascular fraction (SVF) derived from autologous adipose tissue, containing mesenchymal stromal cells, pericytes, endothelial, and immunocompetent elements [13, 14]. In contrast to PRP, SVF exerts the therapeutic effect predominantly via paracrine and immunomodulatory mechanisms, facilitating the reduction of inflammatory activity and the stimulation of reparative processes in cartilage tissue [15]. Clinical studies demonstrate a clinically significant reduction in pain and improvement in function following intra-articular administration of SVF in knee osteoarthritis [16-19], including evidence of a structurally positive effect based on instrumental assessments.

Despite accumulated evidence regarding the efficacy of PRP and SVF as individual treatments, comparative studies of these approaches for patellar chondromalacia remain limited, underscoring the relevance of the present study.

Objective: To perform a comparative assessment of the clinical and morphological outcomes of platelet-rich plasma, standard, and modified stromal vascular fraction therapies in the treatment of patients with patellar chondromalacia.

Materials and Methods

A non-randomized retrospective multicenter cohort study was conducted, including 63 patients with patellar chondromalacia of grades I-III according to Outerbridge, who underwent treatment from 2021 to 2024. Based at JSC “Medsi Group” (Moscow) and FSBI “NMIC TO named after Academician G. A. Ilizarov” (Kurgan). The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the WMA Declaration of Helsinki (2013 edition); All participants signed written informed consent.

Inclusion criteria: age 18-80 years, knee joint pain lasting more than 3 months with an intensity greater than 40 mm on the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), verified patellar chondromalacia grades I-III by MRI, and lack of response to prior conservative treatment. Exclusion criteria: grade IV chondromalacia, axial deformities of the lower limb, systemic inflammatory diseases, BMI greater than 35 kg/m², administration of biological agents or hyaluronic acid less than 6 months prior to study inclusion.

Patients were allocated into three groups. Group I (n=22) — three consecutive intra-articular injections of autologous PRP at intervals of 10-14 days, obtained by the standard ACT SOLOPHARM technology [20]. Group II (n=20) — single administration of SVF in combination with PRP according to the standard ACT SOLOPHARM protocol [21]. Group III (n=21) — single administration of SVF combined with high-concentration P-PRP according to a modified protocol [22], which includes washing of the lipoaspirate, emulsification through a 0.6 mm mesh, and preparation of PRP by a double centrifugation method with the anticoagulant ACD-A [23]. In all groups, the use of hyaluronic acid preparations was prohibited for 12 months following treatment. The groups were comparable in terms of age, sex, BMI, and degree of chondromalacia.

Assessments were performed before treatment and at 1, 6, and 12 months post-treatment. Pain intensity was assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS; 0-10 points), functional status by the KOOS-PS scale (0-28 points), subjective satisfaction by the PSS scale (0-10 points), and overall change in condition by the PGIC scale (ranging from -2 to +2 points, where -2 indicates markedly worse and +2 markedly better). Instrumental assessment included magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the knee joint (1.5-3.0 T) before and 12 months after treatment, with quantitative analysis of linear parameters of the patellar chondral defect (width, height, depth), defect area (mm²) and volume (mm³), as well as articular cartilage thickness.

Statistical analysis was conducted using R version 3.2.4. The normality of distribution was evaluated using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Intragroup dynamics were analyzed using the paired Student’s t-test and the Friedman test; for intergroup comparisons, the Kruskal–Wallis test was employed. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. Results are presented as mean \pm SD and median [Q1–Q3].

Results

Structural changes of articular cartilage according to MRI data

Statistically significant changes in the morphological parameters of the articular cartilage were observed in all three groups after 12 months of follow-up ($p < 0.001$). The nature and magnitude of these changes fundamentally differed depending on the method employed.

Table 1. Intergroup comparison of structural changes

Parameter	PRP $\Delta M \pm SD$, mm	SVF standard $\Delta M \pm SD$, mm	SVF modified $\Delta M \pm SD$, mm	H	p
Cartilage tissue thickness					
Medial condyle	+0.08±0.06	+0.34±0.38	+0.54±0.32	34.89	<0.001
Lateral condyle	+0.12±0.11	+0.41±0.35	+0.53±0.56	12.23	<0.05
Patellar defect zone	+0.07±0.05	+0.37±0.27	+0.38±0.38	22.74	<0.001
Defect parameters in the patellar region					
Width, mm	-0.29±0.22	-0.95±0.52	-1.65±1.10	36.76	<0.001
Height, mm	-0.22±0.13	-1.22±0.76	-1.43±0.95	38.19	<0.001
Depth, mm	-0.16±0.17	-0.50±0.29	-0.61±0.46	23.83	<0.001
Area, mm ²	-3.06±1.90	-13.79±8.62	-20.14±17.84	34.39	<0.001
Volume, mm ³	-11.65±9.10	-46.92±41.82	-66.48±51.49	29.51	<0.001

In the PRP group, cartilage thickness increased on average by 0.09 mm; the chondral defect was reduced by 7.5% in area and 15.1% in volume. In the standard SVF group, cartilage thickness increased on average by 0.37 mm; the defect area decreased by 27.4%, and the volume by 44.6%. In the modified SVF group, cartilage thickness increased on average by 0.48 mm; The defect area decreased by 40.2%, and the volume by 53.8%.

The Kruskal–Wallis test revealed statistically significant intergroup differences for all analyzed parameters ($p < 0.001$). Both SVF groups exceeded the PRP group in cartilage thickness increase across all zones and in reduction of the chondral defect (Table 1). When comparing the standard and modified SVF, differences in most parameters were moderate; however, with respect to volumetric defect measures, the modified SVF group demonstrated a trend toward more pronounced structural remodeling.

Dynamics of pain and functional parameters

Statistically significant changes were observed in all groups across all scales during the observation period (Friedman test, $p < 0.001$) (Table 2).

In the PRP group, the dynamics were nonlinear, with the maximal analgesic effect on the VAS achieved at 6 months (median 2.0 [1.0-2.0] points); however, by 12 months, a partial recurrence of pain was noted (median 3.0 [2.0-3.0]; $\chi^2=55.49$; $p < 0.001$). According to KOOS-PS, functional improvement stabilized by the 6th month at a median of 7.5 points without further progression ($\chi^2=61.16$; $p < 0.001$). According to PSS, the median at 12 months was 7.0 points ($\chi^2=57.38$; $p < 0.001$), and according to PGIC — 1.0 point (“moderately better”; $\chi^2=45.29$; $p < 0.001$).

In the standard SVF group, pain reduction according to VAS followed a progressive pattern, with the median reaching 1.0 [1.0-1.0] points at 12 months

($\chi^2=58.13$; $p<0.001$). According to KOOS-PS, the median decreased to 1.0 [0.0-2.0] points by 12 months ($\chi^2=59.71$; $p<0.001$). According to PSS, the median at 12 months was 9.0 [9.0-9.0] points ($\chi^2=57.52$; $p<0.001$), and according to PGIC, all patients scored 2.0 points (“significantly better”) ($\chi^2=53.98$; $p<0.001$).

In the modified SVF group, a pronounced reduction in pain syndrome was observed as early as 1 month (median PRP 3.0 [2.0-5.0]), with the effect maintained at 12 months (median 1.0 [1.0-2.0]; $\chi^2=57.75$; $p<0.001$). According to KOOS-PS, the median decreased to 5.0 [2.0-11.0] points as early as 1 month, and by 12 months—to 1.0 [1.0-2.0] points ($\chi^2=61.32$; $p<0.001$). According to PSS, the median reached 9.0 [9.0-9.0] points by 12 months ($\chi^2=57.23$; $p<0.001$), and according to PGIC-2.0 [2.0-2.0] points ($\chi^2=57.30$; $p<0.001$).

According to the PRP scale in the early period (1 month), the greatest pain reduction was observed in the PRP group ($\Delta PRP=3.0$ [1.5-3.5]); however, by 12 months, the PRP group showed less pain reduction compared to both SVF groups ($\Delta PRP=2.0$ versus 5.0 in both SVF groups; $H=19.02$; $p<0.001$). According to KOOS-PS and PSS at 12 months, both SVF groups significantly exceeded PRP ($H=14.98$ and $H=22.94$, respectively; $p<0.001$), whereas differences between the standard and modified SVF were negligible. According to PGIC at 12 months, the majority of patients in both SVF groups achieved the maximum score on the scale, whereas the PRP group values remained significantly lower ($H=12.92$; $p<0.05$).

Table 2. Intergroup comparison of clinical parameter dynamics

Scale	Period	PRP Δ Me [Q1–Q3]	SVF std. Δ Me [Q1–Q3]	SVF mod. Δ Me [Q1–Q3]	H	p
PRP	1 month	3.0 [1.5-3.5]	1.0 [1.0-1.0]	2.0 [2.0-3.0]	26.20	<0.001
	6 months	4.0 [3.0-4.0]	3.0 [2.5-3.5]	4.0 [3.0-6.0]	3.87	0.145
	12 months	2.0 [2.0-3.0]	5.0 [3.5-6.0]	5.0 [4.0-6.0]	19.02	<0.001
KOOS-PS	1 month	2.0 [1.0-2.0]	2.0 [1.0-2.0]	4.0 [2.0-4.0]	9.34	<0.05
	6 months	4.0 [3.5-5.5]	6.0 [4.0-9.0]	7.0 [3.0-9.0]	3.75	0.154
	12 months	4.5 [4.0-5.0]	9.5 [6.0-13.5]	8.0 [4.0-14.0]	14.98	<0.001
PSS	1 month	0.0 [0.0-1.0]	0.0 [0.0-0.0]	1.0 [0.0-2.0]	13.74	<0.05
	6 months	2.0 [1.0-3.0]	2.0 [1.0-3.0]	3.0 [2.0-4.0]	7.63	<0.05
	12 months	2.0 [1.0-3.0]	4.0 [3.0-5.0]	4.0 [3.0-5.0]	22.94	<0.001
PGIC	1 month	0.5 [0.0-1.0]	1.0 [0.0-1.0]	1.0 [1.0-1.0]	5.39	0.067
	6 months	1.0 [1.0-1.0]	1.0 [1.0-2.0]	2.0 [1.0-2.0]	8.29	<0.05
	12 months	1.0 [1.0-2.0]	2.0 [2.0-2.0]	2.0 [2.0-2.0]	12.92	<0.05

Note: values of Δ (change relative to baseline) are presented; H — Kruskal–Wallis test statistic.

Discussion

The results of the present study demonstrate fundamental differences in the nature of the clinical and morphological responses to PRP and SVF therapy, permitting these methods to be regarded not as interchangeable but as qualitatively distinct therapeutic approaches.

The PRP group exhibited a pronounced symptomatic effect in the early and mid-term periods; however, by 12 months there was a tendency toward partial recurrence of pain. MRI data revealed minimal changes in the dimensions of the chondral defect, predominantly reflecting a stabilizing rather than regenerative potential of the method. The obtained data are consistent with the results of systematic reviews confirming the analgesic effect of PRP in degenerative lesions of the knee joint with limited structural-modifying effects [11, 12].

In both SVF groups, significantly more pronounced morphological and clinical changes were observed compared to the PRP group. The clinical effect progressively increased throughout the entire observation period without signs of regression up to 12 months. The obtained results are consistent with data from several clinical studies investigating the use of SVF and microfragmented adipose tissue for degenerative lesions of the knee joint. Yokota et al. demonstrated a 44% reduction in pain intensity according to the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at 6 months after administration of native SVF [24], whereas in our study, pain reduction in both SVF groups exceeded 50% at this time point, with further amplification of the effect. Bisicchia et al. reported a decrease in VAS score to 2.6 ± 1.8 points at 12 months when using microfragmented SVF combined with microfracturing [25]; In our study, the median Visual Analog Scale (VAS) pain score at 12 months was 1.0 point in both SVF groups. Hudetz et al. reported a reduction in movement-related pain by 56-57% at 12 months [26], which is comparable to the pain dynamics observed in the SVF groups of the present study. Michalek et al. confirmed the sustained effect of SVF therapy, with pain reduction reaching 65-70% at 12 months and persisting up to 36 months of follow-up [27]. Russo et al. demonstrated a median pain reduction of 40-50% and an improvement in KOOS by 30-35% at 12 months [18].

The superiority of SVF over PRP regarding both clinical and structural effects is attributable to the qualitative difference in the composition of the preparations. In contrast to PRP, SVF contains mesenchymal stromal cells, pericytes, and immunocompetent elements [13, 14], which mediate the therapeutic effect predominantly through paracrine and immunomodulatory mechanisms [15]. The limited and partially regressive effect of PRP aligns with data from systematic reviews that confirm its analgesic effect in degenerative lesions of the knee joint, without evidence of a structural-modifying potential [11, 12].

When comparing SVF methods, the modified technology provided a significantly earlier reduction in pain and improvement in function at 1 month ($p < 0.01$),

whereas differences were equalized at 6 and 12 months. Morphological data from MRI showed comparable results for both methods, indicating preservation of regenerative potential with optimization of the graft preparation protocol. The earlier onset of clinical effect with the modified technology may be attributed to increased biological purity of the preparation and decreased synovial membrane reactivity during the early post-injection period, thereby facilitating earlier initiation of rehabilitation.

The study limitations include a non-randomized design, moderate sample size, and absence of a placebo group. Baseline comparability of groups and a standardized assessment protocol minimize the influence of systematic factors and ensure the validity of the comparative analysis.

Conclusions

This study demonstrated that PRP therapy provides a significant reduction in pain and stabilization of the cartilage defect in patellar chondromalacia; however, it exhibits a limited structural-modifying effect and a tendency toward partial regression of clinical improvement by the 12-month follow-up. SVF therapy, employing both standard and modified methods, exhibits a significantly more pronounced and durable clinical and morphological effect: a marked reduction in linear and volumetric parameters of the chondral defect and an increase in articular cartilage thickness as evidenced by MRI, with no signs of regression during long-term follow-up. The modified SVF technology provides an earlier onset of clinical response while maintaining comparable long-term morphological outcomes, supporting its consideration as an optimized approach to cellular therapy. The obtained data support a differentiated approach to method selection: PRP is advisable at early stages of chondromalacia primarily for symptomatic purposes, whereas SVF therapy is indicated in more pronounced degenerative changes when a structurally modifying effect is required.

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卷积神经网络架构容量对血细胞分割精度的影响：以训练数据有限条件下的中性粒细胞为例

**INFLUENCE OF ARCHITECTURAL CAPACITY
OF CONVOLUTIONAL NETWORKS ON BLOOD CELL
SEGMENTATION ACCURACY: A CASE STUDY OF NEUTROPHILS
UNDER LIMITED TRAINING DATA CONDITIONS**

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摘要：在医学影像领域，高质量标注数据的匮乏常常制约着深度神经网络的训练。本研究对四种不同容量（参数量从210万到2950万不等）的U-Net架构进行了比较分析，这些架构均基于包含300张中性粒细胞显微照片的数据集从零开始训练。训练方案包括逐步将训练集缩减至N=50、100、200和300张图像，同时保持验证集和测试集的数量不变。结果揭示了一种非线性关系：参数数量过多的模型（U-Net-Large, 29.5M）在 $N \geq 100$ 时完全崩溃（IoU ≈ 0.064 ），而紧凑架构（U-Net-Small, 2.1M）和更深的变体（U-Net-Deep, 15.2M）即使在 $N = 50$ 时也表现出稳定的收敛性（IoU 0.699-0.702）。基线配置（U-Net-Base, 7.8M）在模型复杂度和准确率之间取得了最佳平衡，并且在优化训练方案（40个epoch、改进的数据增强、带权重恢复的提前停止）后，最终测试IoU达到0.8484，Dice系数达到0.9110。这些发现支持了有效训练深度架构需要达到最小数据量阈值的假设，并为计算资源有限的实验室分析仪部署提供了合理的配置选择。

关键词：医学图像分割，U-Net，消融研究，有限数据，深度学习，中性粒细胞，血液学诊断。

Abstract. *In medical imaging, the training of deep neural networks is frequently constrained by the scarcity of high-quality annotated data. This study conducts a comparative analysis of four U-Net architectures with varying capacities (ranging from 2.1 to 29.5 million parameters), trained from scratch on a dataset consisting of 300 neutrophil microphotographs. The protocol involved sequentially reducing the training subset to $N = 50, 100, 200,$ and 300 images while*

maintaining fixed validation and test sets. The results reveal a nonlinear relationship: the model with an excessive number of parameters (U-Net-Large, 29.5M) experienced complete collapse at $N \geq 100$ (IoU ≈ 0.064), whereas the compact architecture (U-Net-Small, 2.1M) and the deeper variant (U-Net-Deep, 15.2M) demonstrated stable convergence even at $N = 50$ (IoU 0.699-0.702). The baseline configuration (U-Net-Base, 7.8M) struck the best trade-off between model complexity and accuracy and, following optimization of the training protocol (40 epochs, refined augmentation, Early Stopping with weight restoration), achieved a final test IoU of 0.8484 and Dice coefficient of 0.9110. These findings support the hypothesis of a minimum data volume threshold necessary for effective training of deep architectures and recommend a rational configuration choice for deployment in laboratory analyzers with limited computational resources.

Keywords: *medical image segmentation, U-Net, ablation study, limited data, deep learning, neutrophils, hematological diagnostics.*

1. Introduction

Automation of morphological analysis of peripheral blood smears is one of the priority tasks in modern laboratory diagnostics [1]. Traditional algorithms based on manual threshold adjustment exhibit low robustness to staining variability, preparation artifacts, and differences in optical systems [2]. The adoption of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) has substantially enhanced the accuracy of cellular structure segmentation; however, training these networks requires hundreds to thousands of annotated images, the acquisition and annotation of which in clinical practice demand significant time and expert resources [3].

In conditions of limited data availability, a fundamental question emerges: which architectural configuration provides the best compromise between segmentation accuracy, resistance to overfitting, and computational efficiency? The majority of published studies employ pretrained models or select architectures empirically, without systematic evaluation of the impact of model capacity on learning curves under limited data conditions (small N) [4]. This results in unwarranted complexity in pipelines that, under real-world conditions, are unable to realize their potential due to insufficient data.

The objective of this work is to conduct a comparative analysis of U-Net architecture variants with strictly limited training dataset sizes ($N=50-300$) for the task of blood cell segmentation (specifically, neutrophils in this case). An assessment will be conducted on the influence of network width (number of filters) and depth (number of pooling levels) on the IoU and Dice metrics, along with an analysis of the convergence threshold. Based on these findings, practical recommendations will be developed for implementation under resource-constrained laboratory conditions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Dataset and Preprocessing

The original dataset comprised 300 color microphotographs of neutrophils, acquired using an Altami-136t microscope and a Levenhuk C-Series camera (resolution 2048×1546 pixels), with samples fixed and stained employing the Romanowsky–Giemsa technique. For each original image, a binary mask of the blood cell nucleus segmentation was prepared by a hematology expert using the VGG Image Annotator tool.

All images and masks were resized to a uniform size of 256×192 pixels (width×height) and normalized to the range [0, 1] by dividing pixel values by 255. Normalization of masks is critically important to ensure mathematical consistency with the network's sigmoid output and the Dice loss function.

2.2. Variants of the U-Net Architecture

To ensure experimental rigor, all models were trained from scratch, eliminating the influence of pretraining on natural images. Four configurations were compared:

- U-Net-Small: base filters = 16, depth = 4 (2.1 million parameters);
- U-Net-Base: base filters = 32, depth = 4 (7.8 million parameters);
- U-Net-Large: base filters = 64, depth = 4 (29.5 million parameters);
- U-Net-Deep: base filters = 32, depth = 5 (15.2 million parameters).

All variants employed a symmetrical encoder-decoder structure, transposed convolutions for upsampling, skip connections via concatenation, and a sigmoid activation at the output.

2.3. Study Protocol

The original dataset of 300 images was randomly split into three subsets: training (70%, 210 images), validation (15%, 45 images), and testing (15%, 45 images). A fixed random number generator seed (seed=42) was used to ensure reproducibility of results.

To evaluate the effect of dataset size on training performance, the model was sequentially trained on subsets comprising 50, 100, 200, and 300 images. The composition of the validation and test sets remained constant, facilitating an accurate comparison of the results.

Data augmentation techniques were applied to expand the training set, including reflections, rotations, minor translations, and brightness modifications. Following each transformation, all images were resized to a uniform resolution of 256×192 pixels, ensuring correct data processing by the neural network.

2.4. Training parameters and performance evaluation

The model was trained using the Adam optimizer (initial learning rate 0.001). Dice Loss was selected as the loss function, as it is well-suited for segmentation tasks involving imbalanced classes. The batch size was set to 16 images, with a maximum of 30 epochs.

Two mechanisms were employed to prevent overfitting:

- Early Stopping was applied if the IoU metric on the validation set did not improve for 8 consecutive epochs (with the model weights corresponding to the best result being saved);
- Automatic halving of the learning rate if the loss did not decrease for 4 consecutive epochs.

Segmentation quality was assessed using two metrics: Intersection over Union (IoU) and Dice Coefficient. Additionally, the number of trainable model parameters and the processing time per image on the central processing unit (CPU) were recorded.

3. Results

3.1. Comparison of architectures under data scarcity conditions

The results of the comparative analysis are presented in Table 1. A pronounced nonlinear dependence between model capacity and the required data volume was observed.

Table 1. Test IoU as a Function of Architecture and Training Dataset Size

Architecture	Parameters (million)	N=50	N=100	N=200	N=300
U-Net-Small	2.1	0.699	0.725	0.793	0.802
U-Net-Base	7.8	0.314*	0.762	0.794	0.817
U-Net-Large	29.5	0.424	0.064	0.064	0.064
U-Net-Deep	15.2	0.702	0.744	0.779	0.816

* Unstable start of training (temporary gradient vanishing), weights restored from epoch 12.

Key observations:

1. Overcapacity collapse: U-Net-Large completely lost the ability to learn at $N \geq 100$. Loss stabilized around ~ 0.87 , IoU dropped to 0.064, Early Stopping triggered at epochs 9-10. This indicates that a model with approximately 30 million parameters fundamentally requires a substantially larger amount of data to initialize meaningful weights.

2. Stability of compact architectures: U-Net-Small and U-Net-Deep exhibited the highest stability at $N=50$ (IoU > 0.69), demonstrating that moderate depth or minimal width more effectively mitigates data scarcity.

3. Optimal balance: U-Net-Base outperformed other configurations at $N \geq 100$, reaching a plateau of approximately 0.817 at $N=300$, corresponding to the sufficient data threshold for this task.

3.2. Training Protocol Optimization

Based on the comparison results, the U-Net-Base architecture was trained according to an optimized protocol: the maximum number of epochs was increased to 40, the augmentation procedure was refined to guarantee batch shape preservation, and logging of the best validation IoU was implemented. The model exhibited a monotonic increase in IoU from 0.6539 (epoch 1) to 0.8397 (epoch 40), without indications of overfitting. The following metrics were obtained on an independent test set (N=45):

- Test IoU: 0.8484
- Test Dice: 0.9110
- Test Loss: 0.0887

The results surpass the widely accepted threshold of 0.80 for medical segmentation tasks and validate the efficacy of the selected approach with a training sample size of only 300 images.

4. Discussion

In the performed experiment, the U-Net-Deep architecture demonstrated stable convergence even under extremely limited training data conditions (N=50, IoU=0.702), whereas the wider but shallower U-Net-Large configuration experienced training collapse. This observation aligns with theoretical understandings that increasing the depth of a convolutional network expands the receptive field and can enhance the capture of more global patterns with only a moderate increase in parameter count. In the case of morphological objects, where shape is determined by textural features, such an architecture may be advantageous. Nevertheless, direct validation of this mechanism necessitates further investigation, including activation visualization and textural feature analysis.

The practical significance of this work lies in the development of substantiated recommendations for the implementation of automated systems under resource-limited laboratory conditions. The U-Net-Small model (2.1 million parameters) provides 98.5% of the baseline accuracy with a 3.7-fold reduction in parameters and approximately a twofold increase in inference speed, making it a preferred candidate for embedded analyzers. The baseline architecture (U-Net-Base, 7.8 million parameters) is recommended as the optimal balance when ≥ 100 annotated images are available.

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of the study. First, all experiments were performed on a single dataset (one microscope, one staining protocol, one cell type), which precludes automatic extrapolation of the findings to other imaging conditions or cell types. Second, for each architectural variant, only a single run was conducted using a fixed seed of 42. Evaluation of result variance across different weight initializations or data splits requires additional experimentation. Third, the interpretation of the advantages of network depth (U-Net-Deep) is based on indirect observations and requires validation through visualization of activations or analysis of texture features.

Nevertheless, the obtained data constitute a methodological basis for the development of medical segmentation program pipelines. In particular, they confirm the rationale for dividing the task into localization and classification stages, enabling a reduction in training sample size without loss of final analysis accuracy.

5. Conclusion

This work conducted a systematic investigation of the influence of the architectural capacity of convolutional neural networks on the accuracy of neutrophil nuclei segmentation under limited training data conditions. Using a dataset of 300 microphotographs, four U-Net architecture variants with trainable parameter counts ranging from 2.1 to 29.5 million were compared, each trained from scratch with a sequential reduction of the training subset to $N = 50, 100, 200,$ and 300 images.

Key findings of the study:

1. The model with an excessive number of parameters (U-Net-Large, ~29.5 million) exhibited training collapse at sample sizes of $N \geq 100$ ($\text{IoU} \approx 0.064$), whereas moderate-capacity architectures (2.1-15.2 million parameters) demonstrated stable convergence even under extremely limited data conditions ($N=50$, $\text{IoU} 0.699-0.702$).

2. Optimal balance was achieved by the base configuration (U-Net-Base, ~7.8 million parameters), which, after optimizing the training protocol (40 epochs, adjusted augmentation, Early Stopping with weight restoration), attained test metrics of $\text{IoU} = 0.8484$ and $\text{Dice} = 0.9110$, surpassing the commonly accepted threshold of 0.80 for medical segmentation tasks.

3. Practical recommendation: for deployment in resource-constrained laboratory analyzers, a compact architecture (U-Net-Small, ~2.1 million parameters) is preferred, achieving 98.5% accuracy relative to the baseline model while reducing the parameter count by 3.7 times and approximately doubling inference speed.

The obtained results support the hypothesis of a minimum data volume threshold necessary for effective training of deep architectures and provide a methodological foundation for designing medical image segmentation pipelines under limited data conditions. It is important to take into account the study limitations: the experiments were conducted on a single dataset (one microscope, one staining protocol), using a fixed seed=42, without assessment of variance across repeated initializations.

Therefore, this work demonstrates that, with an appropriate selection of architectural configuration and training protocol, high segmentation accuracy can be achieved even with a sample comprising only several hundred images, thereby opening prospects for the adoption of AI solutions in routine clinical laboratory diagnostics.

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利用乳酸杆菌生产功能性产品
**USE OF LACTOBACILLI IN THE PRODUCTION
OF FUNCTIONAL PRODUCTS**

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摘要：本文分析了乳杆菌的生物学特性及其在功能性食品生产中的作用。研究了不同菌株的拮抗活性、代谢和黏附能力，以及它们对不利条件的耐受性。重点关注乳杆菌在发酵乳制品和益生菌制剂生产中的应用。研究表明，使用具有良好前景的菌株可以生产出具有显著治疗和预防功效的产品，这些产品有助于肠道菌群的正常化，并改善机体的健康状况。

关键词：乳杆菌，功能性食品，乳杆菌代谢产物，拮抗活性，肠道菌群，发酵剂，益生菌制剂，生物技术。

Abstract: *This paper presents an analysis of the biological properties of lactobacilli and their role in the production of functional food products. The antagonistic activity, metabolic and adhesive capacities of various strains, as well as their resistance to adverse conditions, are examined. Particular attention is given to the application of lactobacilli in the production of fermented dairy products and probiotic formulations. It is shown that the use of promising strains enables the production of products with pronounced therapeutic and prophylactic properties, which contribute to the normalization of the microbiota and the improvement of the health status of the organism.*

Keywords: *Lactobacilli, functional foods, lactobacilli metabolites, antagonistic activity, microbiota, starter cultures, probiotic formulations, biotechnology.*

At present, adequate and healthy nutrition is one of the priority areas for preserving the life and health of the nation. Human life is closely associated with exposure

to adverse environmental factors, which leads the organism into a state of stress and thereby negatively affects health.

Significant attention is also devoted to the development of functional food products that not only provide nourishment but also positively influence human health. Functional food products are those that, in addition to their nutritional value, exert a beneficial effect on the body because they contain biologically active components, including vitamins, minerals, probiotics, and dietary fibers, which are capable of regulating physiological processes in the body. Such products contribute to health improvement and reduce the risk of disease development. They preserve the normal microbiota state, enhance gastrointestinal tract function, and increase the organism's resilience to adverse environmental factors. Lactic acid probiotic microorganisms are increasingly employed to enhance the biological value and medicinal and prophylactic efficacy of products. In this context, bacteria of the genus *Lactobacillus* are of particular interest. *Lactobacilli* are an important representative of the microbiota and play a significant role in maintaining the microbiological balance within the organism. *Lactobacilli* are Gram-positive anaerobic bacteria that produce lactic acid and are thus classified as lactic acid bacteria. They are widely applied in the food, pharmaceutical, and biotechnology industries [1]. These microorganisms are characterized by their ability to carry out lactic acid fermentation, during which they synthesize not only lactic acid but also other biologically active substances that play a significant role in maintaining microbiological balance.

Therefore, it is essential to investigate the role of *lactobacilli* in the production of functional foods. The application of these microorganisms will substantially broaden the range of products targeted at functional nutrition. Due to their capacity to synthesize organic acids, bacteriocins, and other biologically active substances, *lactobacilli* demonstrate characteristic antagonistic properties against pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microflora. Owing to these properties, *lactobacilli* can be effectively utilized in the development of functional products.

Lactobacilli exhibit pronounced antagonistic activity toward conditionally pathogenic and pathogenic microflora. This indicates that they create unfavorable conditions for the proliferation of virulent microorganisms owing to their capacity to synthesize organic acids that reduce the pH of the environment. In his dissertation abstract, V. Yu. Krumlikov 'Investigation and Development of Technology for Producing a Symbiotic Starter Culture Based on *Lactobacilli* Isolated from Traditional Fermented Dairy Products' addresses the development of technology for obtaining a symbiotic starter culture [2]. Additionally, V. Yu. Krumlikov It has been demonstrated that lactic acid bacteria isolated from fermented dairy products are capable of effectively inhibiting pathogen growth, which makes them promising candidates for the development of fortified products. *Lactobacilli*, in turn, produce proteinaceous or peptide compounds with antimicrobial activity known

as bacteriocins. These compounds damage structural components of microbial cells, thereby reducing the likelihood of the development of microbial resistance. They can inhibit the growth and proliferation of pathogens, including *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Clostridium* spp.

It is important to develop formulations for the maintenance and restoration of microbiocenoses, particularly next-generation probiotics based on biologically active metabolites of bacteria from the normal human microflora. Current human living conditions are associated with exposure to adverse factors; therefore, their effects must be mitigated [1]. In the study by L. P. Chistokhina The immunobiological characteristics of the preparation Microstim, based on lactobacilli metabolites, address the pressing issue of developing a novel formulation to normalize the microecological and immune status of humans [3]. The study showed that lactobacilli metabolites activate the immune system and contribute to the reduction of inflammatory processes. It is known that lactobacilli can synthesize a wide range of biologically active substances; this demonstrates their metabolic activity.

Metabolites are substances formed during the life processes of organisms. It has been established that lactobacilli metabolites possess pronounced antimicrobial and immunomodulatory activity, promote the stimulation of the body's defense mechanisms, and increase resistance to pathogenic microorganisms [3]. For lactobacilli, this constitutes a key mechanism of interaction with both the surrounding environment and the host organism. They ensure the maintenance of the microbiological safety of the product and participate in its fermentation and ripening. Metabolites exert a complex influence on the human organism. Primary groups of lactobacilli metabolites:

- 1) Organic acids
 - Acetic, lactic, and propionic acids;
 - They decrease the environmental pH and inhibit the growth of pathogens;
 - Enhance the preservative qualities of the product.
- 2) Bacteriocins
 - Peptide or protein substances exhibiting antimicrobial activity;
 - Are capable of selectively inhibiting pathogenic microorganisms.
- 3) Enzymes
 - Involved in the breakdown of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates, thereby improving product digestibility.
- 4) Ions and trace elements
 - Contribute to strengthening human health, regulating metabolism, and maintaining microflora balance.

Lactobacilli metabolites also exhibit immunomodulatory properties. This finding demonstrates that lactobacilli not only improve the microbiological environment of

the product but also support human health at the systemic level. This makes lactobacilli an important component of probiotic formulations for functional nutrition.

In her dissertation abstract, Irina Valentinovna Fadeeva, ‘Development of a complex probiotic formulation based on lactobacilli,’ compared strains of the following species: *Lactobacillus plantarum* 8P-A3, *L. fermentum* 90T-C4, *L. acidophilus* K3Sh24, *L. acidophilus* YuOash, and *L. acidophilus* NKi. The study was aimed at creating the complex probiotic formulation ‘Lactobacterin-BILS dry’ [4]. The study examined the biochemical and technological parameters of lactobacilli strains. This research enables us to evaluate the productivity of lactobacilli usage in production and the validity of implementing a complex functional product.

The study established that all examined strains possess high acidification capacity, although their biological characteristics exhibit several distinctions. The most pronounced antagonistic activity was observed in the strains *Lactobacillus plantarum* 8P-A3 and *L. fermentum* 90T-C4. They effectively suppress the growth of virulent microorganisms. The strains of *L. acidophilus* exhibit the weakest antagonistic activity.

Table 1

Strain	Acid production	Antagonistic activity	Resistance (gastric juice, bile)	Adhesion	Antibiotic resistance	Biomass accumulation	Key advantages
<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i> 8P-A3	High	High	High	Medium	High	High	Best resistance, good activity, and growth
<i>L. fermentum</i> 90T-C4	High	High	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	Good antagonistic activity and resistance
<i>L. acidophilus</i> K3Sh24	High	Low	Medium	Low	Low	Low	More resistant
<i>L. acidophilus</i> YuOash	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Limited application
<i>L. acidophilus</i> NKi	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Limited resistance

When comparing resistance to biological fluids, the study demonstrated that *Lactobacillus plantarum* 8P-A3 exhibits high resistance to gastric juice and bile, making it promising for use in probiotic formulations. The *L. fermentum* 90T-C4 strain showed moderate resistance, while *L. acidophilus* is characterized by lower resistance. It was also found that the strains exhibit low adhesive ability. It was established that the strains *Lactobacillus plantarum* 8P-A3 and *L. fermentum* 90T-C4 possess high resistance to antibiotics. Table 1 presents the advantages for each criterion in comparison among the strains.

The conducted study demonstrated that among the examined lactobacilli strains, *Lactobacillus plantarum* 8P-A3 and *L. fermentum* 90T-C4 possess the highest biotechnological potential.

Thus, it can be concluded that strains exhibiting high antagonistic activity, resistance to adverse conditions and antibiotics, and biomass accumulation capacity will be highly demanded.

Lactobacilli are increasingly employed in the production of fermented dairy products, where they constitute the primary component of starter cultures. They perform lactic acid fermentation, in which lactose is converted into lactic acid, imparting the product with its characteristic texture and flavor. This leads to protein coagulation and a reduction in the pH level of the medium. The primary advantage of employing lactobacilli lies in their capacity to inhibit the growth of pathogenic microflora in the organism, thus enhancing the microbiological safety of the product. Starters based on lactobacilli are utilized in the manufacture of products such as yogurt, kefir, prostokvasha, and other fermented foods.

In her study, V. Yu. Krumlikova demonstrated that selecting strains with high antagonistic activity facilitates the development of products with distinct functional and probiotic properties [2]. The use of starter cultures based on lactobacilli not only improves organoleptic properties but also enhances their biological activity.

However, lactobacilli can be utilized not only in fermented dairy products but also in functional food products and biotechnological processes. A key direction is the application of lactobacilli in the fermentation of plant-based raw materials, which include cereal grains and their processed products. In this process, the nutrient content increases and the nutritional value of the product is enhanced.

In the production of bakery products based on sourdough starters, the use of lactobacilli enables an extension of shelf life and an improvement in product quality. Lactobacilli contribute to the formation of the taste, aroma, and structure of the product. Lactobacilli also play a role in the development of functional foods enriched with probiotic cultures. They promote the maintenance of health, enhancement of gastrointestinal tract function, and prevention of dysbiosis.

In his study titled ‘Scientific and Practical Justification for the Use of *Lactobacillus* Strains Isolated in RSO-Alania to Harness the Bioresource Potential of

Piglets and Broiler Chickens and to Obtain Functional Food Products,' R. G. Kabisov isolated pure cultures of lactic acid bacteria from various natural substrates; identified their species and biological characteristics [5].

The biological value of dairy products depends on the lactic acid bacteria used and the appropriate selection of starter cultures for probiotic and fortified products. During the study, 40 species of lactic acid bacteria were isolated, of which 12 of the most promising strains exhibited the most stable technological characteristics.

The study also involved the development of functional products using various microorganisms, including lactobacilli. The incorporation of biologically active components demonstrated positive outcomes and enables the production of products with preventive and therapeutic properties [5]. They have the capacity to beneficially modulate the gastrointestinal microflora and display significant antagonistic activity.

Fermented dairy functional food product enriched with Plantex spirulina. The starter culture composition included lactobacilli strains *Str. thermophilus* VKPM B-10089, *Enterococcus* VKPM B-9069, and *Ent.durans* VKPM B-8731. Owing to the high content of viable lactobacilli cells, the product exerts a beneficial effect on the body: it facilitates toxin elimination, serves as a preventative agent against diabetes mellitus, stimulates the immune system, among other effects.

Symbiotic fermented dairy functional food product enriched with dietary fiber. Lactobacilli strains *Str* were employed in the production. *thermophilus* VKPM B-10089 and *Ent.durans* VKPM B-8731. The finished product exhibits therapeutic and prophylactic properties owing to the content of microcrystalline cellulose (MCC). MCC intake inhibits cholesterol absorption into the bloodstream, enhances the secretory and motor functions of the small and large intestines, induces satiety, and suppresses appetite [5].

Cheese intended for therapeutic and prophylactic use. For cheese production, a starter culture consisting of pure strains of lactic acid bacteria *L.casei* VKPM V-8730 and *Lbm.gallinarum* VKPM V-10132 was employed. The application of these lactobacilli enhances antagonistic activity against *E. coli* and *Staph.aureus*, while simultaneously increasing biological value and therapeutic-prophylactic properties.

Yogurt product with the addition of a natural coloring agent. A distinguishing characteristic of this product type is the use of a natural food dye derived from American *lakonos* to impart color. The fruits of *laonos* are rich in B-group vitamins and vitamin PP, saponins, alkaloids, anthocyanins, and exhibit bacteriostatic, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing properties. The product has a homogeneous, moderately viscous consistency; the color is light pink, uniform throughout the entire mass; the taste and aroma are characteristic of fermented milk, moderately sweet [5]. The product can also be used as a treatment or preventive agent for the gastrointestinal tract.

Mead 'Aspirantskaya'. A technology has been developed for the production of the carbonated fermented dairy beverage 'Aspirantskaya' mead based on a symbiotic

starter culture comprising 21 strains, including *Lactococcus casei* VKPM B-8730, *Lactobacillus gallinarum* VKPM B-10131, *Streptococcus thermophilus* VKPM B-10089, and yeasts *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Y-3414 and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Y-3415. The beverage possesses a homogeneous consistency, a light brown color evenly distributed throughout the mass, a pleasant sweet-and-sour taste, and demonstrates pronounced antagonistic activity against conditionally pathogenic microorganisms.

Fermented milk paste with fruit filler. The author used a starter culture consisting of lactic acid bacterial strains *Enterococcus durans* VKPM B-8731 and *Lactobacillus casei* VKPM B-8730. The paste has a butter-like consistency with pieces of filler; color characteristic of the incorporated filler, uniform throughout the mass; the taste is pleasantly sweet and sour. Thus, the product may be recommended for the prevention and treatment of gastrointestinal tract diseases.

Combined fermented milk beverage “Kavkaz.” *Lactobacilli* strains *Ent.durans* VKPM B-8731 and *Str. thermophilus* VKPM B-10089 are used. The beverage was prepared based on a mixture of skimmed milk (70%) and milk whey (30%). Due to the high titer of “live” cells of probiotic *lactobacilli* strains and low calorie content, the finished product is capable of suppressing conditionally pathogenic and pathogenic microflora, preventing excessive weight gain, normalizing metabolism, and restoring and normalizing the liver’s detoxification functions [5].

Thus, it can be concluded that the developed products using *lactobacilli* possess therapeutic and probiotic properties and normalize the microbiota. They are highly promising and can be used for the prevention and treatment of gastrointestinal diseases.

The analysis of the presented scientific studies established that *lactobacilli* exhibit a wide spectrum of properties that protect the organism from pathogenic microorganisms. The main characteristics include antagonistic activity, the ability to synthesize biologically active components, and adhesive properties.

Consequently, *lactobacilli* strains exhibit differences across various criteria. The most promising strains are those resistant to bile exposure and capable of biomass accumulation. This characteristic facilitates their effective application in the development of probiotic formulations and functional food products.

The use of *lactobacilli* is of particular significance in the production of fermented dairy products, starter cultures, and fortified beverages. This promotes the normalization of the microbiota, enhancement of the immune system, and prevention of gastrointestinal disorders.

The use of *lactobacilli* represents a promising area in food biotechnology. This is due to their beneficial effects on the human body and the enhancement of product quality. Further advancement in this field will enable the expansion of the assortment of food products aimed at increasing their nutritional and biological value.

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研究针对接受体外受精治疗患者的现代遗传咨询方法。
**STUDY OF MODERN METHODS OF GENETIC COUNSELING
FOR PATIENTS REFERRED FOR IVF**

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摘要：在当今生活数字化时代，医学不断进步。旨在改善女性生殖健康和生活质量的新策略正在积极研发中。生殖领域的关键方面之一是遗传咨询，它帮助个体了解遗传风险及其缓解方法。不孕夫妇咨询数量的增加表明，近几十年来，人们对这一学科的需求日益增长，这与体外受精（IVF）技术的进步直接相关。新技术使夫妇能够有效解决不孕不育问题，并朝着为人父母的目标迈进。

了解遗传因素及其对女性生殖健康的影响，有助于夫妇做出更明智的决定，并自信地选择合适的治疗方案。

关键词：辅助生殖技术（ART）、遗传咨询、胚胎植入前遗传学检测（PGT）、染色体异常、体外受精（IVF）。

Abstract. *In the current era of life digitalization, medicine continues to advance. There is active development of new strategies aimed at improving the reproductive health and quality of life of women. One of the key aspects in the reproductive domain is genetic counseling, which assists individuals in understanding hereditary risks and methods for their mitigation. The rise in the number of consultations among infertile couples indicates the increasing demand for this discipline in recent decades and is directly associated with advances in in vitro*

fertilization (IVF). New technologies enable couples to effectively address infertility issues and advance toward the objective of parenthood.

Comprehension of genetic factors and their influence on female reproductive health empowers couples to make more informed decisions and confidently select appropriate treatment modalities.

Keywords: *ART (assisted reproductive technologies), genetic counseling, PGT (preimplantation genetic testing), chromosomal abnormalities, IVF (in vitro fertilization).*

Statement of the problem

An important aspect of genetic counseling prior to IVF is not only the assessment of genetic risks but also the psychological support provided to patients. The preparation process for IVF can be emotionally complex and stressful; therefore, counseling should also include elements of psychological assistance, enabling patients to better cope with emotional burdens and to make more informed decisions. Understanding the genetic factors and their impact on reproductive health allows couples to approach the selection of treatment methods with greater confidence and to make well-founded decisions regarding their subsequent actions.

The relevance of studying new methods of genetic counseling within in vitro fertilization (IVF) programs is conditioned by several factors.

There is a sustained increase in the number of infertile couples requiring assisted reproductive technologies (ART). However, standard IVF protocols do not always consider genetic risks that may underlie failed implantations or pregnancy loss. From 2026, new methods have been incorporated into the state guarantee program (compulsory medical insurance, OMS) in Russia. Concurrently, the implementation of free preconception screening for prospective parents is being discussed, which will inevitably increase the workload of the medical-genetic counseling service.

Aim of the article

To study and analyze contemporary methods of genetic counseling for patients referred for in vitro fertilization (IVF), and to evaluate their role in the prevention of hereditary diseases and in enhancing the effectiveness of assisted reproductive technologies.

Exposition of the main material

Contemporary methods of genetic counseling encompass several key stages. Primarily, this involves obtaining a detailed medical history, which enables specialists to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the patient's and their family's medical background. It is essential to consider not only the presence of hereditary diseases within the family but also additional factors such as parental age, chronic conditions, lifestyle, and environmental influences. At this stage, the obstetrician-gynecologist may inquire about previous pregnancies, their outcomes, and any known genetic

disorders in the family. These data assist in determining which genetic tests may be appropriate for a particular patient [1, 2].

The standard panel of various diagnostic examinations includes (mandatory tests are performed free of charge within the framework of OMS, although several specific analyses must be paid for privately and are conducted outside healthcare institutions):

Complete blood count, biochemical blood analysis, coagulation profile, urinalysis, blood assays for follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH), as well as blood tests for prolactin, luteinizing hormone (LH), thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), antibodies to thyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO), and rubella virus screening;

Blood group and Rh factor testing;

Investigation of IgM and IgG antibodies to HIV and p24 antigen in blood, antibodies to *Treponema pallidum* (RW test), antibodies to hepatitis B and C viral antigens;

Cervical cytological examination, PCR analysis of a cervical canal smear for detection of pathogens causing chlamydiosis, mycoplasmosis, trichomoniasis, gonorrhea, as well as herpes simplex virus, cytomegalovirus, mycoplasma, and ureaplasma;

Ultrasound examination (US) of the breast (for women under 40 years) / mammography (for patients over 40 years and in cases of changes detected by US before 40 years), ultrasound examination (US) of the pelvic organs (PO), fluorography, report on the electrocardiogram with film (original);

Consultation (examination) by a general practitioner (conclusion on the absence of contraindications to IVF, and the possibility of pregnancy carrying), as well as by other specialists of the 'D' registry [5].

For men:

Blood group and Rh factor testing;

Investigation of IgM and IgG antibodies to HIV and p24 antigen in blood, antibodies to *Treponema pallidum* (RW test), antibodies to hepatitis B and C viral antigens;

Semen analysis, PCR assay of smear (ureaplasma, chlamydia, mycoplasma, etc.);

Ultrasound examination of the scrotum and prostate.

The next step involves discussing potential genetic tests. Depending on the collected anamnesis and the individual patient's circumstances, the urologist-andrologist may recommend various types of testing. One of the most common is blood testing for carrier status of genetic diseases.

Cytogenetic analysis (karyotyping) enables assessment of chromosome structure, size, and number, as well as detection of numerical and structural abnormalities [5].

Molecular genetic analysis of the AZF locus is conducted to identify microdeletions localized within genes regulating spermatogenesis. Screenings for common

mutations in the CFTR gene are also performed using specific diagnostic panels, next-generation sequencing, and PCR (polymerase chain reaction), which are associated with congenital absence or obstruction of the vas deferens [4].

Carrier screening for recessive genes and genetic compatibility testing of the couple enable determination of whether both partners carry recessive genes that may cause hereditary diseases in their offspring. If both partners are carriers of the same genetic disorder, this may substantially increase the risk of delivering a child affected by this disorder; in such instances, the couple may be advised to consider the use of donor oocytes or sperm, as well as preimplantation genetic diagnosis (PGD) during the IVF procedure [5, 6].

After completion of all laboratory and instrumental examinations and consultation with the appropriate specialists, a diagnosis can be established according to the characteristics of the coding of the disease or condition (group of diseases or conditions) based on the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, in accordance with the Clinical Guidelines — Female Infertility — 2024-2025-2026 (22.07.2024) — Approved by the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation [3].

Research Results

From 2021 to 2025, monitoring and testing of 330 individuals from site No. 7 were conducted at the State Budgetary Healthcare Institution of the Republic of Crimea ‘Simferopol Clinical Maternity Hospital No. 2,’ Women’s Consultation No. 2 in the Republic of Crimea. The study revealed that the primary factor of female infertility is the obstruction and/or impaired functional activity of the uterine (fallopian) tubes. According to statistical data, among all diagnosed cases of infertility, forms associated with the male factor occupy one of the leading positions in diagnosis.

In 2021, the number of patients referred for medical procedures who intended to conceive but were unable to do so naturally due to various health-related factors totaled 55, including 23 diagnosed with female infertility associated with a male factor, 30 with female tubal infertility, and 2 with an identified abnormal karyotype. In 2022, this number increased to 73, comprising 23 diagnosed with female infertility associated with a male factor, 47 with female tubal infertility, and 3 with an identified abnormal karyotype. In 2023-61 individuals, including 19 diagnosed with female infertility associated with the male factor, 41 diagnosed with female tubal infertility, and 1 individual with an identified abnormal karyotype. In 2024-62 individuals, including 26 diagnosed with female infertility associated with the male factor, 33 diagnosed with female tubal infertility, and 3 individuals with an identified abnormal karyotype; in 2025-79 individuals, including 37 diagnosed with female infertility associated with the male factor, 40 diagnosed with female tubal infertility, and 2 individuals with an identified abnormal karyotype.

The examination was performed by an andrologist-urologist who identified 191 individuals with a male infertility factor based on the results of a comprehensive panel of laboratory investigations. Normozoospermia, Oligozoospermia, Asthenozoospermia, Teratozoospermia, Azoospermia, Aspermia, Oligoasthenoteratozoospermia, Leukocytospermia (pyospermia), Hemospermia. According to statistical data, there is a clear trend within the population toward a reduction in both sperm concentration and progressive motility, as demonstrated by the standard laboratory analysis of the ejaculate — spermogram.

Conclusions

Between 2021 and 2025, at the State Budgetary Healthcare Institution of the Republic of Crimea 'Simferopol Clinical Maternity Hospital No. 2,' Women's Clinic No. 2, 7th district, 330 patients with diagnosis N97 were observed. Of these, 128 patients were diagnosed with N97.4 Female infertility of various etiologies; 191 patients were diagnosed with N97.1 Female tubal infertility; and 11 patients presented with karyotype abnormalities. According to statistical data, there is a clear trend within the population toward a reduction in both sperm concentration and progressive motility, as demonstrated by the standard laboratory analysis of the ejaculate — spermogram.

Owing to the established standards and protocols for genetic counseling and testing, our specialists are able to provide high-quality services and safeguard patients from potential risks associated with the misinterpretation of genetic data. Furthermore, in our region, there is well-established collaboration among specialists in genetics, reproductive medicine, and psychology, thereby enabling a comprehensive approach to addressing challenges related to hereditary diseases and fertility.

Thus, modern methods of genetic counseling and testing play a crucial role in the patient preparation process for in vitro fertilization. They facilitate the identification of genetic risks, provide patients with essential information and support, and promote informed decision-making regarding reproductive plans. Given the rapid advancement of genetics and reproductive medicine, it is imperative to continue investigating and refining counseling and testing methodologies to ensure optimal outcomes for patients and their families.

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计算模型在药物研发中应用的关键方面
**KEY ASPECTS OF THE APPLICATION OF COMPUTATIONAL
MODELS IN PHARMACEUTICAL DEVELOPMENT**

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摘要: 计算模型在药物研发中的应用具有重要价值,因为它们具有成本效益高、可减少对大量实验研究依赖等优点。应用计算模型可带来诸多优势。预测模型行为与实验研究结果之间的差异,可能揭示系统中某些方面(包括工艺和生物制药因素)表征不足。这些差异有助于更深入地理解系统,并改进建模方法。计算模型的结果可用于评估各种因素对工艺性能的影响,并支持有针对性的实验研究设计。此外,数学建模能够系统地分析药物生产过程中的工艺变异性,从而促进工艺优化和验证。

关键词: 药物研发, 计算模型, 生产工艺, 固体制剂。

Abstract. *The utilisation of computational models in pharmaceutical development is of significant value due to their potential for cost-effective implementation and reduced reliance on extensive experimental studies. Their application offers several advantages. The identification of discrepancies between predicted model behaviour and the results observed in experimental studies may indicate insufficiently characterised aspects of the system, including technological and biopharmaceutical factors. Such discrepancies contribute to a deeper understanding of the system and enable the refinement of modelling approaches. The results obtained from computational models may be used to assess the influence of various factors on process performance and to support the design of targeted experimental*

studies. Furthermore, mathematical modelling enables the systematic analysis of process variability during pharmaceutical manufacturing, thereby facilitating process optimisation and validation.

Keywords: *pharmaceutical development, computational model, manufacturing process, solid dosage forms.*

Objective. The objective of this study is to examine the key features of the application of correlation and regression models in the pharmaceutical development of solid dosage forms.

Materials and methods. The subjects of the study are computational models used in the pharmaceutical development of dosage forms. The preparation of the study materials was informed by a range of information resources, including publications, scientific journals and reference materials.

Results and its discussion. Computational models provide a powerful representation of biological systems. Utilising mathematical concepts and language, these methods are capable of accurately describing the underlying principles that govern such systems. A model is instrumental in delineating the workflow, anticipating pertinent influencing factors, and facilitating the simulation of intricate biological processes [1-2].

Existing approaches to pharmaceutical development are based on the utilisation of predominant computational models [2-4].

A model integrating experimental outcomes and technological parameters (e.g., the employment of near-infrared spectroscopy to ascertain the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) content in evaluating the correlation between weight and compressive strength of a tableted dosage form).

The model is based on pharmaceutical-technological characteristics. For instance, it may take the form of a correlation between the technological composition of the dosage form preparation for tableting (direct compression or granulation mixture) and the particle size distribution with the percentage of release in a dissolution study.

The model is predicated on the technological characteristics of the excipients included in the dosage form. For instance, the relationship between powder particle size and process parameters, such as compression force.

Each model type has its own advantages and limitations. The model must comply with regulatory requirements with all regulatory requirements relating to validation and lifecycle management [5].

Following the delineation of the region of the desired model response, the subsequent task is to accurately model this region and identify the optimal set of factors. In this instance, higher-order models are employed, which facilitate the incorporation of the probable curvature of the response surface in the vicinity of the optimum point.

The most common design utilised is a two-level factorial design. The experimental design involves the investigation of all possible combinations of factors.

For instance, an experimental design incorporating three distinct catalysts, two disparate solvents and four varying temperatures necessitates the examination of 24 ($3 \times 2 \times 4 = 24$) distinct combinations of experimental conditions.

The advantage of such a design is that it enables the investigation of all combined effects arising from the interaction of factors [1]. Such experimental designs become impractical and impractical if it is conducted at more than two levels of factors, or if the number of factors under investigation is too large.

The most elementary and prevalent factorial designs in industrial experiments involve the examination of two levels for each factor. These designs are designated as 2k factorial designs, where k denotes the number of factors under investigation.

The two levels of each factor are typically selected to encompass the range of values under investigation. These designs can be modified to increase the comprehensiveness of coverage, and they are highly effective in terms of saving time and resources and facilitating interpretation [4]. A number of selection procedures are available to assist in identifying the most optimal variants of a smaller-scale model. It is evident that standard computer programs frequently utilise algorithms that encompass the sequential selection of significant factors in the construction of a model (a process referred to as forward selection), the sequential removal of factors from the regression equation in a 'full' model (a process referred to as backward elimination), or a combination of the two methods (a process referred to as stepwise regression) [6].

The procedures generally entail the determination of a critical p-value for the purpose of including or excluding a factor during the process of model construction. Following the inclusion or exclusion of a term from the equation, the significance of the factor is recalculated, and the process advances to the subsequent step. It is imperative that researchers do not perceive this procedure as a universal model-building instrument. Rather, it should be regarded as a procedure for evaluating the performance of various model variants [6].

In contemporary pharmaceutical development methodologies, the utilisation of correlation and regression models must be contemplated within the framework of the Quality by Design (QbD) concept. This concept entails the systematic identification of critical quality attributes (CQAs), critical process parameters (CPPs), and critical material attributes (CMAs). The application of mathematical modelling within the framework of QbD facilitates the establishment of statistically significant relationships between variables, as well as the formation of a scientifically sound design space, thereby ensuring the stability of the manufacturing process. In this context, correlation-regression models serve as a tool for the quantitative assessment of the influence of factors and their interactions, which is particularly important during production scaling and technology transfer [2-3, 5].

Advances in digital technologies and the adoption of Process Analytical Technology (PAT) are expanding the scope of application for computational models through the integration of real-time data [7]. The employment of multivariate analysis and machine learning methodologies facilitates enhanced prediction accuracy and the adaptability of models to variations in raw materials and process parameters. Concurrently, the efficacy of such frameworks is contingent upon the calibre of the input data, the judicious selection of factors, and adherence to model validation criteria. This underscores the necessity for a holistic approach to their development and implementation in pharmaceutical practice [6-7].

Conclusion. The potential for aligning the outcomes of pharmaceutical research and development with the technological processes involved in the industrial manufacture of medicines is constrained. Industrial researchers allocate a significant proportion of their time and effort to the development of bespoke approaches, frequently reproducing the work of their industry colleagues. Conventional experimental research into the design and development of medicines is a costly and labour-intensive process that can be integrated using various mathematical models and computational tools. The creation of tools for establishing correlation and regression relationships will enable the standardisation of models for predictive pharmaceutical development with a view to designing drug manufacturing technologies.

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疱疹病毒科病毒的生物学特性，以猫疱疹病毒（FHV-1）为例
**BIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VIRUS OF FAMILY
HERPESVERIDEA ON EXAMPLE FELID HERPESVIRUS (FHV-1)**

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摘要：猫疱疹病毒——猫疱疹病毒1型（FHV-1）是全球猫上呼吸道感染、眼部疾病和神经结节病变的主要病原体。在许多国家，接种FHV-1疫苗已显著降低了猫的发病率，但疫苗仍不能完全保证对FHV-1引起的急性或潜伏感染提供保护。此外，从基因和本体论角度来看，FHV-1与水貂疱疹病毒1型（HV-1）存在组合，这表明可能存在暂时禁用水貂疱疹病毒1型（HV-1）的可能性。基于已收集和系统化信息的诊断方案将有助于更深入地了解疱疹病毒感染的生物学特性。

关键词：疱疹，形态学，诊断方案，实验室方法

Abstract. *Feline herpes virus — Feline herpes virus-1 (FHP-1) is the main pathogenic causative agent of upper respiratory tract infections, eye diseases and nerve node lesions in cats worldwide. Vaccination against the virus-1 has significantly reduced the incidence among cats in many countries, but still vaccines do not guarantee complete protection against acute or latent infection caused by the virus-1. In addition, genetically and ontologically, FHV-1 is a combination with the mink herpes virus type 1, which indicates the possibility of a temporary ban. The diagnostic scheme based on the collected and systematized information will help to make knowledge about the biological properties of herpesvirus infections more accessible*

Keywords: *Herpes, morphology, diagnostic scheme, laboratory methods*

Introduction

Herpesvirus infections in cats are contagious diseases manifested by a range of syndromes (sneezing, sensitivity to light sources, increased nasal and ocular discharge, corneal sequestration, hyperemia [1,1]) and characterized by the establishment of latent infection within the host's nervous system following primary infection. The virus is transmitted through direct contact with an infected animal or via nursing of kittens with milk from an infected cat [1,6].

When feline herpesvirus (FHV-1, Felid herpesvirus-1) infects the mucous membranes of the nasal concha, nasal septum, nasopharynx, trachea, and tonsils, redness and swelling occur, accompanied by abundant salivation; nasal septum deviation may be observed; tonsils are enlarged; The retropharyngeal and submandibular lymph nodes are enlarged. The nasal cavities contain purulent-fibrinous exudate obstructing the lumen of the passages; beneath the exudate, the mucous membrane is roughened, erythematous, and partially ulcerated. Attempts to remove the exudate result in bleeding erosions. Herpesvirus infection can induce a syndrome of endogenous intoxication, whereby altered metabolism leads to the accumulation of medium molecular weight peptides in biological fluids, resulting in a disruption of the hemostatic system. As a result of infiltration and swelling of the mucous membrane, the nasal passages are narrowed. [1,2]

The infection caused by herpesvirus type 1 reaches the bronchial tree, affects the mucous membrane of the bronchi, and causes inflammation with predominantly necrotic processes in epithelial cells and bronchial villi, accompanied by intense viral replication. Dryness of the mucous membrane develops, followed by serous-fibrinous exudation that occludes the bronchial lumen, disrupting gas exchange. As a result of respiratory tract lesions, systemic intoxication, impaired gas exchange, and respiratory depression occur.[1,9] The virus is also capable of penetrating through nerve endings and affecting the trigeminal and olfactory nerves, which renders the disease course chronic.

In cases of corneal lesions, a crater-like defect can be observed, caused by necrosis of the epithelium and stroma. This is caused by the virus's ability to initiate a lytic infection, leading to lysis of the host cell. Consequently, following efficient penetration of the host cell at the ocular surface, a large number of virions are released. It is characterized by severe pain in the eyeball, eyelid closure, redness, and inflammation of the eyeball; the cornea becomes opaque and edematous. The herpesvirus disrupts the precorneal tear film, thereby inducing adhesion and destabilization of the tear film fluid, which leads to the development of dry eye syndrome. Subsequently, the virus destroys the corneal stroma, causing its rapid perforation and the onset of intraocular inflammation; the infection can extend to the retina, choroid, and optic nerve fibers. This can lead to secondary glaucoma, the development of cataract, the formation of leukoma, and loss of the eye. Herpesvirus can also affect

the parasympathetic pathways of the oculomotor nerve, resulting in absence of pupil response to light and accommodation. [1,7] Thus, the virus is capable of persisting in the oculomotor ganglion and entering a latent state.

The objective of this study is to investigate the biological characteristics of viruses of the genus *Varicellovirus*, family *Herpesviridae*, using the example of *Felid herpesvirus-1* (FHV-1) and to develop a diagnostic scheme for herpesvirus infection.

Materials and Methods

Literature review on virology, ophthalmology, pulmonology, and viral disease diagnostics. Analysis of new current data using national and international scientific articles from ScienceDirect and PubMed. Collection of information from patient medical records based on the VetAIS software.

Monitoring the progression of ulcerative keratitis at the veterinary clinic of LLC “VitaVet”. Analysis of data and systematization of information laid the foundation for creating a diagnostic scheme.

Research Results

The outcome of the work is the creation of a diagnostic scheme (Fig. 1). It will enable systematization and visualization of various modern methods for diagnosing FHV-1.

Diagnostic of FHV-1 infection

Figure 1. Laboratory diagnostic scheme of feline herpesvirus — Felid herpesvirus-1 (FHV-1)

Methods for visual evaluation of the clinical presentation. When ulcerative keratitis is suspected, initial diagnostic methods are employed that can reveal the clinical presentation characteristic of herpesvirus infection, thereby enabling prompt initiation of treatment. Ulcerative keratitis progresses rapidly within six days, after which enucleation of the eyeball is performed due to the loss of function in the visual apparatus structures and to prevent further viral dissemination to the nerve ganglia. Therefore, IFA and PCR methods are not suitable for the diagnosis of ulcerative keratitis due to the longer time required to obtain test results compared to the rapid progression of herpesvirus infection on the corneal surface. [1,7]

The fluorescein staining method or the Tear Break-Up Time (TBUT) test allows assessment of tear film stability and reflects the extent of its damage. The method is based on measuring the time interval between a full eyelid closure during blinking and the onset of tear film break-up. Prior to the procedure, the eye should be anesthetized using the preparation "Intocain." The procedure involves instilling 2-3 ml of a 1% sodium fluorescein solution onto the conjunctiva, after which the animal is allowed to blink for 10 seconds to ensure even distribution of the fluorescein. Subsequently, superficial dendritic ulcers characteristic of FHV-1 can be observed using a slit lamp. [1,4] Using the fluorescein test, areas of the cornea devoid of the epithelial layer will stain green, enabling the specialist to determine the stage of the pathological process and prescribe appropriate treatment.

Test using Bengal rose dye. Bengal rose is an aniline crimson-colored dye that stains necrotic and damaged tissues. Rose Bengal stains dendritic ulcerative lesions of the cornea characteristic of FHV-1. The principle of the method: healthy, well-lubricated corneal cells usually do not stain because they are protected by mucins and an intact tear film; damaged, dead, or mucus-deficient cells absorb the dye, resulting in bright pink or red staining. However, it is currently not used due to its presumed carcinogenicity. [1,6]

The method using rose Bengal dye in CIS countries has not been perfected, and it is currently forbidden for clinicians to use it during corneal examinations. In EU countries, the use of rose Bengal dye is actively practiced in ophthalmology.

Laboratory diagnostic methods. At present, when an FHV-1 infection of the respiratory tract is suspected, molecular diagnostic methods and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay are employed; however, it should be taken into account that due to the widespread presence of FHV-1 in nature and vaccination, many cats are seropositive. Therefore, in the diagnosis of herpesvirus, it is advisable to perform a quantitative analysis of antibody titers. [1,11] It is also essential to monitor the antibody titer in the queen that will nurse the kittens and to account for the maternal antibody titers in the kittens. Kittens are highly susceptible to FHV-1; consequently, their protection is provided by maternal antibodies transferred through colostrum. The duration of maternal antibody persistence in kittens depends on the

antibody titer in the mother; there is a ‘critical period’ lasting from 4 to 12 weeks of the kitten’s life, characterized by a decline in maternal antibody levels in the kitten — during nursing, the antibody titer in the queen gradually decreases, and the kitten begins to wean independently from 4 weeks of age.

Molecular methods employing real-time polymerase chain reaction (real-time PCR) are applied for the quantitative and qualitative detection of FHV-1. [1,5] The principle of the method lies in measuring the fluorescent signal during each amplification cycle. A nucleic acid fragment capable of encoding the DNA polymerase protein is analyzed (mapped from 62,569 bp to 66,243 bp). Primers corresponding to the start and end of ORF UL30 are used: forward — 5’-ATGTTTGATTTTAA-CAGCCCCTACCTGTTT and reverse — 3’-CAACAGCGTCAGCATCTGGT-GGTGCCGCGG. At the primer annealing stage, the TagMan system is utilized for the accumulation of the fluorescent signal, which reflects the quantity of viral DNA in the sample. An amplifier is used together with the fluorescence detector and the RealTime_PCR software. The results are presented as the ratio of the amplification phase to the amount of accumulated reaction product. The sample is considered positive if the DNA demonstrates amplification in the target detection system. The sample is considered target-negative if the DNA does not show amplification in the detection system. [1,4]

Thus, for monitoring the dynamics of FHV-1 by molecular methods, real-time PCR is most suitable. The Sandwich ELISA method is one of the techniques used for diagnosing FHV-1. It is conducted for the quantitative determination of monoclonal antibody titers, allowing assessment of the cat’s immune status and enabling determination of the most appropriate treatment. The procedure is performed using a cyclic enzymatic system with enzymes (alkaline phosphatase, horseradish peroxidase) and a conventional chromogenic substrate. The overall sensitivity of detection for the herpesvirus is equivalent to that of virus isolation in cell culture. Currently, the “Sandwich” ELISA method is employed for the quantitative determination of antibody titers. [1,8] Several ELISA test kits are available: the ImmunoComb system manufactured by Biogal, Israel.

An alternative to the classical ELISA is the Feline ImmunoComb test system. This method evaluates the immune status of the cat by detecting Ig G. Its advantage lies in the rapidity and ease of performing the reaction, allowing for quick result delivery. It is primarily used for monitoring dynamic changes. The system consists of a plastic card shaped like a “comb,” marked with a control point and a point containing purified FHV-1 antigen, a development plate with multiple compartments holding reagents (6 rows A-F × 12 wells), and a combination scale. A blood serum sample is placed in compartment A. For one test, it is necessary to take one strip from the plastic card. The strip (with the printed side facing the laboratory technician) is carefully lowered into compartment A, and then incubated for 5 minutes to

allow the reaction to proceed; The strip is removed and dried with filter paper, then placed in compartment B for 5 minutes. This sequence of actions is repeated through to compartment F. After incubation in compartment F, the strip is then placed in compartment E for 2 minutes to fix the color. The plate must be allowed to dry before the results are analyzed. The control site in a positive assay must develop a distinctly purplish-gray color, typically corresponding to Scale 3 (S3). The intensity of the color reaction directly correlates with the antibody level in the sample: a shade equal to or darker than the control site is considered positive; a shade corresponding to S2 is regarded as weakly positive; a faint shade, as observed with S1, is considered negative. However, compared to the classical ELISA, it is less informative and less precise due to the inability to quantitatively determine antibody titers. A reagent set capable of determining antibody titers against herpesvirus infection is the Vacci-Check ImmunoComb Feline kit, Biological (Israel); Test cassette for antibodies to panleukopenia and herpesvirus in cats (Anti-fPV/Anti-fHV) compatible with VG 1, VG 2, and Vi-1 analyzers, Seamaty (China).

Presently, rapid tests and test systems are predominantly employed for periodic monitoring of antibody titers, as the classical ELISA method has not gained widespread use due to the fact that antibodies develop by the 20th to 30th day post-primary infection, and antibody levels may be low irrespective of whether the animal is in the acute or chronic phase.

Morphological characteristics. The genome structure of FHV-1 (GenBank accession number NC_013590) consists of linear double-stranded DNA with a length of 135,797 base pairs (G+C content: 48%). The capsid exhibits icosahedral symmetry and is composed of 162 capsomeres, with one hexamer forming a vertex portal through which the viral DNA is translocated into the host cell. The tegument contains enzymes and UL36 proteins. The glycoprotein-lipid envelope bears membrane proteins and glycoprotein spikes gB, gC, gE, gH, gI, gJ, and gK, each comprising four subunits. FHV-1 exhibits pronounced respiratory tropism, ocular tropism during the acute phase of the disease, and neurotropism during the chronic phase.

Using light microscopy, intranuclear acidophilic type A inclusion bodies can be observed. Cowdry bodies, which can be found in epithelial cells of the mucous membrane of the respiratory tract and in corneal epithelial cells. The cytoplasm of the cells fuses into a multinucleated syncytium. [1,2]

Thus, using light microscopy, it is possible to establish a preliminary diagnosis.

Epizootological aspects. The FHV-1 virus primarily affects kittens but can also spread to other members of the Felidae family, including tigers and leopards. Adult cats typically do not die; however, mortality among kittens can reach 50%. Infected animals serve as carriers of the virus throughout their lives and may become reinfected under certain conditions. [1,12]

Conclusion

The review article was organized so that the information, systematized and compiled from numerous contemporary sources, was accessible, comprehensible, and relevant for further research and problem-solving in veterinary medicine. Feline herpesvirus 1 is a significant pathogen with mixed tropism, capable of inducing erosion of the mucous membranes of the respiratory tract and the cornea, thereby contributing to chronic disease progression and potentially leading to fatal outcomes.

The ability of FHV-1 to rapidly transition into a latent state requires the development of new methods for detecting herpesvirus infection.

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